

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 4489–4612

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0041

Cover photo

MAHLI view of a brushed target called Copacabana, located in the sulfate unit that contains Boxworks-type features, acquired on Sol 4577. Illuminated by sunlight from the upper left, this is MAHLI image 4577MH0007060021604219C00.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity's 4489th and 4612th Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team's notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 4489 and 4612.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA’s MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator’s Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook: Sols 4489–4612*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 40 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 23 March 2025 through 28 July 2025.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report’s period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for an indefinite period of time after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 4489 through 4612 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI Team, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4489 – 4612						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Driving Southwest between Gould Mesa and Texoli towards the Boxworks	23 Mar 25	4489	0	0	7	Focus stack images from Sol 4488 were merged.
Driving West between Gould Mesa and Devils Gate towards the Boxworks	01 Apr 25	4498	7	62	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Los Osos and the target Black_Star_Canyon. The focus stack images were also merged.
	03 Apr 25	4500	8	41	3	MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets as well the DRT-brushed target Chuckwalla. The focus stack images were also merged.
	09 Apr 25	4505	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Coronado and the focus stack images were merged.
Driving Southwest between Ghost Mountain and Devils Gate towards the Boxworks	13 Apr 25	4509	26	68	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Iron Mountain and the APXS Calibration target. The imaging of Iron Mountain included a test with the aim of optimizing stereo separation for smoother targets. For the MAHLI stereo optimization test, 10 stereo sets were acquired; 5 stereo sets were acquired with translation only and 5 stereo sets were acquired with translation and rotation. A quantitative relief model (QRM) set was acquired as a part of the stereo test in order to have a high resolution baseline to compare to the acquired stereo sets.
	14 Apr 25	4510	0	0	2	Focus stack images from Sol 4509 were merged.
	15 Apr 25	4511	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the target Torrey_Pines and the DRT-brushed target The Grotto.
	16 Apr 25	4512	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4511 were merged.
	17 Apr 25	4513	7	62	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Elephant_Tree and La Purisima.
	18 Apr 25	4514	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4513 were merged.
Driving Southwest around Ghost Mountain towards the Boxworks	22 Apr 25	4518	20	20	0	MAHLI imaged $\geq 360^\circ$ of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.
	26 Apr 25	4522	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the target Hale_Telescope and the target Cerro Alto, which includes a 1x3 mosaic.
	27 Apr 25	4523	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4522 were merged.
	29 Apr 25	4525	8	64	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Bradshaw_Trail and Sweetwater_River.
	30 Apr 25	4526	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4525 were merged.
Driving Southwest around Ghost Mountain towards the Boxworks	01 May 25	4527	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Tamarak_Valley and the focus stack images were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4489 – 4612						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Driving Southwest around Ghost Mountain towards the Boxworks	03 May 25	4529	14	140	0	MAHLI acquired an 8x1 mosaic on the target Valley_of_the_Moon. MAHLI also imaged the targets Box_Canyon and Orosco_Ridge.
	04 May 25	4530	0	0	14	Focus stack images from Sol 4529 were merged.
	06 May 25	4532	7	62	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Encinitas and the target Jack_Creek. The focus stack images were also merged.
	08 May 25	4534	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Chumash and the focus stack images were merged.
	10 May 25	4536	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Crescenta_Valley and the target Rockhouse_Canyon.
	11 May 25	4537	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4536 were merged.
	13 May 25	4539	6	28	2	MAHLI imaged the targets Canyon_Oak and Jeffrey_Pine. The focus stack images were also merged.
First taste of the Boxworks	18 May 25	4543	8	72	0	MAHLI imaged the target Mesa_Grande and the DRT-brushed target Arroyo_Seco.
	19 May 25	4544	0	0	7	Focus stack images from Sol 4543 were merged.
Driving towards the Altadena Drill Site in the sulfate unit that contains Boxworks-type features	21 May 25	4546	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Cucamonga_Peak and the focus stack images were merged.
	22 May 25	4547	6	40	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Big_Bear_Lake.
	23 May 25	4548	0	0	3	Focus stack images from Sol 4547 were merged.
	25 May 25	4550	8	72	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Mount_Baden_Powell and Camino_Del_Mar.
	27 May 25	4552	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4550 were merged.
	28 May 25	4553	0	0	3	Focus stack images from the Sol 4550 target Camino_Del_Mar were merged again; this happened because a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented acquisition and merge of new MAHLI data planned for the target Palo_Verde_Mountains.
	29 May 25	4554	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Palo_Verde_Mountains and the focus stack images were merged.
Driving towards the Altadena Drill Site in the sulfate unit that contains Boxworks-type features	03 Jun 25	4559	8	72	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Holcomb_Valley and Santa_Ysabel_Valley.
	04 Jun 25	4560	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4559 were merged.
At Altadena Drill Site in the sulfate unit that contains Boxworks-type features	05 Jun 25	4561	6	50	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Altadena after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were also merged.
	12 Jun 25	4568	3	14	0	MAHLI imaged the Altadena drill hole and cuttings.
	13 Jun 25	4569	0	0	1	Focus stack images from Sol 4568 were merged.
	14 Jun 25/ 15 Jun 25	4570	12	68	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Angels_Flight, the target Ballona_Creek, and the Altadena drill cuttings. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	15 Jun 25	4571	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4570 were merged.
Driving South toward Volcan Pena Blanca	17 Jun 25	4573	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Flamingo and the focus stack images were merged.
	19 Jun 25	4575	4	36	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Tarija and the focus stack images were merged.
	22 Jun 25	4577	11	75	0	MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. MAHLI also imaged the target Copiapo and the DRT-brushed target Copacabana.
	23 Jun 25	4578	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4577 were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4489 – 4612						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Driving South toward Volcan Pena Blanca	25 Jun 25	4580	4	36	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Hornitos and the focus stack images were merged.
	29 Jun 25	4584	8	59	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Estancia Allkamari, Santa Elena, and Ticatica.
Driving South toward Volcan Pena Blanca	30 Jun 25	4585	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4584 were merged.
Driving South toward Volcan Pena Blanca	01 Jul 25	4586	10	65	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Playa Agua De Luna and La Paz. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	02 Jul 25	4587	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4586 were merged.
	03 Jul 25	4588	4	36	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Guapay and the focus stack images were merged.
	05 Jul 25	4590	6	58	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Huellas De Dinosaurios.
	06 Jul 25	4591	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4590 were merged.
At the Volcan Pena Blanca ridge	08 Jul 25	4593	11	110	0	MAHLI acquired a 3x1 mosaic on Pan_De_Azucar. MAHLI also imaged the DRT-brushed target Parinacota and the target Wila Willki.
	09 Jul 25	4594	0	0	11	Focus stack images from Sol 4593 were merged.
On top of the Volcan Pena Blanca Ridge	10 Jul 25	4595	7	62	0	MAHLI imaged the target Rio Ivirizu and the DRT-brushed target Cataratas Del Jardin.
	11 Jul 25	4596	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4595 were merged.
Driving to the Boxworks	12 Jul 25	4597	14	100	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Cochabamba and the targets Incachaca and Tejas.
	13 Jul 25	4598	0	0	9	On Sol 4598, MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 1 through 3535 (data from Sols 4359-4537) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage. Focus stack images from Sol 4597 were also merged.
	15 Jul 25	4600	9	53	2	MAHLI imaged the target Playa De La Gallina. MAHLI also imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding (sky flats). The focus stack images were also merged.
Driving through the Boxworks	17 Jul 25	4602	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Nocarane and the focus stack images were merged.
	19 Jul 25	4604	9	90	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Vicuna, Totoral and Sillar.
	20 Jul 25	4605	0	0	9	Focus stack images from Sol 4604 were also merged.
	23 Jul 25/ 24 Jul 25	4608	10	76	7	MAHLI imaged the target Paposo, the target Aqua Dulce and the DRT-brushed target La Tranquita. The focus stack images were merged as well.
	27 Jul 25	4611	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the target Tipnis and the DRT-brushed target Yura Tuff.
	27 Jul 25/ 28 Jul 25	4612	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4611 were merged.

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

MAHLI Image IDs

- This is the only official, correct, archival image ID scheme.
- Raw Images released rapidly at <http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/> do not always give you the correct, archival image ID.

0132MH0001580010101221C00

sol → 0132

camera
MH = MAHLI → MH

CDPID
a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID → 0001580010101221

product type
as received from Mars → C00

sequence ID → 0001580010101221

order in sequence
usually, first = 0, second = 1, etc. → 0001580010101221

CDPID counter
How many times the following CDPID has been used since landing → 0001580010101221

version
version received on Earth
0 = parent image on Mars → C00

GOP counter
for video Group of Pictures (JPEG video frames) → C00

Note that, for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol that the merge took place. This is **not** always on the same sol that the parent images were acquired.

The MAHLI team pays most attention to the items in yellow. In a focus stack, the images are acquired in order of increasing CDPID.

Product type tells you about the image as received from Mars; not necessarily the image you are looking at, if it has been further processed, uncompressed, or recompressed on Earth.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (Section 6).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 4489–4612 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 4498, 4500, 4505, 4509, 4511, 4513, 4518, 4522, 4525, 4527, 4529, 4532, 4534, 4536, 4539, 4543, 4546, 4547, 4550, 4554, 4559, 4561, 4568, 4570, 4573, 4575, 4577, 4580, 4584, 4586, 4588, 4590, 4593, 4595, 4597, 4600, 4602, 4604, 4608, 4611.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{uncertainty} = (p_{far} + p_{near})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

SOL 4498 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Los_Osos - after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4498MH0001900011602626C00	2626	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4498MH0003360011602628C00	2628	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602697R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602698S00								
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4498MH0003360011602638C00	2638	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602695R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602696S00								
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm											
	4498MH0008480011602648C00	2648	14901	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602693R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602694S00								

target named **Black_Star_Canyon**

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4498MH0003590011602658C00	2658	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602691R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602692S00								
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4498MH0003060011602668C00	2668	14163	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602689R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602690S00								
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4498MH0003060011602678C00	2678	14118	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602687R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4498MH0001630001602688S00								

SOL 4500 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI calibration target														
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGES TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGES.														
mhl100371	BAR TARGET - 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	4500MH0003710011602700C00	2700	14374	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl100372	CENT TARGET - 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	4500MH0003720011602702C00	2702	14370	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl100374	CALIBRATION TARGET + FRONT LEFT WHEEL + SURFACE - 30 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	AUTOFOCUS ON CALIBRATION TARGET													
	4500MH0003740011602704C00	2704	12963	30.2	28.3	-2.3	2.6	113.3	8.6	1608	1198	18.2	13.6	
mhl100374	MANUAL INFINITY FOCUS													
	4500MH0003740021602705C00	2705	12552	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	

APXS calibration target													
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).													
mhl100373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4500MH0003730011602707C00	2707	13947	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

target named Chuckwalla - after DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4500MH0001900011602709C00	2709	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4500MH0003360011602711C00	2711	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4500MH0001930001602744R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4500MH0001930001602745S00					
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4500MH0003360011602721C00	2721	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4500MH0001930001602742R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4500MH0001930001602743S00					
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm										
	4500MH0008480011602731C00	2731	15128	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4500MH0001930001602740R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4500MH0001930001602741S00					

UPDATED: 09_April_2025

SOL 4505 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Coronado – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4505MH0001900011602747C00	2747	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4505MH0001680011602749C00	2749	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4505MH0001930001602782R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4505MH0001930001602783S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4505MH0001680011602759C00	2759	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4505MH0001930001602780R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4505MH0001930001602781S00
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm												
	4505MH0008480011602769C00	2769	14896	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4505MH0001930001602778R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4505MH0001930001602779S00

SOL 4505 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Iron_Mountain – after DRT – MAHLI stereo optimization test – quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhli00190	CONTEXT VIEW													
	4509MH0001900011602785C00	2785	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhli00336	MED RES – STEREO-1 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1													
	4509MH0003360011602787C00	2787	14036	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:													
	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4510MH0002650001602854R00										
	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:									4510MH0002650001602855S00				
mhli00705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3													
	4509MH0007050011602797C00	2797	14041	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2													
	4509MH0007050011602799C00	2799	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 – STEREO SET 2													
	4509MH0007050011602801C00	2801	14032	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 – STEREO SET 3													
	4509MH0007050011602803C00	2803	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 – STEREO SET 4													
	4509MH0007050011602805C00	2805	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 – STEREO SET 5													
	4509MH0007050011602807C00	2807	14028	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 – STEREO SET 6													
	4509MH0007050011602809C00	2809	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 – STEREO SET 7													
	4509MH0007050011602811C00	2811	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 – STEREO SET 8													
	4509MH0007050011602813C00	2813	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 – STEREO SET 9													
	4509MH0007050011602815C00	2815	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-2 – STEREO SET 10													
	4509MH0007050011602817C00	2817	14028	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5													
	4509MH0007050011602819C00	2819	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4													
	4509MH0007050011602821C00	2821	14038	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 – STEREO SET 2													
	4509MH0007050011602823C00	2823	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 – STEREO SET 3													
	4509MH0007050011602825C00	2825	14041	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 – STEREO SET 4													
	4509MH0007050011602827C00	2827	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 – STEREO SET 5													
	4509MH0007050011602829C00	2829	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 – STEREO SET 6													
	4509MH0007050011602831C00	2831	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 – STEREO SET 7													
	4509MH0007050011602833C00	2833	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 – STEREO SET 8													
	4509MH0007050011602835C00	2835	14020	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 – STEREO SET 9													
	4509MH0007050011602837C00	2837	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
mhli00705	MED RES – STEREO-3 – STEREO SET 10													
	4509MH0007050011602839C00	2839	14028	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
mhli00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW													
	4509MH0008480011602841C00	2841	15177	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:													
	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4510MH0002650001602852R00										
	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:									4510MH0002650001602853S00				

APXS calibration target

NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).

mhli00373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	4509MH0003730011602851C00	2851	13944	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9	

SOL 4511 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Torrey_Pines**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4511MH0001900011602857C00	2857	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4511MH0002990011602859C00	2859	13961	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4512MH0002270001602918R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4512MH0002270001602919S00	
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4511MH0002990011602869C00	2869	13962	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4512MH0002270001602916R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4512MH0002270001602917S00	

target named **The Grotto - after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4511MH0001900011602879C00	2879	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4511MH0001680011602881C00	2881	14020	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4512MH0002270001602914R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4512MH0002270001602915S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4511MH0001680011602891C00	2891	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4512MH0002270001602912R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4512MH0002270001602913S00	
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm												
	4511MH0007430011602901C00	2901	15156	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4512MH0002270001602910R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4512MH0002270001602911S00	

SOL 4513 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Elephant_Tree**

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4513MH0003590011602921C00	2921	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4514MH0001630001602992R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4514MH0001630001602993S00	
mhl100383	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4513MH0003830011602931C00	2931	14234	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4514MH0001630001602990R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4514MH0001630001602991S00	
mhl100383	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4513MH0003830011602941C00	2941	14166	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4514MH0001630001602988R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4514MH0001630001602989S00	

target named **La_Purisima**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4513MH0001900011602951C00	2951	13027	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4514MH0001630001602986R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4514MH0001630001602987S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
4513MH0001820011602953C00	2953	14105	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4514MH0001630001602984R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4514MH0001630001602985S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
4513MH0001820011602963C00	2963	14112	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4514MH0001630001602984R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4514MH0001630001602985S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
4513MH0001820011602973C00	2973	14105	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4514MH0001630001602982R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4514MH0001630001602983S00	

SOL 4518 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 1 of 5 (performed on sol 4518)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4518MH0007690011602994E01	2994	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4518MH0007700011602995E01	2995	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4518MH0007710011602996E01	2996	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4518MH0007720011602997E01	2997	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 2 of 5 (performed on sol 4518)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4518MH0007690011602998E01	2998	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4518MH0007700011602999E01	2999	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4518MH0007710011603000E01	3000	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4518MH0007720011603001E01	3001	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 3 of 5 (performed on sol 4518)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4518MH0007690011603002E01	3002	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4518MH0007700011603003E01	3003	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4518MH0007710011603004E01	3004	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4518MH0007720011603005E01	3005	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 4 of 5 (performed on sol 4518)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4518MH0007690011603006E01	3006	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4518MH0007700011603007E01	3007	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4518MH0007710011603008E01	3008	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4518MH0007720011603009E01	3009	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

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rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 5 of 5 (performed on sol 4518)													
mhl00769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4518MH0007690011603010E01	3010	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~-612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4518MH0007700011603011E01	3011	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~-408	~-137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4518MH0007710011603012E01	3012	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~-489	~-210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4518MH0007720011603013E01	3013	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~-450	~-175	1608	1198	~72	~54

SOL 4522 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Hale_Telescope**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4522MH0001900011603015C00	3015	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4522MH0003360011603017C00	3017	13974	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4523MH0002270001603076R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4523MH0002270001603077S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4522MH0003360011603027C00	3027	13981	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4523MH0002270001603074R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4523MH0002270001603075S00

target named **Cerro_Alto – a 1 x 3 mosaic**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4522MH0001900011603037C00	3037	13029	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7	
mhl100306	POSITION 1 OF 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4522MH0003060011603039C00	3039	14058	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4523MH0002270001603072R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4523MH0002270001603073S00
mhl100306	POSITION 2 OF 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4522MH0003060011603049C00	3049	14212	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4523MH0002270001603070R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4523MH0002270001603071S00
mhl100306	POSITION 3 OF 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4522MH0003060011603059C00	3059	14176	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4523MH0002270001603068R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4523MH0002270001603069S00

SOL 4525 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Bradshaw_Trail – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4525MH0001900011603079C00	3079	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4525MH0001680011603081C00	3081	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4526MH0001630001603152R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4526MH0001630001603153S00		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4525MH0001680011603091C00	3091	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4526MH0001630001603150R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4526MH0001630001603151S00		
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm												
	4525MH0008640011603101C00	3101	14844	3.4	1.5	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.3	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4526MH0001630001603148R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4526MH0001630001603149S00		

target named Sweetwater_River – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4525MH0001900011603111C00	3111	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4525MH0003360011603113C00	3113	14024	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4526MH0001630001603146R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4526MH0001630001603147S00		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4525MH0003360011603123C00	3123	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4526MH0001630001603144R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4526MH0001630001603145S00		
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm												
	4525MH0008480011603133C00	3133	14895	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4526MH0001630001603142R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4526MH0001630001603143S00		

SOL 4527 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Tamarak_Valley** - after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4527MH0001900011603155C00	3155	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4527MH0001680011603157C00	3157	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4527MH0001930001603190R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4527MH0001930001603191S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4527MH0001680011603167C00	3167	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4527MH0001930001603188R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4527MH0001930001603189S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm										
	4527MH0007430011603177C00	3177	15086	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4527MH0001930001603186R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4527MH0001930001603187S00

SOL 4529 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Valley_of_the_Moon** – an 8 x 1 mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)				
POSITION 1 OF 8														
mhli00898	4529MH0008980011603193C00		3193	13364	14.3	12.4	-0.6	0.6	57.1	2.0	1608	1198	9.2	6.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603358R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603359S00														
POSITION 2 OF 8														
mhli00898	4529MH0008980011603203C00		3203	13333	14.9	13.0	-0.6	0.6	59.4	2.1	1608	1198	9.6	7.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603356R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603357S00														
POSITION 3 OF 8														
mhli00898	4529MH0008980011603213C00		3213	13363	14.3	12.4	-0.6	0.6	57.2	2.0	1608	1198	9.2	6.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603354R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603355S00														
POSITION 4 OF 8														
mhli00898	4529MH0008980011603223C00		3223	13307	15.5	13.6	-0.6	0.7	61.5	2.3	1608	1198	9.9	7.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603352R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603353S00														
POSITION 5 OF 8														
mhli00898	4529MH0008980011603233C00		3233	13280	16.2	14.3	-0.7	0.7	63.9	2.5	1608	1198	10.3	7.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603350R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603351S00														
POSITION 6 OF 8														
mhli00898	4529MH0008980011603243C00		3243	13273	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	1608	1198	10.4	7.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603348R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603349S00														
POSITION 7 OF 8														
mhli00898	4529MH0008980011603253C00		3253	13269	16.5	14.6	-0.7	0.7	64.9	2.6	1608	1198	10.4	7.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603346R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603347S00														
POSITION 8 OF 8														
mhli00898	4529MH0008980011603263C00		3263	13274	16.3	14.4	-0.7	0.7	64.4	2.5	1608	1198	10.4	7.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603344R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603345S00														

target named **Box_Canyon**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)				
CONTEXT VIEW														
mhli00876	4529MH0008760011603273C00		3273	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603342R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603343S00														
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1														
mhli00299	4529MH0002990011603283C00		3283	14097	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603340R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603341S00														
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2														
mhli00299	4529MH0002990011603293C00		3293	14102	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603338R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603339S00														

target named **Orosco_Ridge**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)				
CONTEXT VIEW														
mhli00876	4529MH0008760011603303C00		3303	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603336R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603337S00														
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1														
mhli00363	4529MH0003630011603313C00		3313	14071	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603334R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603335S00														
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2														
mhli00363	4529MH0003630011603323C00		3323	14073	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603332R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4530MH0007280001603333S00														

SOL 4532 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Encinitas – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4532MH0001900011603361C00	3361	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4532MH0001680011603363C00	3363	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4532MH0001630001603432R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4532MH0001630001603433S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4532MH0001680011603373C00	3373	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4532MH0001630001603430R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4532MH0001630001603431S00
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4532MH0008640011603383C00	3383	15151	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4532MH0001630001603428R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4532MH0001630001603429S00

target named Jack_Creek

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4532MH0003590011603393C00	3393	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4532MH0001630001603426R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4532MH0001630001603427S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4532MH0001520011603403C00	3403	14141	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4532MH0001630001603424R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4532MH0001630001603425S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4532MH0001520011603413C00	3413	14191	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4532MH0001630001603422R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4532MH0001630001603423S00	

UPDATED: 09_May_2025

SOL 4534 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Chumash – after DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4534MH0001900011603435C00	3435	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4534MH0001680011603437C00	3437	14039	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4534MH0001930001603470R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4534MH0001930001603471S00				
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4534MH0001680011603447C00	3447	14043	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4534MH0001930001603468R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4534MH0001930001603469S00				
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm									
	4534MH0008640011603457C00	3457	15232	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4534MH0001930001603466R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4534MH0001930001603467S00				

SOL 4536 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Crescenta_Valley** – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4536MH0001900011603473C00	3473	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4536MH0001680011603475C00	3475	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4537MH0002270001603534R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4537MH0002270001603535S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4536MH0001680011603485C00	3485	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4537MH0002270001603532R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4537MH0002270001603533S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4536MH0007430011603495C00	3495	15060	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4537MH0002270001603530R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4537MH0002270001603531S00

target named **Rockhouse_Canyon**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4536MH0001900011603505C00	3505	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4536MH0001680011603507C00	3507	14054	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4537MH0002270001603528R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4537MH0002270001603529S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4536MH0001680011603517C00	3517	14054	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4537MH0002270001603526R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4537MH0002270001603527S00

UPDATED: 14_May_2025

SOL 4539 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Canyon_Oak

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
CONTEXT STEREO-1													
mhli00190	4539MH0001900011603537C00	3537	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
CONTEXT STEREO-2													
mhli00190	4539MH0001900011603539C00	3539	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
CONTEXT STEREO-3													
mhli00190	4539MH0001900011603541C00	3541	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													

target named Jeffrey_Pine

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
CONTEXT VIEW													
mhli00190	4539MH0001900011603543C00	3543	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
mhli00168	4539MH0001680011603545C00	3545	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:													
				BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4539MH0002650001603566R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4539MH0002650001603567S00			
INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
mhli00168	4539MH0001680011603555C00	3555	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:													
				BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4539MH0002650001603564R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4539MH0002650001603565S00			

SOL 4543 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Mesa_Grande

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		
CONTEXT VIEW													INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm	
mhli00359	4543MH0003590011603569C00		3569	13006	27.2	25.3	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4544MH0001710001603652R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4544MH0001710001603653S00		
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm	
mhli00299	4543MH0002990011603579C00		3579	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4544MH0001710001603650R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4544MH0001710001603651S00		
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm	
mhli00299	4543MH0002990011603589C00		3589	13982	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4544MH0001710001603648R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4544MH0001710001603649S00		
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW													INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 1 cm	
mhli00796	4543MH0007960011603599C00		3599	15085	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4544MH0001710001603646R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4544MH0001710001603647S00		

target named Arroyo_Seco - after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		
CONTEXT VIEW													INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm	
mhli00190	4543MH0001900011603609C00		3609	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4544MH0001710001603644R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4544MH0001710001603645S00		
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm	
mhli00168	4543MH0001680011603611C00		3611	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4544MH0001710001603644R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4544MH0001710001603645S00		
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm	
mhli00168	4543MH0001680011603621C00		3621	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4544MH0001710001603642R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4544MH0001710001603643S00		
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW													INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 15 mm	
mhli00743	4543MH0007430011603631C00		3631	14886	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4544MH0001710001603640R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4544MH0001710001603641S00		

SOL 4546 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Cucamonga_Peak – after DRT														
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW													
	4546MH0001900011603655C00	3655	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
	4546MH0001680011603657C00	3657	14041	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4546MH0001930001603690R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4546MH0001930001603691S00							
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
	4546MH0001680011603667C00	3667	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4546MH0001930001603688R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4546MH0001930001603689S00							
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW													
	4546MH0008640011603677C00	3677	15206	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4546MH0001930001603686R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4546MH0001930001603687S00							

SOL 4547 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Big_Bear_Lake – before DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4547MH0001900011603693C00	3693	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4547MH0001220011603695C00	3695	14023	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7

target named Big_Bear_Lake – after DRT

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4547MH0007060011603697C00	3697	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4547MH0008790011603700C00	3700	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4548MH0001930001603736R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4548MH0001930001603737S00
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4547MH0008790011603711C00	3711	14028	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4548MH0001930001603734R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4548MH0001930001603735S00
mhl100822	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4547MH0008220011603722C00	3722	15168	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4548MH0001930001603732R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4548MH0001930001603733S00

SOL 4550 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Mount_Baden_Powell** - after DRT

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm									
	4550MH0007060011603739C00	3739	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4550MH0008340011603742C00	3742	13961	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603820R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603821500					
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4550MH0008340011603753C00	3753	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603818R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603819500					
mhl100801	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm									
	4550MH0008010011603764C00	3764	14770	3.6	1.7	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.2	1608	1198	3.1	2.3
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603816R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603817500					

target named **Camino_Del_Mar** - after DRT

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm									
	4550MH0007060011603775C00	3775	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4550MH0008340011603778C00	3778	14054	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603814R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603815500					
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4550MH0008340011603789C00	3789	14050	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603812R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603813500					
mhl100835	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm									
	4550MH0008350011603800C00	3800	15261	2.5	0.6	0.0	0.1	15.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.5	1.9
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603810R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4552MH0001630001603811500					
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4553MH0001930001603822R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4553MH0001930001603823500					

UPDATED: 30_May_2025

SOL 4554 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Palo_Verde_Mountains													
mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm										
	4554MH0003590011603829C00	3829	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4554MH0001930001603862R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4554MH0001930001603863S00					
mhl00152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4554MH0001520011603839C00	3839	14180	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4554MH0001930001603860R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4554MH0001930001603861S00					
mhl00152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4554MH0001520011603849C00	3849	14184	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4554MH0001930001603858R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4554MH0001930001603859S00					

SOL 4559 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Holcomb_Valley** - after DRT

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4559MH0007060011603865C00	3865	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4559MH0008790011603868C00	3868	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603946R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4560MH0001630001603947S00
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4559MH0008790011603879C00	3879	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603944R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4560MH0001630001603945S00
mhl100822	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm											
	4559MH0008220011603890C00	3890	14919	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603942R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4560MH0001630001603943S00

target named **Santa_Ysabel_Valley** - after DRT

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4559MH0007060011603901C00	3901	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4559MH0008790011603904C00	3904	14033	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603940R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4560MH0001630001603941S00
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4559MH0008790011603915C00	3915	14028	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603938R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4560MH0001630001603939S00
mhl100822	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm											
	4559MH0008220011603926C00	3926	14935	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603936R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4560MH0001630001603937S00

SOL 4561 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named **Altadena** - after DRT

mhl00706	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
	4561MH0007060011603949C00	3949	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4561MH0008790011603952C00	3952	14045	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4561MH0001530001604004R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4561MH0001530001604005S00	
mhl00879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4561MH0008790011603963C00	3963	14036	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4561MH0001530001604002R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4561MH0001530001604003S00	
mhl00879	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4561MH0008790011603974C00	3974	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4561MH0001530001604000R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4561MH0001530001604001S00	
mhl00822	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4561MH0008220011603985C00	3985	14966	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4561MH0001530001603998R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4561MH0001530001603999S00	

intended drill target named **Altadena** - after drill bit pre-load test

mhl00881	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 35 cm											
	4561MH0008810011603996C00	3996	12897	36.3	34.4	-3.2	3.9	134.5	12.5	1608	1198	21.6	16.1

UPDATED: 13_June_2025

SOL 4568 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Altadena drill hole

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100197	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4568MH0001970011604007C00	4007	13029	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
mhl100774	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 10 cm											
	4568MH0007740011604009C00	4009	13573	10.8	8.9	-0.3	0.3	45.0	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.4

Altadena drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4568MH0001520011604011C00	4011	13984	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4569MH0002580001604020R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4569MH0002580001604021S00					

SOL 4570 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/R6.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Angels_Flight** – after DRT

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4570MH0007060011604023C00	4023	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4570MH0008790011604026C00	4026	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4571MH0002270001604098R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4571MH0002270001604099S00		
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4570MH0008790011604037C00	4037	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4571MH0002270001604096R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4571MH0002270001604097S00		
mhl100822	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm											
	4570MH0008220011604048C00	4048	14893	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4571MH0002270001604094R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4571MH0002270001604095S00		

target named **Ballona_Creek**

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4570MH0007060011604059C00	4059	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4570MH0008340011604062C00	4062	14113	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4571MH0002270001604092R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4571MH0002270001604093S00	
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4570MH0008340011604073C00	4073	14113	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4571MH0002270001604090R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4571MH0002270001604091S00	

Altadena drill hole cuttings

mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4570MH0001220011604084C00	4084	13979	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO MESH IS 12.4 cm; TO FUNNEL THROAT IS 16.3 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl100312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 1 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT		INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm										
	MANUAL FOCUS	4570MH0003120001604085C00	4085	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 2 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT		INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm										
	MANUAL FOCUS	4570MH0003260001604086C00	4086	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT		INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm										
	MANUAL FOCUS	4570MH0003260001604087C00	4087	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT		INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm										
	MANUAL FOCUS	4570MH0003260001604088C00	4088	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – overview of entire inlet

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO INLET IS ~19 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl100228	MANUAL FOCUS		INTENDED DISTANCE: ~19 cm										
	4570MH0002280001604089C00	4089	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

UPDATED: 18_June_2025

SOL 4573 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Flamingo															
mhl00876	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4573MH0008760011604101C00	4101	13005	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4573MH0001930001604134R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4573MH0001930001604135S00	
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4573MH0002240011604111C00	4111	13892	7.6	5.7	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	1608	1198	5.4	4.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4573MH0001930001604132R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4573MH0001930001604133S00	
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4573MH0002240011604121C00	4121	13932	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4573MH0001930001604130R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4573MH0001930001604131S00	

UPDATED: 20_June_2025

SOL 4575 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Tarija – after DRT															
mhlI00706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4575MH0007060011604137C00	4137	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhlI00834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4575MH0008340011604140C00	4140	14051	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4575MH0001930001604176R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4575MH0001930001604177S00
mhlI00834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4575MH0008340011604151C00	4151	14049	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4575MH0001930001604174R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4575MH0001930001604175S00
mhlI00835	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm												
	4575MH0008350011604162C00	4162	14976	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4575MH0001930001604172R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4575MH0001930001604173S00

SOL 4577 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI calibration target														
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGES TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGES.														
mhl100371	BAR TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	4577MH0003710011604179C00	4179	14374	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl100372	CENT TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	4577MH0003720011604181C00	4181	14369	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl100374	CALIBRATION TARGET + FRONT LEFT WHEEL + SURFACE – 30 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	AUTOFOCUS ON CALIBRATION TARGET													
	4577MH0003740011604183C00	4183	12963	30.2	28.3	-2.3	2.6	113.3	8.6	1608	1198	18.2	13.6	
mhl100374	MANUAL INFINITY FOCUS													
	4577MH0003740021604184C00	4184	12552	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	

APXS calibration target														
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).														
mhl100373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	4577MH0003730011604186C00	4186	13946	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9	

target named Copiapo														
mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4577MH0008760011604188C00	4188	12991	28.2	26.3	-2.0	2.3	106.1	7.5	1608	1198	17.1	12.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604263R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604264S00						
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4577MH0002990011604198C00	4198	13883	7.7	5.8	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	1608	1198	5.5	4.1	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604261R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604262S00						
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4577MH0002990011604208C00	4208	13910	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	4.0	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604259R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604260S00						

target named Copacabana – after DRT														
mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4577MH0007060011604218C00	4218	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4577MH0008340011604221C00	4221	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604257R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604258S00						
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4577MH0008340011604232C00	4232	14041	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604255R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604256S00						
mhl100835	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	4577MH0008350011604243C00	4243	15221	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604253R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4578MH0001630001604254S00						

UPDATED: 25_June_2025

SOL 4580 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Hornitos - after DRT															
mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4580MH0007060011604266C00	4266	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4580MH0008790011604269C00	4269	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4580MH0001930001604305R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4580MH0001930001604306S00	
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4580MH0008790011604280C00	4280	14043	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4580MH0001930001604303R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4580MH0001930001604304S00	
mhl100835	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm												
	4580MH0008350011604291C00	4291	15234	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4580MH0001930001604301R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4580MH0001930001604302S00	

SOL 4584 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Estancia_Alkkamari

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhlI00706	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4584MH0007060011604308C00	4308	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhlI00554	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4584MH0005540011604311C00	4311	13976	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
mhlI00554	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4584MH0005540011604314C00	4314	13980	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8

target named Santa_Elena

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhlI00879	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4584MH0008760011604317C00	4317	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604374R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604375S00					
mhlI00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4584MH0001820011604327C00	4327	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604372R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604373S00					
mhlI00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4584MH0001820011604337C00	4337	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604370R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604371S00					

target named Ticatica

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhlI00865	CONTEXT VIEW STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4584MH0008650011604347C00	4347	13003	27.4	25.5	-1.9	2.1	103.3	7.1	1608	1198	16.6	12.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604368R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604369S00					
mhlI00865	CONTEXT VIEW STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4584MH0008650011604357C00	4357	12994	28.0	26.1	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	1608	1198	17.0	12.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604366R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604367S00					

SOL 4586 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

*NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (COPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Playa_Agua_De_Luna**

mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm													
	4586MH0008760011604377C00	4377	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4587MH0001630001604451R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4587MH0001630001604452S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	4586MH0001730011604387C00	4387	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4587MH0001630001604449R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4587MH0001630001604450S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	4586MH0001730011604397C00	4397	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4587MH0001630001604447R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4587MH0001630001604448S00	

target named **La_Paz**

mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm													
	4586MH0008760011604407C00	4407	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4587MH0001630001604445R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4587MH0001630001604446S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	4586MH0001730011604417C00	4417	13980	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4587MH0001630001604443R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4587MH0001630001604444S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	4586MH0001730011604427C00	4427	13986	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4587MH0001630001604441R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4587MH0001630001604442S00	

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO MESH IS 12.4 cm; TO FUNNEL THROAT IS 16.3 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl100312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 1 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	4586MH0003120001604436C00	4436	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
	IMAGE FOCUSED AT MESH												
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 2 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	4586MH0003260001604438C00	4438	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
mhl100326	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	4586MH0003260001604439C00	4439	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – overview of entire inlet

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO INLET IS ~19 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl100228	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE: ~19 cm											
4586MH0002280001604440C00	4440	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9	

UPDATED: 03_July_2025

SOL 4588 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Guapay – after DRT														
mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW													
	4588MH0007060011604454C00	4454	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
	4588MH0008790011604457C00	4457	14044	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4588MH0001930001604493R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4588MH0001930001604494S00								
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
	4588MH0008790011604468C00	4468	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4588MH0001930001604491R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4588MH0001930001604492S00								
mhl100835	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW													
	4588MH0008350011604479C00	4479	15163	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4588MH0001930001604489R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4588MH0001930001604490S00								

SOL 4590 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Huellas_De_Dinosaurios** – after DRT

mhl00706	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4590MH0007060011604496C00	4496	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4590MH0008340011604499C00	4499	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4591MH0002270001604561R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4591MH0002270001604562S00	
mhl00834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4590MH0008340011604510C00	4510	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4591MH0002270001604559R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4591MH0002270001604560S00	
mhl00834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4590MH0008340011604521C00	4521	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4591MH0002270001604557R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4591MH0002270001604558S00	
mhl00801	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4590MH0008010011604532C00	4532	14985	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4591MH0002270001604555R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4591MH0002270001604556S00	
mhl00801	HIGH-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4590MH0008010011604543C00	4543	15012	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4591MH0002270001604553R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4591MH0002270001604554S00	

SOL 4593 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Pan_De_Azucar – a 3 x 1 mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
target named Pan_De_Azucar – a 3 x 1 mosaic										
mhlI00899	POSITION 1 OF 3									
	4593MH0008990011604564C00	4564	12796	51.5	49.6	-6.3	8.3	188.3	25.7	1608 1198 30.3 22.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504693R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001404694S00										
mhlI00899	POSITION 2 OF 3									
	4593MH0008990011604574C00	4574	12896	36.4	34.5	-3.2	3.9	134.9	12.6	1608 1198 21.7 16.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504691R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504692S00										
mhlI00899	POSITION 3 OF 3									
	4593MH0008990011604584C00	4584	12936	32.5	30.6	-2.6	3.1	121.1	10.0	1608 1198 19.5 14.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504689R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504690S00										

target named Parinacota – after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
target named Parinacota – after DRT										
mhlI00359	CONTEXT VIEW									
	4593MH0003590011604594C00	4594	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608 1198 16.1 12.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504687R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504688S00										
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1									
	4593MH0001680011604604C00	4604	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608 1198 5.0 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504685R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504686S00										
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2									
	4593MH0001680011604614C00	4614	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608 1198 5.0 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504683R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504684S00										
mhlI00864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW									
	4593MH0008640011604624C00	4624	15000	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	1608 1198 2.8 2.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504681R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504682S00										

target named Wila_Willki

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
target named Wila_Willki										
mhlI00865	CONTEXT VIEW									
	4593MH0008650011604634C00	4634	13010	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	1608 1198 16.4 12.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504679R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504680S00										
mhlI00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1									
	4593MH0002240011604644C00	4644	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608 1198 5.1 3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504677R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504678S00										
mhlI00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2									
	4593MH0002240011604654C00	4654	13956	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608 1198 5.2 3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504675R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504676S00										
mhlI00335	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW									
	4593MH0003350011604664C00	4664	14590	4.1	2.2	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	1608 1198 3.4 2.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504673R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4594MH0004490001504674S00										

SOL 4595 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Rio_Ivirizu**

mhlI00359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4595MH0003590011404696C00	4696	13033	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4596MH0001630001004767R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4596MH0001630001004768S00	
mhlI00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4595MH0002240011404706C00	4706	14277	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4596MH0001630001004765R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4596MH0001630001004766S00	
mhlI00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4595MH0002240011404716C00	4716	14280	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4596MH0001630001004763R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4596MH0001630001004764S00	

target named **Cataratas_Del_Jardin – after DRT**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4595MH0001900011404726C00	4726	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4595MH0003360011404728C00	4728	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4596MH0001630001104761R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4596MH0001630001104762S00	
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4595MH0003360011204738C00	4738	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4596MH0001630001104759R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4596MH0001630001104760S00	
mhlI00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm													
	4595MH0008480011204748C00	4748	14835	3.4	1.5	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4596MH0001630001104757R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4596MH0001630001104758S00	

SOL 4597 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/R6.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Cochabamba – after DRT – quantitative relief model (QRM) data

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
CONTEXT VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
mhli00190	4597MH0001900011004770C00	4770	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
MED RES – STEREO-1 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00336	4597MH0003360011004772C00	4772	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700017R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700018S00													
MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00336	4597MH0003360011004782C00	4782	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700015R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700016S00													
MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00705	4597MH0007050011004792C00	4792	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00705	4597MH0007050011004794C00	4794	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00705	4597MH0007050011004796C00	4796	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
mhli00848	4597MH0008480011004798C00	4798	15069	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700013R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700014S00													

target named Incachaca

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
CONTEXT VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
mhli00190	4597MH0001900011004808C00	4808	13009	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00308	4597MH0003080011004810C00	4810	13966	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700011R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700012S00													
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00308	4597MH0003080011004820C00	4820	13975	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700009R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700010S00													
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
mhli00357	4597MH0003570010904830C00	4830	14624	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700007R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700008S00													

target named Tejas

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
CONTEXT VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
mhli00876	4597MH0008760010904840C00	4840	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700005R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700006S00													
INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1 INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm													
mhli00878	4597MH0008780010804850C00	4850	13517	11.6	9.7	-0.4	0.4	47.7	1.3	1608	1198	7.7	5.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700003R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700004S00													
INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2 INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm													
mhli00878	4597MH0008780010604860C00	4860	13525	11.5	9.6	-0.4	0.4	47.3	1.3	1608	1198	7.6	5.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001800001R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4598MH0005360001700002S00													

SOL 4600 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Playa_De_La_Gallina**

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW													
	4600MH0007060011700020C00	20	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100900	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
	4600MH0009000011700023C00	23	13529	11.4	9.5	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	1608	1198	7.6	5.6	
mhl100900	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
	4600MH0009000011700026C00	26	13526	11.5	9.6	-0.4	0.4	47.3	1.3	1608	1198	7.6	5.7	
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
	4600MH0008790011700029C00	29	14057	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:													
	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4600MH0007030001700074R00										
	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:													
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
	4600MH0008790011700040C00	40	14067	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:													
	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4600MH0007030001700072R00										
	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:													

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - first set

NOTE: WHERE THE MOTOR COUNT IS GIVEN IN BLUE FONT, THE DUST COVER WAS CLOSED DURING THE IMAGING; PLEASE USE CAUTION IN INTERPRETING THE RANGE AND SCALE INFORMATION, AS THE RESULTS ARE LESS CERTAIN.

mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0007120001700050C00	50	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0007120011700051C00	51	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0007120021700052C00	52	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
4600MH0007120031700053C00	53	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		
	INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0007120041700054C00	54	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - first set

mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530001700055C00	55	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530011700056C00	56	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530021700057C00	57	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
4600MH0004530031700058C00	58	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		
	PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT - ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530041700059C00	59	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530051700060C00	60	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530001700061C00	61	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530011700062C00	62	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530021700063C00	63	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
4600MH0004530031700064C00	64	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		
	PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT - ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530041700065C00	65	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
	4600MH0004530051700066C00	66	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

Continued on Next Page..

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)													
NOTE: WHERE THE MOTOR COUNT IS GIVEN IN BLUE FONT, THE DUST COVER WAS CLOSED DURING THE IMAGING; PLEASE USE CAUTION IN INTERPRETING THE RANGE AND SCALE INFORMATION, AS THE RESULTS ARE LESS CERTAIN.													
mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4600#H0007120001700067C00	67	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4600#H0007120011700068C00	68	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4600#H0007120021700069C00	69	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4600#H0007120031700070C00	70	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4600#H0007120041700071C00	71	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a

UPDATED: 18_July_2025

SOL 4602 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Nocarane															
mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4602MH0003590011700077C00	77	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4602MH0001930001700110R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4602MH0001930001700111S00	
mhl00173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4602MH0001730011700087C00	87	14160	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4602MH0001930001700108R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4602MH0001930001700109S00	
mhl00173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4602MH0001730011700097C00	97	14167	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4602MH0001930001700106R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4602MH0001930001700107S00	

SOL 4604 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Vicuna

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4604MH0003590011700113C00	113	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4605MH0005360001700218R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4605MH0005360001700219S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4604MH0002240011700123C00	123	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4605MH0005360001700216R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4605MH0005360001700217S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4604MH0002240011700133C00	133	14024	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4605MH0005360001700214R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4605MH0005360001700215S00					

target named Totoral

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4604MH0003590011700143C00	143	13004	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	1608	1198	16.6	12.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4605MH0005360001700212R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4605MH0005360001700213S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4604MH0002240011700153C00	153	13911	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	4.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4605MH0005360001700210R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4605MH0005360001700211S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4604MH0002240011700163C00	163	13922	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4605MH0005360001700208R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4605MH0005360001700209S00					

target named Sillar

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4604MH0003590011700173C00	173	13006	27.2	25.3	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4605MH0005360001700206R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4605MH0005360001700207S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4604MH0002240011700183C00	183	13887	7.6	5.7	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	1608	1198	5.4	4.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4605MH0005360001700204R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4605MH0005360001700205S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4604MH0002240011700193C00	193	13914	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	4.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4605MH0005360001700202R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4605MH0005360001700203S00					

SOL 4608 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Paposo

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4608MH0001900011700221C00	221	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4608MH0001730011700223C00	223	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4608MH0001710001700308R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4608MH0001710001700309S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4608MH0001730011700233C00	233	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4608MH0001710001700306R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4608MH0001710001700307S00	

target named Aqua_Dulce

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4608MH0001900011700243C00	243	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4608MH0003360011700245C00	245	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4608MH0001710001700304R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4608MH0001710001700305S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4608MH0003360011700255C00	255	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4608MH0001710001700302R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4608MH0001710001700303S00	

target named La_Tranquita – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4608MH0001900011700265C00	265	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4608MH0001680011700267C00	267	13986	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4608MH0001710001700300R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4608MH0001710001700301S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4608MH0001680011700277C00	277	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4608MH0001710001700298R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4608MH0001710001700299S00	
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm												
	4608MH0007430011700287C00	287	14905	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4608MH0001710001700296R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4608MH0001710001700297S00	

SOL 4611 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Tipnis**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4611MH0001900011700311C00	311	13038	25.3	23.4	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.5		
mhlI00173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4611MH0001730011700313C00	313	14272	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4612MH0002270001700372R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4612MH0002270001700373S00	
mhlI00173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4611MH0001730011700323C00	323	14259	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4612MH0002270001700370R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4612MH0002270001700371S00	

target named **Yura_Tuff – after DRT**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4611MH0001900011700333C00	333	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4611MH0001680011700335C00	335	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4612MH0002270001700368R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4612MH0002270001700369S00	
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4611MH0001680011700345C00	345	14022	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4612MH0002270001700366R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4612MH0002270001700367S00	
mhlI00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm													
	4611MH0007430011700355C00	355	14912	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4612MH0002270001700364R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4612MH0002270001700365S00	

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);

15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and
16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow-colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow-colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange-colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI or on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 4489–4612 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 4498, 4500, 4505, 4509, 4511, 4513, 4522, 4525, 4527, 4529, 4532, 4534, 4536, 4539, 4543, 4546, 4547, 4550, 4554, 4559, 4561, 4568, 4570, 4573, 4575, 4577, 4580, 4584, 4586, 4588, 4590, 4593, 4595, 4597, 4600, 4602, 4604, 4608, 4611**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus

position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green-colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3**, **Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the

second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange-colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 71 to 138, then only four of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocus (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the

motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2 (Equations 1 and 3, respectively)**. Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

UPDATED: 03_April_2025

SOL 4498 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Los_Osos - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4498MH0003360011602628C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4498MH0001630001602697R00	2697	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4498MH0001630001602698S00	2698	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4498	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4498		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4498MH0003360021602629C00	2629	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4498MH0003360021602630C00	2630	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4498MH0003360021602631C00	2631	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4498MH0003360021602632C00	2632	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4498MH0003360021602633C00	2633	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4498MH0003360021602634C00	2634	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4498MH0003360021602635C00	2635	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4498MH0003360021602636C00	2636	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_April_2025

SOL 4498 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Los_Osos - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4498MH0003360011602638C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4498MH0001630001602695R00	2695	MOTOR COUNT:		14007	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4498MH0001630001602696S00	2696	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4498	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4498		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4498MH0003360021602639C00	2639	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
4498MH0003360021602640C00	2640	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4498MH0003360021602641C00	2641	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4498MH0003360021602642C00	2642	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4498MH0003360021602643C00	2643	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4498MH0003360021602644C00	2644	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4498MH0003360021602645C00	2645	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4498MH0003360021602646C00	2646	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_April_2025

SOL 4498 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Los_Osos - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4498MH0008480011602648C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4498MH0001630001602693R00	2693	MOTOR COUNT:		14901	RANGE (cm):	3.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4498MH0001630001602694S00	2694	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4498	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4498		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4498MH0008480021602649C00	2649	14805	3.50	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	255	1
4498MH0008480021602650C00	2650	14829	3.44	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	223	2
4498MH0008480021602651C00	2651	14853	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	191	3
4498MH0008480021602652C00	2652	14877	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	159	4
4498MH0008480021602653C00	2653	14901	3.26	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	127	5
4498MH0008480021602654C00	2654	14925	3.21	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	95	6
4498MH0008480021602655C00	2655	14949	3.15	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	63	7
4498MH0008480021602656C00	2656	14973	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_April_2025

SOL 4498 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Black_Star_Canyon - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4498MH0003590011602658C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4498MH0001630001602691R00	2691	MOTOR COUNT:		13021	RANGE (cm):	26.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4498MH0001630001602692S00	2692	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4498	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4498		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4498MH0003590021602659C00	2659	12949	31.34	-2.4	2.9	117.2	9.3	255	1
4498MH0003590021602660C00	2660	12967	29.92	-2.2	2.6	112.2	8.5	223	2
4498MH0003590021602661C00	2661	12985	28.61	-2.1	2.3	107.6	7.7	191	3
4498MH0003590021602662C00	2662	13003	27.40	-1.9	2.1	103.3	7.1	159	4
4498MH0003590021602663C00	2663	13021	26.28	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	127	5
4498MH0003590021602664C00	2664	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	95	6
4498MH0003590021602665C00	2665	13057	24.28	-1.5	1.7	92.4	5.6	63	7
4498MH0003590021602666C00	2666	13075	23.37	-1.4	1.5	89.2	5.1	31	8

UPDATED: 03_April_2025

SOL 4498 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4498MH0003060011602668C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4498MH0001630001602689R00	2689	MOTOR COUNT:		14163	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4498MH0001630001602690S00	2690	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4498	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4498	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4498MH0003060021602669C00	2669	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4498MH0003060021602670C00	2670	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4498MH0003060021602671C00	2671	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	191	3
4498MH0003060021602672C00	2672	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	159	4
4498MH0003060021602673C00	2673	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4498MH0003060021602674C00	2674	14217	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	95	6
4498MH0003060021602675C00	2675	14271	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	63	7
4498MH0003060021602676C00	2676	14325	5.11	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_April_2025

SOL 4498 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4498MH0003060011602678C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4498MH0001630001602687R00	2687	MOTOR COUNT:		14118	RANGE (cm):	6.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4498MH0001630001602688S00	2688	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4498	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4498	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4498MH0003060021602679C00	2679	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
4498MH0003060021602680C00	2680	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4498MH0003060021602681C00	2681	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4498MH0003060021602682C00	2682	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	159	4
4498MH0003060021602683C00	2683	14118	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	127	5
4498MH0003060021602684C00	2684	14172	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	95	6
4498MH0003060021602685C00	2685	14226	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	63	7
4498MH0003060021602686C00	2686	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 04_April_2025

SOL 4500 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chuckwalla - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4500MH0003360011602711C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4500MH0001930001602744R00	2744	MOTOR COUNT:		14018	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4500MH0001930001602745S00	2745	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4500	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4500	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4500MH0003360021602712C00	2712	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4500MH0003360021602713C00	2713	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4500MH0003360021602714C00	2714	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4500MH0003360021602715C00	2715	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4500MH0003360021602716C00	2716	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4500MH0003360021602717C00	2717	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4500MH0003360021602718C00	2718	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	63	7
4500MH0003360021602719C00	2719	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 04_April_2025

SOL 4500 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chuckwalla - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4500MH0003360011602721C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4500MH0001930001602742R00	2742	MOTOR COUNT:		14014	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4500MH0001930001602743S00	2743	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4500	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4500	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4500MH0003360021602722C00	2722	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4500MH0003360021602723C00	2723	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4500MH0003360021602724C00	2724	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4500MH0003360021602725C00	2725	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4500MH0003360021602726C00	2726	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4500MH0003360021602727C00	2727	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4500MH0003360021602728C00	2728	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4500MH0003360021602729C00	2729	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 04_April_2025

SOL 4500 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chuckwalla - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4500MH0008480011602731C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4500MH0001930001602740R00	2740	MOTOR COUNT:		15128	RANGE (cm):		2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4500MH0001930001602741S00	2741	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Apr-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4500	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4500	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4500MH0008480021602732C00	2732	15032	2.97	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	255	1
4500MH0008480021602733C00	2733	15056	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2
4500MH0008480021602734C00	2734	15080	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
4500MH0008480021602735C00	2735	15104	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
4500MH0008480021602736C00	2736	15128	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
4500MH0008480021602737C00	2737	15152	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6
4500MH0008480021602738C00	2738	15176	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4500MH0008480021602739C00	2739	15200	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 14_April_2025

SOL 4505 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coronado - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4505MH0001680011602749C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4505MH0001930001602782R00	2782	MOTOR COUNT:		14006	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4505MH0001930001602783S00	2783	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4505	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4505		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4505MH0001680021602750C00	2750	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4505MH0001680021602751C00	2751	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4505MH0001680021602752C00	2752	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4505MH0001680021602753C00	2753	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4505MH0001680021602754C00	2754	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4505MH0001680021602755C00	2755	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4505MH0001680021602756C00	2756	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	63	7
4505MH0001680021602757C00	2757	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_April_2025

SOL 4505 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coronado - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4505MH0001680011602759C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4505MH0001930001602780R00	2780	MOTOR COUNT:		14004	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4505MH0001930001602781S00	2781	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4505	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4505		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4505MH0001680021602760C00	2760	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4505MH0001680021602761C00	2761	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4505MH0001680021602762C00	2762	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4505MH0001680021602763C00	2763	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4505MH0001680021602764C00	2764	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4505MH0001680021602765C00	2765	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4505MH0001680021602766C00	2766	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4505MH0001680021602767C00	2767	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_April_2025

SOL 4505 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coronado – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4505MH0008480011602769C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4505MH0001930001602778R00		2778		MOTOR COUNT:		14896		RANGE (cm): 3.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4505MH0001930001602779S00		2779		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		9-Apr-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4505		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4505	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4505MH0008480021602770C00	2770	14800	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	255	1		
4505MH0008480021602771C00	2771	14824	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	223	2		
4505MH0008480021602772C00	2772	14848	3.39	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	191	3		
4505MH0008480021602773C00	2773	14872	3.33	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	159	4		
4505MH0008480021602774C00	2774	14896	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	127	5		
4505MH0008480021602775C00	2775	14920	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	95	6		
4505MH0008480021602776C00	2776	14944	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	63	7		
4505MH0008480021602777C00	2777	14968	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 14_April_2025

SOL 4509 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Iron_Mountain - after DRT - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4509MH0003360011602787C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4510MH0002650001602854R00	2854	MOTOR COUNT:		14036	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4510MH0002650001602855S00	2855	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4509	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4510		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4509MH0003360021602788C00	2788	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4509MH0003360021602789C00	2789	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4509MH0003360021602790C00	2790	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4509MH0003360021602791C00	2791	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4509MH0003360021602792C00	2792	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5
4509MH0003360021602793C00	2793	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4509MH0003360021602794C00	2794	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4509MH0003360021602795C00	2795	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_April_2025

SOL 4509 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Iron_Mountain - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4509MH0008480011602841C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4510MH0002650001602852R00	2852	MOTOR COUNT:		15177	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4510MH0002650001602853S00	2853	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4509	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4510		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4509MH0008480021602842C00	2842	15081	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	255	1
4509MH0008480021602843C00	2843	15105	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	223	2
4509MH0008480021602844C00	2844	15129	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	191	3
4509MH0008480021602845C00	2845	15153	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
4509MH0008480021602846C00	2846	15177	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	127	5
4509MH0008480021602847C00	2847	15201	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
4509MH0008480021602848C00	2848	15225	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
4509MH0008480021602849C00	2849	15249	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 16_April_2025

SOL 4511 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4511MH0002990011602859C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4512MH0002270001602918R00	2918	MOTOR COUNT:		13961	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4512MH0002270001602919S00	2919	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4511	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4512		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4511MH0002990021602860C00	2860	13817	8.22	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.8	255	1
4511MH0002990021602861C00	2861	13853	7.92	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	223	2
4511MH0002990021602862C00	2862	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	191	3
4511MH0002990021602863C00	2863	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4
4511MH0002990021602864C00	2864	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
4511MH0002990021602865C00	2865	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	95	6
4511MH0002990021602866C00	2866	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4511MH0002990021602867C00	2867	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 16_April_2025

SOL 4511 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4511MH0002990011602869C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4512MH0002270001602916R00	2916	MOTOR COUNT:		13962	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4512MH0002270001602917S00	2917	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4511	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4512		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4511MH0002990021602870C00	2870	13818	8.21	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.8	255	1
4511MH0002990021602871C00	2871	13854	7.91	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	223	2
4511MH0002990021602872C00	2872	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	191	3
4511MH0002990021602873C00	2873	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4
4511MH0002990021602874C00	2874	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
4511MH0002990021602875C00	2875	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4511MH0002990021602876C00	2876	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4511MH0002990021602877C00	2877	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 16_April_2025

SOL 4511 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target The_Grotto - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4511MH0001680011602881C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4512MH0002270001602914R00	2914	MOTOR COUNT:		14020	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4512MH0002270001602915S00	2915	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4511	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4512	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4511MH0001680021602882C00	2882	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4511MH0001680021602883C00	2883	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4511MH0001680021602884C00	2884	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4511MH0001680021602885C00	2885	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4511MH0001680021602886C00	2886	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4511MH0001680021602887C00	2887	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4511MH0001680021602888C00	2888	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4511MH0001680021602889C00	2889	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 16_April_2025

SOL 4511 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target The_Grotto - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4511MH0001680011602891C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4512MH0002270001602912R00	2912	MOTOR COUNT:		14014	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4512MH0002270001602913S00	2913	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4511	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4512	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4511MH0001680021602892C00	2892	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4511MH0001680021602893C00	2893	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4511MH0001680021602894C00	2894	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4511MH0001680021602895C00	2895	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4511MH0001680021602896C00	2896	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4511MH0001680021602897C00	2897	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4511MH0001680021602898C00	2898	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4511MH0001680021602899C00	2899	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 16_April_2025

SOL 4511 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target The_Grotto – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4511MH0007430011602901C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4512MH0002270001602910R00	2910		MOTOR COUNT:		15156	RANGE (cm):	2.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4512MH0002270001602911S00	2911		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4511	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4512	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4511MH0007430021602902C00	2902	15012	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
4511MH0007430021602903C00	2903	15048	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2
4511MH0007430021602904C00	2904	15084	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
4511MH0007430021602905C00	2905	15120	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
4511MH0007430021602906C00	2906	15156	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
4511MH0007430021602907C00	2907	15192	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
4511MH0007430021602908C00	2908	15228	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
4511MH0007430021602909C00	2909	15264	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 18_April_2025

SOL 4513 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Elephant_Tree - ~24 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4513MH0003590011602921C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4514MH0001630001602992R00	2992	MOTOR COUNT:		13020	RANGE (cm):	26.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4514MH0001630001602993S00	2993	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4513	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4514	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4513MH0003590021602922C00	2922	12948	31.42	-2.5	2.9	117.5	9.4	255	1
4513MH0003590021602923C00	2923	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	223	2
4513MH0003590021602924C00	2924	12984	28.68	-2.1	2.4	107.8	7.8	191	3
4513MH0003590021602925C00	2925	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	159	4
4513MH0003590021602926C00	2926	13020	26.34	-1.8	2.0	99.6	6.6	127	5
4513MH0003590021602927C00	2927	13038	25.30	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	95	6
4513MH0003590021602928C00	2928	13056	24.33	-1.5	1.7	92.5	5.6	63	7
4513MH0003590021602929C00	2929	13074	23.42	-1.4	1.5	89.4	5.2	31	8

UPDATED: 18_April_2025

SOL 4513 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Elephant_Tree - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4513MH0003830011602931C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4514MH0001630001602990R00	2990	MOTOR COUNT:		14234	RANGE (cm):	5.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4514MH0001630001602991S00	2991	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00383	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		90	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4513	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4514	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4513MH0003830021602932C00	2932	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
4513MH0003830021602933C00	2933	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4513MH0003830021602934C00	2934	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	191	3
4513MH0003830021602935C00	2935	14144	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
4513MH0003830021602936C00	2936	14234	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	127	5
4513MH0003830021602937C00	2937	14324	5.11	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	95	6
4513MH0003830021602938C00	2938	14414	4.74	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	63	7
4513MH0003830021602939C00	2939	14504	4.41	-0.1	0.1	22.4	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 18_April_2025

SOL 4513 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Elephant_Tree - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4513MH0003830011602941C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4514MH0001630001602988R00	2988	MOTOR COUNT:		14166	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4514MH0001630001602989S00	2989	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00383	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Apr-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		90	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4513	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4514	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4513MH0003830021602942C00	2942	13806	8.32	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	255	1
4513MH0003830021602943C00	2943	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
4513MH0003830021602944C00	2944	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4513MH0003830021602945C00	2945	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	159	4
4513MH0003830021602946C00	2946	14166	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4513MH0003830021602947C00	2947	14256	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	95	6
4513MH0003830021602948C00	2948	14346	5.02	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	63	7
4513MH0003830021602949C00	2949	14436	4.66	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 18_April_2025

SOL 4513 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Purissima - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4513MH0001820011602953C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4514MH0001630001602986R00	2986	MOTOR COUNT:		14105	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4514MH0001630001602987S00	2987	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Apr-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4513	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4514	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4513MH0001820021602954C00	2954	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	255	1
4513MH0001820021602955C00	2955	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	223	2
4513MH0001820021602956C00	2956	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	191	3
4513MH0001820021602957C00	2957	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	159	4
4513MH0001820021602958C00	2958	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	127	5
4513MH0001820021602959C00	2959	14129	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	95	6
4513MH0001820021602960C00	2960	14153	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	63	7
4513MH0001820021602961C00	2961	14177	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 18_April_2025

SOL 4513 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Purissima - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4513MH0001820011602963C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4514MH0001630001602984R00	2984		MOTOR COUNT:		14112	RANGE (cm):	6.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4514MH0001630001602985S00	2985		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Apr-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4513	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4514	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4513MH0001820021602964C00	2964	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	255	1
4513MH0001820021602965C00	2965	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	223	2
4513MH0001820021602966C00	2966	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	191	3
4513MH0001820021602967C00	2967	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
4513MH0001820021602968C00	2968	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	127	5
4513MH0001820021602969C00	2969	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	95	6
4513MH0001820021602970C00	2970	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	63	7
4513MH0001820021602971C00	2971	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 18_April_2025

SOL 4513 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Purissima - APXS spot 1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4513MH0001820011602973C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4514MH0001630001602982R00	2982		MOTOR COUNT:		14105	RANGE (cm):	6.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4514MH0001630001602983S00	2983		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Apr-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4513	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4514	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4513MH0001820021602974C00	2974	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	255	1
4513MH0001820021602975C00	2975	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	223	2
4513MH0001820021602976C00	2976	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	191	3
4513MH0001820021602977C00	2977	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	159	4
4513MH0001820021602978C00	2978	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	127	5
4513MH0001820021602979C00	2979	14129	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	95	6
4513MH0001820021602980C00	2980	14153	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	63	7
4513MH0001820021602981C00	2981	14177	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 30_April_2025

SOL 4522 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4522MH0003360011603017C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4523MH0002270001603076R00	3076	MOTOR COUNT:		13974	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4523MH0002270001603077S00	3077	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Apr-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4522	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4523	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4522MH0003360021603018C00	3018	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4522MH0003360021603019C00	3019	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4522MH0003360021603020C00	3020	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4522MH0003360021603021C00	3021	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4522MH0003360021603022C00	3022	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
4522MH0003360021603023C00	3023	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
4522MH0003360021603024C00	3024	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	63	7
4522MH0003360021603025C00	3025	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 30_April_2025

SOL 4522 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4522MH0003360011603027C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4523MH0002270001603074R00	3074	MOTOR COUNT:		13981	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4523MH0002270001603075S00	3075	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Apr-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4522	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4523	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4522MH0003360021603028C00	3028	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4522MH0003360021603029C00	3029	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4522MH0003360021603030C00	3030	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4522MH0003360021603031C00	3031	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4522MH0003360021603032C00	3032	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
4522MH0003360021603033C00	3033	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
4522MH0003360021603034C00	3034	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
4522MH0003360021603035C00	3035	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4522 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4522MH0003060011603039C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4523MH0002270001603072R00	3072	MOTOR COUNT:		14058	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4523MH0002270001603073S00	3073	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4522	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4523	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4522MH0003060021603040C00	3040	13842	8.01	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	255	1
4522MH0003060021603041C00	3041	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
4522MH0003060021603042C00	3042	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4522MH0003060021603043C00	3043	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4522MH0003060021603044C00	3044	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	127	5
4522MH0003060021603045C00	3045	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	95	6
4522MH0003060021603046C00	3046	14166	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7
4522MH0003060021603047C00	3047	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4522 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4522MH0003060011603049C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4523MH0002270001603070R00	3070	MOTOR COUNT:		14212	RANGE (cm):	5.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4523MH0002270001603071S00	3071	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4522	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4523	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4522MH0003060021603050C00	3050	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	255	1
4522MH0003060021603051C00	3051	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	223	2
4522MH0003060021603052C00	3052	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	191	3
4522MH0003060021603053C00	3053	14158	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	159	4
4522MH0003060021603054C00	3054	14212	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	127	5
4522MH0003060021603055C00	3055	14266	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	95	6
4522MH0003060021603056C00	3056	14320	5.13	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7
4522MH0003060021603057C00	3057	14374	4.90	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 30_April_2025

SOL 4522 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4522MH0003060011603059C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4523MH0002270001603068R00	3068	MOTOR COUNT:		14176	RANGE (cm):	5.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4523MH0002270001603069S00	3069	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Apr-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4522	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4523	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4522MH0003060021603060C00	3060	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4522MH0003060021603061C00	3061	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	223	2
4522MH0003060021603062C00	3062	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	191	3
4522MH0003060021603063C00	3063	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	159	4
4522MH0003060021603064C00	3064	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	127	5
4522MH0003060021603065C00	3065	14230	5.54	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	95	6
4522MH0003060021603066C00	3066	14284	5.29	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	63	7
4522MH0003060021603067C00	3067	14338	5.05	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 02_May_2025

SOL 4525 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bradshaw_Trail - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4525MH0001680011603081C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4526MH0001630001603152R00	3152	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4526MH0001630001603153S00	3153	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4525	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4526	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4525MH0001680021603082C00	3082	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4525MH0001680021603083C00	3083	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4525MH0001680021603084C00	3084	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4525MH0001680021603085C00	3085	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4525MH0001680021603086C00	3086	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4525MH0001680021603087C00	3087	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4525MH0001680021603088C00	3088	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4525MH0001680021603089C00	3089	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_May_2025

SOL 4525 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bradshaw_Trail - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4525MH0001680011603091C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4526MH0001630001603150R00	3150	MOTOR COUNT:		13995	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4526MH0001630001603151S00	3151	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4525	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4526	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4525MH0001680021603092C00	3092	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4525MH0001680021603093C00	3093	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4525MH0001680021603094C00	3094	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4525MH0001680021603095C00	3095	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4525MH0001680021603096C00	3096	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4525MH0001680021603097C00	3097	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4525MH0001680021603098C00	3098	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4525MH0001680021603099C00	3099	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_May_2025

SOL 4525 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bradshaw_Trail - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4525MH0008640011603101C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4526MH0001630001603148R00	3148	MOTOR COUNT:		14844	RANGE (cm):	3.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4526MH0001630001603149S00	3149	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4525	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4526	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4525MH0008640021603102C00	3102	14724	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	255	1
4525MH0008640021603103C00	3103	14754	3.63	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	223	2
4525MH0008640021603104C00	3104	14784	3.55	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	191	3
4525MH0008640021603105C00	3105	14814	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	159	4
4525MH0008640021603106C00	3106	14844	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	127	5
4525MH0008640021603107C00	3107	14874	3.33	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	95	6
4525MH0008640021603108C00	3108	14904	3.25	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	63	7
4525MH0008640021603109C00	3109	14934	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 02_May_2025

SOL 4525 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sweetwater_River - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4525MH0003360011603113C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4526MH0001630001603146R00	3146	MOTOR COUNT:		14024	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4526MH0001630001603147S00	3147	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4525	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4526	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4525MH0003360021603114C00	3114	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4525MH0003360021603115C00	3115	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4525MH0003360021603116C00	3116	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4525MH0003360021603117C00	3117	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4525MH0003360021603118C00	3118	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4525MH0003360021603119C00	3119	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
4525MH0003360021603120C00	3120	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4525MH0003360021603121C00	3121	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_May_2025

SOL 4525 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sweetwater_River - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4525MH0003360011603123C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4526MH0001630001603144R00	3144	MOTOR COUNT:		14013	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4526MH0001630001603145S00	3145	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4525	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4526	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4525MH0003360021603124C00	3124	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4525MH0003360021603125C00	3125	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4525MH0003360021603126C00	3126	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4525MH0003360021603127C00	3127	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4525MH0003360021603128C00	3128	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4525MH0003360021603129C00	3129	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4525MH0003360021603130C00	3130	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4525MH0003360021603131C00	3131	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_May_2025

SOL 4525 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sweetwater_River - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4525MH0008480011603133C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4526MH0001630001603142R00	3142	MOTOR COUNT:		14895	RANGE (cm):	3.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4526MH0001630001603143S00	3143	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Apr-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4525	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4526	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4525MH0008480021603134C00	3134	14799	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	255	1
4525MH0008480021603135C00	3135	14823	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.2	223	2
4525MH0008480021603136C00	3136	14847	3.39	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	191	3
4525MH0008480021603137C00	3137	14871	3.33	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	159	4
4525MH0008480021603138C00	3138	14895	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	127	5
4525MH0008480021603139C00	3139	14919	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	95	6
4525MH0008480021603140C00	3140	14943	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	63	7
4525MH0008480021603141C00	3141	14967	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 05_May_2025

SOL 4527 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tamarak_Valley - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4527MH0001680011603157C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4527MH0001930001603190R00	3190	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4527MH0001930001603191S00	3191	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4527	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4527	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4527MH0001680021603158C00	3158	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4527MH0001680021603159C00	3159	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4527MH0001680021603160C00	3160	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4527MH0001680021603161C00	3161	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4527MH0001680021603162C00	3162	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4527MH0001680021603163C00	3163	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4527MH0001680021603164C00	3164	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4527MH0001680021603165C00	3165	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_May_2025

SOL 4527 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tamarak_Valley - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4527MH0001680011603167C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4527MH0001930001603188R00	3188	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4527MH0001930001603189S00	3189	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4527	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4527	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4527MH0001680021603168C00	3168	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4527MH0001680021603169C00	3169	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4527MH0001680021603170C00	3170	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4527MH0001680021603171C00	3171	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4527MH0001680021603172C00	3172	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4527MH0001680021603173C00	3173	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4527MH0001680021603174C00	3174	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4527MH0001680021603175C00	3175	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_May_2025

SOL 4527 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tamarak_Valley - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4527MH0007430011603177C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4527MH0001930001603186R00		3186		MOTOR COUNT:		15086		RANGE (cm): 2.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4527MH0001930001603187S00		3187		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		1-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			36			ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4527		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL: 4527	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4527MH0007430021603178C00	3178	14942	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	255	1		
4527MH0007430021603179C00	3179	14978	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2		
4527MH0007430021603180C00	3180	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3		
4527MH0007430021603181C00	3181	15050	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4		
4527MH0007430021603182C00	3182	15086	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5		
4527MH0007430021603183C00	3183	15122	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6		
4527MH0007430021603184C00	3184	15158	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7		
4527MH0007430021603185C00	3185	15194	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 09_May_2025

SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Valley_of_the_Moon - mosaic position 1 of 8 - ~12 cm standoff								
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008980011603193C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603358R00			3358	MOTOR COUNT:		13364	RANGE (cm):	14.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603359S00			3359	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00898	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4529		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4529MH0008980021603194C00	3194	13148	20.26	-1.1	1.1	78.2	3.9	255	1	
4529MH0008980021603195C00	3195	13202	18.40	-0.9	0.9	71.7	3.2	223	2	
4529MH0008980021603196C00	3196	13256	16.81	-0.8	0.8	66.1	2.7	191	3	
4529MH0008980021603197C00	3197	13310	15.44	-0.6	0.7	61.3	2.3	159	4	
4529MH0008980021603198C00	3198	13364	14.26	-0.6	0.6	57.1	2.0	127	5	
4529MH0008980021603199C00	3199	13418	13.21	-0.5	0.5	53.4	1.7	95	6	
4529MH0008980021603200C00	3200	13472	12.29	-0.4	0.4	50.2	1.5	63	7	
4529MH0008980021603201C00	3201	13526	11.47	-0.4	0.4	47.3	1.3	31	8	

UPDATED: 09_May_2025

SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Valley_of_the_Moon - mosaic position 2 of 8 - ~13 cm standoff								
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008980011603203C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603356R00			3356	MOTOR COUNT:		13333	RANGE (cm):	14.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603357S00			3357	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00898	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4529		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4529MH0008980021603204C00	3204	13117	21.49	-1.2	1.3	82.5	4.4	255	1	
4529MH0008980021603205C00	3205	13171	19.43	-1.0	1.0	75.3	3.6	223	2	
4529MH0008980021603206C00	3206	13225	17.69	-0.8	0.9	69.2	3.0	191	3	
4529MH0008980021603207C00	3207	13279	16.20	-0.7	0.7	63.9	2.5	159	4	
4529MH0008980021603208C00	3208	13333	14.92	-0.6	0.6	59.4	2.1	127	5	
4529MH0008980021603209C00	3209	13387	13.80	-0.5	0.5	55.5	1.9	95	6	
4529MH0008980021603210C00	3210	13441	12.81	-0.5	0.5	52.0	1.6	63	7	
4529MH0008980021603211C00	3211	13495	11.93	-0.4	0.4	48.9	1.4	31	8	

UPDATED: 09_May_2025

SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Valley_of_the_Moon - mosaic position 3 of 8 - ~12 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008980011603213C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4530MH0007280001603354R00		3354		MOTOR COUNT:		13363		RANGE (cm): 14.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4530MH0007280001603355S00		3355		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00898		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4529		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4529MH0008980021603214C00	3214	13147	20.30	-1.1	1.1	78.4	3.9	255	1		
4529MH0008980021603215C00	3215	13201	18.43	-0.9	0.9	71.8	3.2	223	2		
4529MH0008980021603216C00	3216	13255	16.84	-0.8	0.8	66.2	2.7	191	3		
4529MH0008980021603217C00	3217	13309	15.47	-0.6	0.7	61.4	2.3	159	4		
4529MH0008980021603218C00	3218	13363	14.28	-0.6	0.6	57.2	2.0	127	5		
4529MH0008980021603219C00	3219	13417	13.23	-0.5	0.5	53.5	1.7	95	6		
4529MH0008980021603220C00	3220	13471	12.30	-0.4	0.4	50.2	1.5	63	7		
4529MH0008980021603221C00	3221	13525	11.48	-0.4	0.4	47.3	1.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 09_May_2025

SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Valley_of_the_Moon - mosaic position 4 of 8 - ~14 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008980011603223C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4530MH0007280001603352R00		3352		MOTOR COUNT:		13307		RANGE (cm): 15.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4530MH0007280001603353S00		3353		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00898		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4529		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4529MH0008980021603224C00	3224	13091	22.62	-1.3	1.4	86.5	4.8	255	1		
4529MH0008980021603225C00	3225	13145	20.37	-1.1	1.2	78.6	3.9	223	2		
4529MH0008980021603226C00	3226	13199	18.49	-0.9	0.9	72.0	3.2	191	3		
4529MH0008980021603227C00	3227	13253	16.89	-0.8	0.8	66.4	2.7	159	4		
4529MH0008980021603228C00	3228	13307	15.52	-0.7	0.7	61.5	2.3	127	5		
4529MH0008980021603229C00	3229	13361	14.32	-0.6	0.6	57.3	2.0	95	6		
4529MH0008980021603230C00	3230	13415	13.27	-0.5	0.5	53.6	1.7	63	7		
4529MH0008980021603231C00	3231	13469	12.34	-0.4	0.4	50.3	1.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 09_May_2025

SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Valley_of_the_Moon - mosaic position 5 of 8 - ~14 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008980011603233C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4530MH0007280001603350R00		3350		MOTOR COUNT:		13280		RANGE (cm): 16.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4530MH0007280001603351S00		3351		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00898		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4529		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4529MH0008980021603234C00	3234	13064	23.92	-1.5	1.6	91.1	5.4	255	1		
4529MH0008980021603235C00	3235	13118	21.45	-1.2	1.3	82.4	4.3	223	2		
4529MH0008980021603236C00	3236	13172	19.39	-1.0	1.0	75.2	3.6	191	3		
4529MH0008980021603237C00	3237	13226	17.66	-0.8	0.9	69.1	3.0	159	4		
4529MH0008980021603238C00	3238	13280	16.18	-0.7	0.7	63.9	2.5	127	5		
4529MH0008980021603239C00	3239	13334	14.90	-0.6	0.6	59.3	2.1	95	6		
4529MH0008980021603240C00	3240	13388	13.78	-0.5	0.5	55.4	1.8	63	7		
4529MH0008980021603241C00	3241	13442	12.79	-0.5	0.5	51.9	1.6	31	8		

UPDATED: 09_May_2025

SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Valley_of_the_Moon - mosaic position 6 of 8 - ~15 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008980011603243C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4530MH0007280001603348R00		3348		MOTOR COUNT:		13273		RANGE (cm): 16.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4530MH0007280001603349S00		3349		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00898		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4529		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4529MH0008980021603244C00	3244	13057	24.28	-1.5	1.7	92.4	5.6	255	1		
4529MH0008980021603245C00	3245	13111	21.74	-1.2	1.3	83.4	4.5	223	2		
4529MH0008980021603246C00	3246	13165	19.64	-1.0	1.1	76.0	3.6	191	3		
4529MH0008980021603247C00	3247	13219	17.87	-0.8	0.9	69.8	3.0	159	4		
4529MH0008980021603248C00	3248	13273	16.36	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	127	5		
4529MH0008980021603249C00	3249	13327	15.05	-0.6	0.6	59.9	2.2	95	6		
4529MH0008980021603250C00	3250	13381	13.91	-0.5	0.5	55.9	1.9	63	7		
4529MH0008980021603251C00	3251	13435	12.91	-0.5	0.5	52.3	1.6	31	8		

UPDATED: 09_May_2025

SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Valley_of_the_Moon - mosaic position 7 of 8 - ~15 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008980011603253C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603346R00	3346	MOTOR COUNT:		13269	RANGE (cm):	16.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603347S00	3347	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00898	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4529	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4529MH0008980021603254C00	3254	13053	24.49	-1.5	1.7	93.1	5.7	255	1
4529MH0008980021603255C00	3255	13107	21.91	-1.2	1.3	84.0	4.5	223	2
4529MH0008980021603256C00	3256	13161	19.78	-1.0	1.1	76.5	3.7	191	3
4529MH0008980021603257C00	3257	13215	17.99	-0.9	0.9	70.2	3.1	159	4
4529MH0008980021603258C00	3258	13269	16.46	-0.7	0.8	64.9	2.6	127	5
4529MH0008980021603259C00	3259	13323	15.14	-0.6	0.6	60.2	2.2	95	6
4529MH0008980021603260C00	3260	13377	13.99	-0.5	0.5	56.2	1.9	63	7
4529MH0008980021603261C00	3261	13431	12.98	-0.5	0.5	52.6	1.7	31	8

UPDATED: 09_May_2025

SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Valley_of_the_Moon - mosaic position 8 of 8 - ~14 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008980011603263C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603344R00	3344	MOTOR COUNT:		13274	RANGE (cm):	16.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603345S00	3345	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00898	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4529	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4529MH0008980021603264C00	3264	13058	24.22	-1.5	1.7	92.2	5.5	255	1
4529MH0008980021603265C00	3265	13112	21.70	-1.2	1.3	83.3	4.4	223	2
4529MH0008980021603266C00	3266	13166	19.60	-1.0	1.1	75.9	3.6	191	3
4529MH0008980021603267C00	3267	13220	17.84	-0.8	0.9	69.7	3.0	159	4
4529MH0008980021603268C00	3268	13274	16.33	-0.7	0.7	64.4	2.5	127	5
4529MH0008980021603269C00	3269	13328	15.03	-0.6	0.6	59.8	2.2	95	6
4529MH0008980021603270C00	3270	13382	13.89	-0.5	0.5	55.8	1.9	63	7
4529MH0008980021603271C00	3271	13436	12.89	-0.5	0.5	52.3	1.6	31	8

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SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Box_Canyon - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008760011603273C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603342R00	3342	MOTOR COUNT:		13026	RANGE (cm):	26.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603343S00	3343	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4529	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4529MH0008760021603274C00	3274	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	255	1
4529MH0008760021603275C00	3275	12990	28.26	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	223	2
4529MH0008760021603276C00	3276	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	191	3
4529MH0008760021603277C00	3277	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	159	4
4529MH0008760021603278C00	3278	13026	25.99	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	127	5
4529MH0008760021603279C00	3279	13038	25.30	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	95	6
4529MH0008760021603280C00	3280	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	63	7
4529MH0008760021603281C00	3281	13062	24.02	-1.5	1.6	91.5	5.4	31	8

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SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Box_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0002990011603283C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603340R00	3340	MOTOR COUNT:		14097	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603341S00	3341	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4529	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4529MH0002990021603284C00	3284	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4529MH0002990021603285C00	3285	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4529MH0002990021603286C00	3286	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	191	3
4529MH0002990021603287C00	3287	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	159	4
4529MH0002990021603288C00	3288	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	127	5
4529MH0002990021603289C00	3289	14133	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	95	6
4529MH0002990021603290C00	3290	14169	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	63	7
4529MH0002990021603291C00	3291	14205	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Box_Canyon - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0002990011603293C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603338R00	3338	MOTOR COUNT:		14102	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603339S00	3339	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4529	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4529MH0002990021603294C00	3294	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
4529MH0002990021603295C00	3295	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4529MH0002990021603296C00	3296	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	191	3
4529MH0002990021603297C00	3297	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	159	4
4529MH0002990021603298C00	3298	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	127	5
4529MH0002990021603299C00	3299	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	95	6
4529MH0002990021603300C00	3300	14174	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	63	7
4529MH0002990021603301C00	3301	14210	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Orosco_Ridge - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0008760011603303C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603336R00	3336	MOTOR COUNT:		13019	RANGE (cm):	26.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603337S00	3337	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4529	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4529MH0008760021603304C00	3304	12971	29.62	-2.2	2.5	111.2	8.3	255	1
4529MH0008760021603305C00	3305	12983	28.75	-2.1	2.4	108.1	7.8	223	2
4529MH0008760021603306C00	3306	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	191	3
4529MH0008760021603307C00	3307	13007	27.14	-1.9	2.1	102.4	7.0	159	4
4529MH0008760021603308C00	3308	13019	26.40	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	127	5
4529MH0008760021603309C00	3309	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	95	6
4529MH0008760021603310C00	3310	13043	25.02	-1.6	1.8	95.0	5.9	63	7
4529MH0008760021603311C00	3311	13055	24.38	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	31	8

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SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0003630011603313C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603334R00	3334	MOTOR COUNT:		14071	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603335S00	3335	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00363	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		72	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4529	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4529MH0003630021603314C00	3314	13783	8.52	-0.2	0.2	36.9	0.8	255	1
4529MH0003630021603315C00	3315	13855	7.90	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	223	2
4529MH0003630021603316C00	3316	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
4529MH0003630021603317C00	3317	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4529MH0003630021603318C00	3318	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	127	5
4529MH0003630021603319C00	3319	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	95	6
4529MH0003630021603320C00	3320	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
4529MH0003630021603321C00	3321	14287	5.28	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4529 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4529MH0003630011603323C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4530MH0007280001603332R00	3332	MOTOR COUNT:		14073	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4530MH0007280001603333S00	3333	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00363	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		72	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4529	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4530	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4529MH0003630021603324C00	3324	13785	8.50	-0.2	0.2	36.8	0.8	255	1
4529MH0003630021603325C00	3325	13857	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	223	2
4529MH0003630021603326C00	3326	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
4529MH0003630021603327C00	3327	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4529MH0003630021603328C00	3328	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	127	5
4529MH0003630021603329C00	3329	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	95	6
4529MH0003630021603330C00	3330	14217	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7
4529MH0003630021603331C00	3331	14289	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4532 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Encinitas - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4532MH0001680011603363C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4532MH0001630001603432R00	3432	MOTOR COUNT:		14009	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4532MH0001630001603433S00	3433	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4532	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4532		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4532MH0001680021603364C00	3364	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4532MH0001680021603365C00	3365	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4532MH0001680021603366C00	3366	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4532MH0001680021603367C00	3367	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4532MH0001680021603368C00	3368	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4532MH0001680021603369C00	3369	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4532MH0001680021603370C00	3370	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4532MH0001680021603371C00	3371	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4532 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Encinitas - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4532MH0001680011603373C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4532MH0001630001603430R00	3430	MOTOR COUNT:		14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4532MH0001630001603431S00	3431	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4532	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4532		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4532MH0001680021603374C00	3374	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4532MH0001680021603375C00	3375	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4532MH0001680021603376C00	3376	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4532MH0001680021603377C00	3377	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4532MH0001680021603378C00	3378	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4532MH0001680021603379C00	3379	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4532MH0001680021603380C00	3380	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4532MH0001680021603381C00	3381	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4532 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Encinitas - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4532MH0008640011603383C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4532MH0001630001603428R00	3428	MOTOR COUNT:		15151	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4532MH0001630001603429S00	3429	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4532	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4532		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4532MH0008640021603384C00	3384	15031	2.97	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	255	1
4532MH0008640021603385C00	3385	15061	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	223	2
4532MH0008640021603386C00	3386	15091	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	191	3
4532MH0008640021603387C00	3387	15121	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
4532MH0008640021603388C00	3388	15151	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
4532MH0008640021603389C00	3389	15181	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
4532MH0008640021603390C00	3390	15211	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
4532MH0008640021603391C00	3391	15241	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4532 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jack_Creek - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4532MH0003590011603393C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4532MH0001630001603426R00	3426	MOTOR COUNT:		13024	RANGE (cm):	26.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4532MH0001630001603427S00	3427	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4532	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4532		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4532MH0003590021603394C00	3394	12952	31.10	-2.4	2.8	116.4	9.2	255	1
4532MH0003590021603395C00	3395	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	223	2
4532MH0003590021603396C00	3396	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	191	3
4532MH0003590021603397C00	3397	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	159	4
4532MH0003590021603398C00	3398	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	127	5
4532MH0003590021603399C00	3399	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	95	6
4532MH0003590021603400C00	3400	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	63	7
4532MH0003590021603401C00	3401	13078	23.23	-1.4	1.5	88.7	5.1	31	8

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SOL 4532 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4532MH0001520011603403C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4532MH0001630001603424R00	3424	MOTOR COUNT:		14141	RANGE (cm):	6.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4532MH0001630001603425S00	3425	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4532	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4532		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4532MH0001520021603404C00	3404	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4532MH0001520021603405C00	3405	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4532MH0001520021603406C00	3406	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	191	3
4532MH0001520021603407C00	3407	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	159	4
4532MH0001520021603408C00	3408	14141	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	127	5
4532MH0001520021603409C00	3409	14189	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	95	6
4532MH0001520021603410C00	3410	14237	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	63	7
4532MH0001520021603411C00	3411	14285	5.29	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 14_May_2025

SOL 4532 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4532MH0001520011603413C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4532MH0001630001603422R00	3422	MOTOR COUNT:		14191	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4532MH0001630001603423S00	3423	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4532	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4532		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4532MH0001520021603414C00	3414	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	255	1
4532MH0001520021603415C00	3415	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	223	2
4532MH0001520021603416C00	3416	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	191	3
4532MH0001520021603417C00	3417	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
4532MH0001520021603418C00	3418	14191	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	127	5
4532MH0001520021603419C00	3419	14239	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	95	6
4532MH0001520021603420C00	3420	14287	5.28	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	63	7
4532MH0001520021603421C00	3421	14335	5.07	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 12_May_2025

SOL 4534 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chumash - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4534MH0001680011603437C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4534MH0001930001603470R00		3470		MOTOR COUNT:		14039		RANGE (cm): 6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4534MH0001930001603471S00		3471		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4534		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4534	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4534MH0001680021603438C00	3438	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1		
4534MH0001680021603439C00	3439	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2		
4534MH0001680021603440C00	3440	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3		
4534MH0001680021603441C00	3441	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4		
4534MH0001680021603442C00	3442	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5		
4534MH0001680021603443C00	3443	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6		
4534MH0001680021603444C00	3444	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7		
4534MH0001680021603445C00	3445	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 12_May_2025

SOL 4534 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chumash - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4534MH0001680011603447C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4534MH0001930001603468R00		3468		MOTOR COUNT:		14043		RANGE (cm): 6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4534MH0001930001603469S00		3469		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4534		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4534	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4534MH0001680021603448C00	3448	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1		
4534MH0001680021603449C00	3449	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2		
4534MH0001680021603450C00	3450	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3		
4534MH0001680021603451C00	3451	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4		
4534MH0001680021603452C00	3452	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5		
4534MH0001680021603453C00	3453	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6		
4534MH0001680021603454C00	3454	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7		
4534MH0001680021603455C00	3455	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 12_May_2025

SOL 4534 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chumash - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4534MH0008640011603457C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4534MH0001930001603466R00	3466	MOTOR COUNT:		15232	RANGE (cm):		2.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4534MH0001930001603467S00	3467	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4534	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4534	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4534MH0008640021603458C00	3458	15112	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	255	1
4534MH0008640021603459C00	3459	15142	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	223	2
4534MH0008640021603460C00	3460	15172	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	191	3
4534MH0008640021603461C00	3461	15202	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	159	4
4534MH0008640021603462C00	3462	15232	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	127	5
4534MH0008640021603463C00	3463	15262	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	95	6
4534MH0008640021603464C00	3464	15292	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7
4534MH0008640021603465C00	3465	15322	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 12_May_2025

SOL 4536 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Crescenta_Valley - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4536MH0001680011603475C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4537MH0002270001603534R00		3534		MOTOR COUNT:		13990		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4537MH0002270001603535S00		3535		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4536		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4537	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4536MH0001680021603476C00	3476	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1		
4536MH0001680021603477C00	3477	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2		
4536MH0001680021603478C00	3478	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3		
4536MH0001680021603479C00	3479	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4		
4536MH0001680021603480C00	3480	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5		
4536MH0001680021603481C00	3481	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6		
4536MH0001680021603482C00	3482	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7		
4536MH0001680021603483C00	3483	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 12_May_2025

SOL 4536 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Crescenta_Valley - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4536MH0001680011603485C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4537MH0002270001603532R00		3532		MOTOR COUNT:		13989		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4537MH0002270001603533S00		3533		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4536		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4537	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4536MH0001680021603486C00	3486	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1		
4536MH0001680021603487C00	3487	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2		
4536MH0001680021603488C00	3488	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3		
4536MH0001680021603489C00	3489	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4		
4536MH0001680021603490C00	3490	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5		
4536MH0001680021603491C00	3491	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6		
4536MH0001680021603492C00	3492	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7		
4536MH0001680021603493C00	3493	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 12_May_2025

SOL 4536 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Crescenta_Valley - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4536MH0007430011603495C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4537MH0002270001603530R00	3530	MOTOR COUNT:		15060	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4537MH0002270001603531S00	3531	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4536	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4537		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4536MH0007430021603496C00	3496	14916	3.23	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	255	1
4536MH0007430021603497C00	3497	14952	3.14	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	223	2
4536MH0007430021603498C00	3498	14988	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	191	3
4536MH0007430021603499C00	3499	15024	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4
4536MH0007430021603500C00	3500	15060	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	127	5
4536MH0007430021603501C00	3501	15096	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	95	6
4536MH0007430021603502C00	3502	15132	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	63	7
4536MH0007430021603503C00	3503	15168	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 12_May_2025

SOL 4536 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4536MH0001680011603507C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4537MH0002270001603528R00	3528	MOTOR COUNT:		14054	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4537MH0002270001603529S00	3529	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4536	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4537		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4536MH0001680021603508C00	3508	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4536MH0001680021603509C00	3509	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4536MH0001680021603510C00	3510	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4536MH0001680021603511C00	3511	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	159	4
4536MH0001680021603512C00	3512	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
4536MH0001680021603513C00	3513	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
4536MH0001680021603514C00	3514	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
4536MH0001680021603515C00	3515	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 12_May_2025

SOL 4536 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rockhouse_Canyon – stereo-2 – ~45 mm standoff										
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4536MH0001680011603517C00						
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4537MH0002270001603526R00		3526		MOTOR COUNT:		14054		RANGE (cm): 6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4537MH0002270001603527S00		3527		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4536		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4537	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8			
				NEAR	FAR							
4536MH0001680021603518C00	3518	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1			
4536MH0001680021603519C00	3519	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2			
4536MH0001680021603520C00	3520	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3			
4536MH0001680021603521C00	3521	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	159	4			
4536MH0001680021603522C00	3522	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5			
4536MH0001680021603523C00	3523	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6			
4536MH0001680021603524C00	3524	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7			
4536MH0001680021603525C00	3525	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8			

UPDATED: 14_May_2025

SOL 4539 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4539MH0001680011603545C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4539MH0002650001603566R00	3566	MOTOR COUNT:		13995	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4539MH0002650001603567S00	3567	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4539	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4539	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4539MH0001680021603546C00	3546	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4539MH0001680021603547C00	3547	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4539MH0001680021603548C00	3548	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4539MH0001680021603549C00	3549	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4539MH0001680021603550C00	3550	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4539MH0001680021603551C00	3551	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4539MH0001680021603552C00	3552	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4539MH0001680021603553C00	3553	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_May_2025

SOL 4539 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4539MH0001680011603555C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4539MH0002650001603564R00	3564	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4539MH0002650001603565S00	3565	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4539	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4539	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4539MH0001680021603556C00	3556	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4539MH0001680021603557C00	3557	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4539MH0001680021603558C00	3558	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4539MH0001680021603559C00	3559	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4539MH0001680021603560C00	3560	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4539MH0001680021603561C00	3561	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4539MH0001680021603562C00	3562	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4539MH0001680021603563C00	3563	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_May_2025

SOL 4543 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mesa_Grande – ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4543MH0003590011603569C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4544MH0001710001603652R00	3652	MOTOR COUNT:		13006	RANGE (cm):	27.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4544MH0001710001603653S00	3653	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4543	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4544		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4543MH0003590021603570C00	3570	12934	32.63	-2.6	3.1	121.8	10.1	255	1
4543MH0003590021603571C00	3571	12952	31.10	-2.4	2.8	116.4	9.2	223	2
4543MH0003590021603572C00	3572	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	191	3
4543MH0003590021603573C00	3573	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	159	4
4543MH0003590021603574C00	3574	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	127	5
4543MH0003590021603575C00	3575	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	95	6
4543MH0003590021603576C00	3576	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	63	7
4543MH0003590021603577C00	3577	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_May_2025

SOL 4543 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mesa_Grande – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4543MH0002990011603579C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4544MH0001710001603650R00	3650	MOTOR COUNT:		13987	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4544MH0001710001603651S00	3651	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4543	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4544		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4543MH0002990021603580C00	3580	13843	8.00	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	255	1
4543MH0002990021603581C00	3581	13879	7.71	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
4543MH0002990021603582C00	3582	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
4543MH0002990021603583C00	3583	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
4543MH0002990021603584C00	3584	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4543MH0002990021603585C00	3585	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4543MH0002990021603586C00	3586	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4543MH0002990021603587C00	3587	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_May_2025

SOL 4543 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mesa_Grande – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4543MH0002990011603589C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4544MH0001710001603648R00	3648	MOTOR COUNT:		13982	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4544MH0001710001603649S00	3649	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4543	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4544		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4543MH0002990021603590C00	3590	13838	8.04	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
4543MH0002990021603591C00	3591	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	223	2
4543MH0002990021603592C00	3592	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
4543MH0002990021603593C00	3593	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
4543MH0002990021603594C00	3594	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
4543MH0002990021603595C00	3595	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4543MH0002990021603596C00	3596	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4543MH0002990021603597C00	3597	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_May_2025

SOL 4543 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mesa_Grande – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4543MH0007960011603599C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4544MH0001710001603646R00	3646	MOTOR COUNT:		15085	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4544MH0001710001603647S00	3647	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00796	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4543	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4544		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4543MH0007960021603600C00	3600	14917	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	255	1
4543MH0007960021603601C00	3601	14959	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	223	2
4543MH0007960021603602C00	3602	15001	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3
4543MH0007960021603603C00	3603	15043	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	159	4
4543MH0007960021603604C00	3604	15085	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
4543MH0007960021603605C00	3605	15127	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
4543MH0007960021603606C00	3606	15169	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4543MH0007960021603607C00	3607	15211	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 19_May_2025

SOL 4543 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arroyo_Seco – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4543MH0001680011603611C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4544MH0001710001603644R00	3644	MOTOR COUNT:		14001	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4544MH0001710001603645S00	3645	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4543	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4544	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4543MH0001680021603612C00	3612	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4543MH0001680021603613C00	3613	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4543MH0001680021603614C00	3614	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4543MH0001680021603615C00	3615	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4543MH0001680021603616C00	3616	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4543MH0001680021603617C00	3617	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4543MH0001680021603618C00	3618	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4543MH0001680021603619C00	3619	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_May_2025

SOL 4543 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arroyo_Seco – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4543MH0001680011603621C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4544MH0001710001603642R00	3642	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4544MH0001710001603643S00	3643	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4543	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4544	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4543MH0001680021603622C00	3622	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4543MH0001680021603623C00	3623	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4543MH0001680021603624C00	3624	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4543MH0001680021603625C00	3625	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4543MH0001680021603626C00	3626	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4543MH0001680021603627C00	3627	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4543MH0001680021603628C00	3628	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4543MH0001680021603629C00	3629	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_May_2025

SOL 4543 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arroyo_Seco – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4543MH0007430011603631C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4544MH0001710001603640R00	3640	MOTOR COUNT:		14886	RANGE (cm):		3.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4544MH0001710001603641S00	3641	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-May-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4543		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4544
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4543MH0007430021603632C00	3632	14742	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	255	1
4543MH0007430021603633C00	3633	14778	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	223	2
4543MH0007430021603634C00	3634	14814	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	191	3
4543MH0007430021603635C00	3635	14850	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	159	4
4543MH0007430021603636C00	3636	14886	3.30	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	127	5
4543MH0007430021603637C00	3637	14922	3.21	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	95	6
4543MH0007430021603638C00	3638	14958	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	63	7
4543MH0007430021603639C00	3639	14994	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 21_May_2025

SOL 4546 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cucamonga_Peak – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4546MH0001680011603657C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4546MH0001930001603690R00	3690	MOTOR COUNT:		14041	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4546MH0001930001603691S00	3691	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4546	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4546	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4546MH0001680021603658C00	3658	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4546MH0001680021603659C00	3659	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4546MH0001680021603660C00	3660	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4546MH0001680021603661C00	3661	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4546MH0001680021603662C00	3662	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
4546MH0001680021603663C00	3663	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4546MH0001680021603664C00	3664	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4546MH0001680021603665C00	3665	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_May_2025

SOL 4546 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cucamonga_Peak – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4546MH0001680011603667C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4546MH0001930001603688R00	3688	MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4546MH0001930001603689S00	3689	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4546	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4546	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4546MH0001680021603668C00	3668	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4546MH0001680021603669C00	3669	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4546MH0001680021603670C00	3670	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4546MH0001680021603671C00	3671	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4546MH0001680021603672C00	3672	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4546MH0001680021603673C00	3673	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4546MH0001680021603674C00	3674	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4546MH0001680021603675C00	3675	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_May_2025

SOL 4546 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cucamonga_Peak – after DRT – ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4546MH0008640011603677C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4546MH0001930001603686R00	3686	MOTOR COUNT:		15206	RANGE (cm):		2.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4546MH0001930001603687S00	3687	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-May-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4546		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4546
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4546MH0008640021603678C00	3678	15086	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	255	1
4546MH0008640021603679C00	3679	15116	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	223	2
4546MH0008640021603680C00	3680	15146	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	191	3
4546MH0008640021603681C00	3681	15176	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	159	4
4546MH0008640021603682C00	3682	15206	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	127	5
4546MH0008640021603683C00	3683	15236	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	95	6
4546MH0008640021603684C00	3684	15266	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	63	7
4546MH0008640021603685C00	3685	15296	2.48	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 27_May_2025

SOL 4547 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Big_Bear_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4547MH0008790011603700C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4548MH0001930001603736R00	3736	MOTOR COUNT:		14006	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4548MH0001930001603737S00	3737	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4547	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4548		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4547MH0008790031603702C00	3702	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
4547MH0008790031603703C00	3703	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4547MH0008790031603704C00	3704	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4547MH0008790031603705C00	3705	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4547MH0008790031603706C00	3706	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4547MH0008790031603707C00	3707	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4547MH0008790031603708C00	3708	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4547MH0008790031603709C00	3709	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 27_May_2025

SOL 4547 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Big_Bear_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4547MH0008790011603711C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4548MH0001930001603734R00	3734	MOTOR COUNT:		14028	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4548MH0001930001603735S00	3735	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4547	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4548		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4547MH0008790031603713C00	3713	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4547MH0008790031603714C00	3714	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4547MH0008790031603715C00	3715	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4547MH0008790031603716C00	3716	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4547MH0008790031603717C00	3717	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4547MH0008790031603718C00	3718	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4547MH0008790031603719C00	3719	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4547MH0008790031603720C00	3720	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 27_May_2025

SOL 4547 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Big_Bear_Lake - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4547MH0008220011603722C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4548MH0001930001603732R00		3732		MOTOR COUNT:		15168	RANGE (cm):	2.7
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4548MH0001930001603733S00		3733		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00822	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		22-May-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4547	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4548	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4547MH0008220031603724C00	3724	15072	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1	
4547MH0008220031603725C00	3725	15096	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	223	2	
4547MH0008220031603726C00	3726	15120	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	191	3	
4547MH0008220031603727C00	3727	15144	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	159	4	
4547MH0008220031603728C00	3728	15168	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	127	5	
4547MH0008220031603729C00	3729	15192	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6	
4547MH0008220031603730C00	3730	15216	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7	
4547MH0008220031603731C00	3731	15240	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8	

UPDATED: 29_May_2025

SOL 4550 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Mount_Baden_Powell - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4550MH0008340011603742C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4552MH0001630001603820R00	3820	MOTOR COUNT:		13961	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4552MH0001630001603821S00	3821	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4550	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4552		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4550MH0008340031603744C00	3744	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
4550MH0008340031603745C00	3745	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
4550MH0008340031603746C00	3746	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
4550MH0008340031603747C00	3747	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
4550MH0008340031603748C00	3748	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
4550MH0008340031603749C00	3749	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
4550MH0008340031603750C00	3750	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	63	7
4550MH0008340031603751C00	3751	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 29_May_2025

SOL 4550 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Mount_Baden_Powell - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4550MH0008340011603753C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4552MH0001630001603818R00	3818	MOTOR COUNT:		13978	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4552MH0001630001603819S00	3819	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4550	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4552		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4550MH0008340031603755C00	3755	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
4550MH0008340031603756C00	3756	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
4550MH0008340031603757C00	3757	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
4550MH0008340031603758C00	3758	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4550MH0008340031603759C00	3759	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
4550MH0008340031603760C00	3760	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	95	6
4550MH0008340031603761C00	3761	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4550MH0008340031603762C00	3762	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 29_May_2025

SOL 4550 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Mount_Baden_Powell - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4550MH0008010011603764C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4552MH0001630001603816R00	3816	MOTOR COUNT:		14770	RANGE (cm):	3.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4552MH0001630001603817S00	3817	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00801	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4550	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4552	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4550MH0008010031603766C00	3766	14626	4.00	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	255	1
4550MH0008010031603767C00	3767	14662	3.90	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	223	2
4550MH0008010031603768C00	3768	14698	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	191	3
4550MH0008010031603769C00	3769	14734	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	159	4
4550MH0008010031603770C00	3770	14770	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	127	5
4550MH0008010031603771C00	3771	14806	3.50	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	95	6
4550MH0008010031603772C00	3772	14842	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	63	7
4550MH0008010031603773C00	3773	14878	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 29_May_2025

SOL 4550 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Camino_Del_Mar - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4550MH0008340011603778C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4552MH0001630001603814R00	3814	MOTOR COUNT:		14054	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4552MH0001630001603815S00	3815	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4550	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4552	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4550MH0008340031603780C00	3780	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4550MH0008340031603781C00	3781	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4550MH0008340031603782C00	3782	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4550MH0008340031603783C00	3783	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	159	4
4550MH0008340031603784C00	3784	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
4550MH0008340031603785C00	3785	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
4550MH0008340031603786C00	3786	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
4550MH0008340031603787C00	3787	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_May_2025

SOL 4550 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	second merge of: target Camino_Del_Mar - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff - merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on Sol 4553								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4550MH0008340011603778C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4553MH0001930001603826R00	3826	MOTOR COUNT:		14054	RANGE (cm):		6.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4553MH0001930001603827S00	3827	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4550	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4553	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4550MH0008340031603780C00	3780	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4550MH0008340031603781C00	3781	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4550MH0008340031603782C00	3782	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4550MH0008340031603783C00	3783	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	159	4
4550MH0008340031603784C00	3784	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
4550MH0008340031603785C00	3785	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
4550MH0008340031603786C00	3786	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
4550MH0008340031603787C00	3787	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_May_2025

SOL 4550 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Camino_Del_Mar - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4550MH0008340011603789C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4552MH0001630001603812R00	3812	MOTOR COUNT:		14050	RANGE (cm):		6.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4552MH0001630001603813S00	3813	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4550	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4552	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4550MH0008340031603791C00	3791	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4550MH0008340031603792C00	3792	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4550MH0008340031603793C00	3793	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4550MH0008340031603794C00	3794	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
4550MH0008340031603795C00	3795	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
4550MH0008340031603796C00	3796	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4550MH0008340031603797C00	3797	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4550MH0008340031603798C00	3798	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_May_2025

SOL 4550 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	second merge of: target Camino_Del_Mar - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff - merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on Sol 4553								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4550MH0008340011603789C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4553MH0001930001603824R00	3824	MOTOR COUNT:		14050	RANGE (cm):		6.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4553MH0001930001603825S00	3825	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4550	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4553	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4550MH0008340031603791C00	3791	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4550MH0008340031603792C00	3792	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4550MH0008340031603793C00	3793	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4550MH0008340031603794C00	3794	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
4550MH0008340031603795C00	3795	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
4550MH0008340031603796C00	3796	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4550MH0008340031603797C00	3797	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4550MH0008340031603798C00	3798	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_May_2025

SOL 4550 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Camino_Del_Mar - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4550MH0008350011603800C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4552MH0001630001603810R00	3810	MOTOR COUNT:		15261	RANGE (cm):		2.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4552MH0001630001603811S00	3811	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00835		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-May-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4550	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4552	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4550MH0008350031603802C00	3802	15141	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	255	1
4550MH0008350031603803C00	3803	15171	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	223	2
4550MH0008350031603804C00	3804	15201	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	191	3
4550MH0008350031603805C00	3805	15231	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	159	4
4550MH0008350031603806C00	3806	15261	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	127	5
4550MH0008350031603807C00	3807	15291	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	95	6
4550MH0008350031603808C00	3808	15321	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	63	7
4550MH0008350031603809C00	3809	15351	2.39	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 29_May_2025

SOL 4550 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		second merge of: target Camino_Del_Mar – after DRT – ~5 mm standoff – merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on Sol 4553							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4553MH0001930001603822R00		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4550MH0008350011603800C00		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4553MH0001930001603823S00		3822	MOTOR COUNT:		15261	RANGE (cm):	2.5
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		25-May-25		3823	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00835	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4550		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4553			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4550MH0008350031603802C00	3802	15141	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	255	1
4550MH0008350031603803C00	3803	15171	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	223	2
4550MH0008350031603804C00	3804	15201	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	191	3
4550MH0008350031603805C00	3805	15231	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	159	4
4550MH0008350031603806C00	3806	15261	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	127	5
4550MH0008350031603807C00	3807	15291	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	95	6
4550MH0008350031603808C00	3808	15321	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	63	7
4550MH0008350031603809C00	3809	15351	2.39	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 02_June_2025

SOL 4554 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Palo_Verde_Mountains - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4554MH0003590011603829C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4554MH0001930001603862R00	3862	MOTOR COUNT:		13032	RANGE (cm):	25.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4554MH0001930001603863S00	3863	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4554	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4554	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4554MH0003590021603830C00	3830	12960	30.46	-2.3	2.7	114.1	8.8	255	1
4554MH0003590021603831C00	3831	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	223	2
4554MH0003590021603832C00	3832	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	191	3
4554MH0003590021603833C00	3833	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	159	4
4554MH0003590021603834C00	3834	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	127	5
4554MH0003590021603835C00	3835	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	95	6
4554MH0003590021603836C00	3836	13068	23.72	-1.4	1.6	90.4	5.3	63	7
4554MH0003590021603837C00	3837	13086	22.85	-1.3	1.5	87.3	4.9	31	8

UPDATED: 02_June_2025

SOL 4554 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4554MH0001520011603839C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4554MH0001930001603860R00	3860	MOTOR COUNT:		14180	RANGE (cm):	5.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4554MH0001930001603861S00	3861	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4554	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4554	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4554MH0001520021603840C00	3840	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4554MH0001520021603841C00	3841	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	223	2
4554MH0001520021603842C00	3842	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	191	3
4554MH0001520021603843C00	3843	14132	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	159	4
4554MH0001520021603844C00	3844	14180	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5
4554MH0001520021603845C00	3845	14228	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	95	6
4554MH0001520021603846C00	3846	14276	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	63	7
4554MH0001520021603847C00	3847	14324	5.11	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 02_June_2025

SOL 4554 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4554MH0001520011603849C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4554MH0001930001603858R00	3858	MOTOR COUNT:		14184	RANGE (cm):		5.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4554MH0001930001603859S00	3859	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-May-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4554	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4554	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4554MH0001520021603850C00	3850	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
4554MH0001520021603851C00	3851	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	223	2
4554MH0001520021603852C00	3852	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	191	3
4554MH0001520021603853C00	3853	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	159	4
4554MH0001520021603854C00	3854	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5
4554MH0001520021603855C00	3855	14232	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	95	6
4554MH0001520021603856C00	3856	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	63	7
4554MH0001520021603857C00	3857	14328	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 05_June_2025

SOL 4559 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Holcomb_Valley - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4559MH0008790011603868C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4560MH0001630001603946R00	3946	MOTOR COUNT:		14005	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603947S00	3947	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4559	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4560		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4559MH0008790031603870C00	3870	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
4559MH0008790031603871C00	3871	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4559MH0008790031603872C00	3872	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4559MH0008790031603873C00	3873	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4559MH0008790031603874C00	3874	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4559MH0008790031603875C00	3875	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4559MH0008790031603876C00	3876	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4559MH0008790031603877C00	3877	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_June_2025

SOL 4559 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Holcomb_Valley - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4559MH0008790011603879C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4560MH0001630001603944R00	3944	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603945S00	3945	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4559	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4560		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4559MH0008790031603881C00	3881	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4559MH0008790031603882C00	3882	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4559MH0008790031603883C00	3883	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4559MH0008790031603884C00	3884	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4559MH0008790031603885C00	3885	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4559MH0008790031603886C00	3886	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4559MH0008790031603887C00	3887	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4559MH0008790031603888C00	3888	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_June_2025

SOL 4559 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Holcomb_Valley - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4559MH0008220011603890C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4560MH0001630001603942R00	3942	MOTOR COUNT:		14919	RANGE (cm):	3.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603943S00	3943	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00822	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4559	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4560	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4559MH0008220031603892C00	3892	14823	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.2	255	1
4559MH0008220031603893C00	3893	14847	3.39	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	223	2
4559MH0008220031603894C00	3894	14871	3.33	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	191	3
4559MH0008220031603895C00	3895	14895	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	159	4
4559MH0008220031603896C00	3896	14919	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	127	5
4559MH0008220031603897C00	3897	14943	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	95	6
4559MH0008220031603898C00	3898	14967	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	63	7
4559MH0008220031603899C00	3899	14991	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 05_June_2025

SOL 4559 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4559MH0008790011603904C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4560MH0001630001603940R00	3940	MOTOR COUNT:		14033	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603941S00	3941	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4559	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4560	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4559MH0008790031603906C00	3906	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4559MH0008790031603907C00	3907	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4559MH0008790031603908C00	3908	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4559MH0008790031603909C00	3909	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4559MH0008790031603910C00	3910	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4559MH0008790031603911C00	3911	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4559MH0008790031603912C00	3912	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4559MH0008790031603913C00	3913	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_June_2025

SOL 4559 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4559MH0008790011603915C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4560MH0001630001603938R00			3938	MOTOR COUNT:		14028	RANGE (cm):	6.7
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603939S00			3939	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4559		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4560
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4559MH0008790031603917C00	3917	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4559MH0008790031603918C00	3918	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4559MH0008790031603919C00	3919	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4559MH0008790031603920C00	3920	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4559MH0008790031603921C00	3921	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4559MH0008790031603922C00	3922	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4559MH0008790031603923C00	3923	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4559MH0008790031603924C00	3924	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_June_2025

SOL 4559 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4559MH0008220011603926C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4560MH0001630001603936R00			3936	MOTOR COUNT:		14935	RANGE (cm):	3.2
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4560MH0001630001603937S00			3937	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00822	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4559		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4560
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4559MH0008220031603928C00	3928	14839	3.41	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	255	1
4559MH0008220031603929C00	3929	14863	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	223	2
4559MH0008220031603930C00	3930	14887	3.29	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	191	3
4559MH0008220031603931C00	3931	14911	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	159	4
4559MH0008220031603932C00	3932	14935	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	127	5
4559MH0008220031603933C00	3933	14959	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	95	6
4559MH0008220031603934C00	3934	14983	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	63	7
4559MH0008220031603935C00	3935	15007	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 06_June_2025

SOL 4461 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Altadena - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4561MH0008790011603952C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4561MH0001530001604004R00	4004	MOTOR COUNT:		14045	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4561MH0001530001604005S00	4005	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4561	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4561	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4561MH0008790031603954C00	3954	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	255	1
4561MH0008790031603955C00	3955	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	223	2
4561MH0008790031603956C00	3956	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	191	3
4561MH0008790031603957C00	3957	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
4561MH0008790031603958C00	3958	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4561MH0008790031603959C00	3959	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4561MH0008790031603960C00	3960	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
4561MH0008790031603961C00	3961	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 06_June_2025

SOL 4461 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Altadena - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4561MH0008790011603963C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4561MH0001530001604002R00	4002	MOTOR COUNT:		14036	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4561MH0001530001604003S00	4003	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4561	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4561	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4561MH0008790031603965C00	3965	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4561MH0008790031603966C00	3966	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4561MH0008790031603967C00	3967	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4561MH0008790031603968C00	3968	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4561MH0008790031603969C00	3969	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5
4561MH0008790031603970C00	3970	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4561MH0008790031603971C00	3971	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4561MH0008790031603972C00	3972	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 06_June_2025

SOL 4461 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Altadena - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4561MH0008790011603974C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4561MH0001530001604000R00		4000		MOTOR COUNT:		14015	RANGE (cm):	6.7
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4561MH0001530001604001S00		4001		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Jun-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4561		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4561
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4561MH0008790031603976C00	3976	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1	
4561MH0008790031603977C00	3977	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2	
4561MH0008790031603978C00	3978	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3	
4561MH0008790031603979C00	3979	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4	
4561MH0008790031603980C00	3980	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5	
4561MH0008790031603981C00	3981	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6	
4561MH0008790031603982C00	3982	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7	
4561MH0008790031603983C00	3983	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8	

UPDATED: 06_June_2025

SOL 4461 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Altadena - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4561MH0008220011603985C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4561MH0001530001603998R00		3998		MOTOR COUNT:		14966	RANGE (cm):	3.1
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4561MH0001530001603999S00		3999		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00822	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Jun-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4561		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4561
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4561MH0008220031603987C00	3987	14870	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	255	1	
4561MH0008220031603988C00	3988	14894	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	223	2	
4561MH0008220031603989C00	3989	14918	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	191	3	
4561MH0008220031603990C00	3990	14942	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	159	4	
4561MH0008220031603991C00	3991	14966	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	127	5	
4561MH0008220031603992C00	3992	14990	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	95	6	
4561MH0008220031603993C00	3993	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	63	7	
4561MH0008220031603994C00	3994	15038	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	31	8	

UPDATED: 13_June_2025

SOL 4568 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		Altadena drill cuttings – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4568MH0001520011604011C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4569MH0002580001604020R00		4020		MOTOR COUNT:		13984		RANGE (cm):	7.0
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4569MH0002580001604021S00		4021		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		12-Jun-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00258		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4568		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4569	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4568MH0001520021604012C00	4012	13792	8.44	-0.2	0.2	36.6	0.8	255	1		
4568MH0001520021604013C00	4013	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2		
4568MH0001520021604014C00	4014	13888	7.64	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	191	3		
4568MH0001520021604015C00	4015	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4		
4568MH0001520021604016C00	4016	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5		
4568MH0001520021604017C00	4017	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6		
4568MH0001520021604018C00	4018	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7		
4568MH0001520021604019C00	4019	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 23_June_2025

SOL 4570 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Angels_Flight - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4570MH0008790011604026C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4571MH0002270001604098R00	4098	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4571MH0002270001604099S00	4099	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4570	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4571	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4570MH0008790031604028C00	4028	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4570MH0008790031604029C00	4029	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4570MH0008790031604030C00	4030	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4570MH0008790031604031C00	4031	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4570MH0008790031604032C00	4032	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4570MH0008790031604033C00	4033	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4570MH0008790031604034C00	4034	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4570MH0008790031604035C00	4035	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 23_June_2025

SOL 4570 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Angels_Flight - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4570MH0008790011604037C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4571MH0002270001604096R00	4096	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4571MH0002270001604097S00	4097	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4570	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4571	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4570MH0008790031604039C00	4039	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4570MH0008790031604040C00	4040	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4570MH0008790031604041C00	4041	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4570MH0008790031604042C00	4042	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4570MH0008790031604043C00	4043	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4570MH0008790031604044C00	4044	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4570MH0008790031604045C00	4045	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4570MH0008790031604046C00	4046	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_June_2025

SOL 4570 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Angels_Flight - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4570MH0008220011604048C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4571MH0002270001604094R00	4094	MOTOR COUNT:		14893	RANGE (cm):	3.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4571MH0002270001604095S00	4095	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00822	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4570	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4571		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4570MH0008220031604050C00	4050	14797	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	255	1
4570MH0008220031604051C00	4051	14821	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	223	2
4570MH0008220031604052C00	4052	14845	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	191	3
4570MH0008220031604053C00	4053	14869	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	159	4
4570MH0008220031604054C00	4054	14893	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	127	5
4570MH0008220031604055C00	4055	14917	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	95	6
4570MH0008220031604056C00	4056	14941	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	63	7
4570MH0008220031604057C00	4057	14965	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 23_June_2025

SOL 4570 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4570MH0008340011604062C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4571MH0002270001604092R00	4092	MOTOR COUNT:		14113	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4571MH0002270001604093S00	4093	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4570	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4571		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4570MH0008340031604064C00	4064	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	255	1
4570MH0008340031604065C00	4065	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
4570MH0008340031604066C00	4066	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	191	3
4570MH0008340031604067C00	4067	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
4570MH0008340031604068C00	4068	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	127	5
4570MH0008340031604069C00	4069	14131	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	95	6
4570MH0008340031604070C00	4070	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	63	7
4570MH0008340031604071C00	4071	14167	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 23_June_2025

SOL 4570 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4570MH0008340011604073C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4571MH0002270001604090R00	4090	MOTOR COUNT:		14113	RANGE (cm):		6.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4571MH0002270001604091S00	4091	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Jun-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4570		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4571
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4570MH0008340031604075C00	4075	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	255	1
4570MH0008340031604076C00	4076	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
4570MH0008340031604077C00	4077	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	191	3
4570MH0008340031604078C00	4078	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
4570MH0008340031604079C00	4079	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	127	5
4570MH0008340031604080C00	4080	14131	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	95	6
4570MH0008340031604081C00	4081	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	63	7
4570MH0008340031604082C00	4082	14167	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 19_June_2025

SOL 4573 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Flamingo - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4573MH0008760011604101C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4573MH0001930001604134R00	4134	MOTOR COUNT:		13005	RANGE (cm):	27.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4573MH0001930001604135S00	4135	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4573	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4573	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4573MH0008760021604102C00	4102	12957	30.69	-2.3	2.7	114.9	8.9	255	1
4573MH0008760021604103C00	4103	12969	29.77	-2.2	2.6	111.7	8.4	223	2
4573MH0008760021604104C00	4104	12981	28.89	-2.1	2.4	108.6	7.9	191	3
4573MH0008760021604105C00	4105	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	159	4
4573MH0008760021604106C00	4106	13005	27.27	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	127	5
4573MH0008760021604107C00	4107	13017	26.52	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	95	6
4573MH0008760021604108C00	4108	13029	25.81	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	63	7
4573MH0008760021604109C00	4109	13041	25.13	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	31	8

UPDATED: 19_June_2025

SOL 4573 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Flamingo - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4573MH0002240011604111C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4573MH0001930001604132R00	4132	MOTOR COUNT:		13892	RANGE (cm):	7.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4573MH0001930001604133S00	4133	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4573	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4573	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4573MH0002240021604112C00	4112	13724	9.08	-0.3	0.2	38.9	0.9	255	1
4573MH0002240021604113C00	4113	13766	8.68	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	223	2
4573MH0002240021604114C00	4114	13808	8.30	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	191	3
4573MH0002240021604115C00	4115	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	159	4
4573MH0002240021604116C00	4116	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	127	5
4573MH0002240021604117C00	4117	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	95	6
4573MH0002240021604118C00	4118	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	63	7
4573MH0002240021604119C00	4119	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 19_June_2025

SOL 4573 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Flamingo - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4573MH0002240011604121C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4573MH0001930001604130R00	4130	MOTOR COUNT:		13932	RANGE (cm):		7.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4573MH0001930001604131S00	4131	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Jun-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4573		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4573
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4573MH0002240021604122C00	4122	13764	8.70	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1
4573MH0002240021604123C00	4123	13806	8.32	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2
4573MH0002240021604124C00	4124	13848	7.96	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	191	3
4573MH0002240021604125C00	4125	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	159	4
4573MH0002240021604126C00	4126	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	127	5
4573MH0002240021604127C00	4127	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	95	6
4573MH0002240021604128C00	4128	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4573MH0002240021604129C00	4129	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 30_June_2025

SOL 4575 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tarija - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4575MH0008340011604140C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4575MH0001930001604176R00	4176	MOTOR COUNT:		14051	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4575MH0001930001604177S00	4177	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4575	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4575		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4575MH0008340031604142C00	4142	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4575MH0008340031604143C00	4143	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4575MH0008340031604144C00	4144	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4575MH0008340031604145C00	4145	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
4575MH0008340031604146C00	4146	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
4575MH0008340031604147C00	4147	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4575MH0008340031604148C00	4148	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4575MH0008340031604149C00	4149	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 30_June_2025

SOL 4575 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tarija - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4575MH0008340011604151C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4575MH0001930001604174R00	4174	MOTOR COUNT:		14049	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4575MH0001930001604175S00	4175	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4575	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4575		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4575MH0008340031604153C00	4153	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4575MH0008340031604154C00	4154	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4575MH0008340031604155C00	4155	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4575MH0008340031604156C00	4156	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
4575MH0008340031604157C00	4157	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
4575MH0008340031604158C00	4158	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4575MH0008340031604159C00	4159	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4575MH0008340031604160C00	4160	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 30_June_2025

SOL 4575 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tarija - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4575MH0008350011604162C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4575MH0001930001604172R00		4172		MOTOR COUNT:		14976		RANGE (cm):	3.1
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4575MH0001930001604173S00		4173		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00835	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		19-Jun-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4575		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4575	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4575MH0008350031604164C00	4164	14856	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	255	1		
4575MH0008350031604165C00	4165	14886	3.30	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	223	2		
4575MH0008350031604166C00	4166	14916	3.23	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	191	3		
4575MH0008350031604167C00	4167	14946	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	159	4		
4575MH0008350031604168C00	4168	14976	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	127	5		
4575MH0008350031604169C00	4169	15006	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	95	6		
4575MH0008350031604170C00	4170	15036	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	63	7		
4575MH0008350031604171C00	4171	15066	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	31	8		

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SOL 4577 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Copiapo - ~26 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4577MH0008760011604188C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4578MH0001630001604263R00	4263	MOTOR COUNT:		12991	RANGE (cm):	28.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4578MH0001630001604264S00	4264	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4577	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4578		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4577MH0008760021604189C00	4189	12943	31.85	-2.5	2.9	119.0	9.6	255	1
4577MH0008760021604190C00	4190	12955	30.85	-2.4	2.8	115.5	9.0	223	2
4577MH0008760021604191C00	4191	12967	29.92	-2.2	2.6	112.2	8.5	191	3
4577MH0008760021604192C00	4192	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	159	4
4577MH0008760021604193C00	4193	12991	28.19	-2.0	2.3	106.1	7.5	127	5
4577MH0008760021604194C00	4194	13003	27.40	-1.9	2.1	103.3	7.1	95	6
4577MH0008760021604195C00	4195	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	63	7
4577MH0008760021604196C00	4196	13027	25.93	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	31	8

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SOL 4577 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Copiapo - stereo-1 - ~6 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4577MH0002990011604198C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4578MH0001630001604261R00	4261	MOTOR COUNT:		13883	RANGE (cm):	7.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4578MH0001630001604262S00	4262	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4577	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4578		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4577MH0002990021604199C00	4199	13739	8.94	-0.3	0.2	38.4	0.9	255	1
4577MH0002990021604200C00	4200	13775	8.59	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	223	2
4577MH0002990021604201C00	4201	13811	8.27	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	191	3
4577MH0002990021604202C00	4202	13847	7.97	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	159	4
4577MH0002990021604203C00	4203	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	127	5
4577MH0002990021604204C00	4204	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	95	6
4577MH0002990021604205C00	4205	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	63	7
4577MH0002990021604206C00	4206	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4577 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Copiapo - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4577MH0002990011604208C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4578MH0001630001604259R00	4259	MOTOR COUNT:		13910	RANGE (cm):	7.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4578MH0001630001604260S00	4260	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4577	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4578		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4577MH0002990021604209C00	4209	13766	8.68	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	255	1
4577MH0002990021604210C00	4210	13802	8.35	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	223	2
4577MH0002990021604211C00	4211	13838	8.04	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
4577MH0002990021604212C00	4212	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	159	4
4577MH0002990021604213C00	4213	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	127	5
4577MH0002990021604214C00	4214	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	95	6
4577MH0002990021604215C00	4215	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	63	7
4577MH0002990021604216C00	4216	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2025

SOL 4577 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Copacabana - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4577MH0008340011604221C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4578MH0001630001604257R00	4257	MOTOR COUNT:		14040	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4578MH0001630001604258S00	4258	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4577	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4578		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4577MH0008340031604223C00	4223	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4577MH0008340031604224C00	4224	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4577MH0008340031604225C00	4225	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4577MH0008340031604226C00	4226	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4577MH0008340031604227C00	4227	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
4577MH0008340031604228C00	4228	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4577MH0008340031604229C00	4229	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4577MH0008340031604230C00	4230	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2025

SOL 4577 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Copacabana - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4577MH0008340011604232C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4578MH0001630001604255R00	4255	MOTOR COUNT:		14041	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4578MH0001630001604256S00	4256	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4577	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4578	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4577MH0008340031604234C00	4234	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4577MH0008340031604235C00	4235	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4577MH0008340031604236C00	4236	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4577MH0008340031604237C00	4237	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4577MH0008340031604238C00	4238	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
4577MH0008340031604239C00	4239	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4577MH0008340031604240C00	4240	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4577MH0008340031604241C00	4241	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2025

SOL 4577 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Copacabana - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4577MH0008350011604243C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4578MH0001630001604253R00	4253	MOTOR COUNT:		15221	RANGE (cm):	2.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4578MH0001630001604254S00	4254	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00835	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4577	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4578	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4577MH0008350031604245C00	4245	15101	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	255	1
4577MH0008350031604246C00	4246	15131	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	223	2
4577MH0008350031604247C00	4247	15161	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	191	3
4577MH0008350031604248C00	4248	15191	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	159	4
4577MH0008350031604249C00	4249	15221	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	127	5
4577MH0008350031604250C00	4250	15251	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	95	6
4577MH0008350031604251C00	4251	15281	2.51	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7
4577MH0008350031604252C00	4252	15311	2.46	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 25_June_2025

SOL 4580 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Hornitos - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4580MH0008790011604269C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4580MH0001930001604305R00	4305	MOTOR COUNT:		14040	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4580MH0001930001604306S00	4306	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4580	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4580		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4580MH0008790031604271C00	4271	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
4580MH0008790031604272C00	4272	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2
4580MH0008790031604273C00	4273	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4580MH0008790031604274C00	4274	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4580MH0008790031604275C00	4275	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
4580MH0008790031604276C00	4276	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4580MH0008790031604277C00	4277	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4580MH0008790031604278C00	4278	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 25_June_2025

SOL 4580 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Hornitos - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4580MH0008790011604280C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4580MH0001930001604303R00	4303	MOTOR COUNT:		14043	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4580MH0001930001604304S00	4304	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4580	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4580		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4580MH0008790031604282C00	4282	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	255	1
4580MH0008790031604283C00	4283	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	223	2
4580MH0008790031604284C00	4284	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4580MH0008790031604285C00	4285	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
4580MH0008790031604286C00	4286	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4580MH0008790031604287C00	4287	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4580MH0008790031604288C00	4288	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
4580MH0008790031604289C00	4289	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 25_June_2025

SOL 4580 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Hornitos - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4580MH0008350011604291C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4580MH0001930001604301R00		4301		MOTOR COUNT:		15234		RANGE (cm):	2.6
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4580MH0001930001604302S00		4302		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00835	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		25-Jun-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4580		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4580	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4580MH0008350031604293C00	4293	15114	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	255	1		
4580MH0008350031604294C00	4294	15144	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	223	2		
4580MH0008350031604295C00	4295	15174	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	191	3		
4580MH0008350031604296C00	4296	15204	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	159	4		
4580MH0008350031604297C00	4297	15234	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	127	5		
4580MH0008350031604298C00	4298	15264	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	95	6		
4580MH0008350031604299C00	4299	15294	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7		
4580MH0008350031604300C00	4300	15324	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8		

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SOL 4584 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Santa_Elena - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4584MH0008760011604317C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4585MH0002270001604374R00	4374	MOTOR COUNT:		13018	RANGE (cm):	26.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4585MH0002270001604375S00	4375	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4584	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4585	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4584MH0008760021604318C00	4318	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	255	1
4584MH0008760021604319C00	4319	12982	28.82	-2.1	2.4	108.3	7.9	223	2
4584MH0008760021604320C00	4320	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	191	3
4584MH0008760021604321C00	4321	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	159	4
4584MH0008760021604322C00	4322	13018	26.46	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	127	5
4584MH0008760021604323C00	4323	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	95	6
4584MH0008760021604324C00	4324	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	63	7
4584MH0008760021604325C00	4325	13054	24.43	-1.5	1.7	92.9	5.6	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2025

SOL 4584 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4584MH0001820011604327C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4585MH0002270001604372R00	4372	MOTOR COUNT:		14012	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4585MH0002270001604373S00	4373	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jun-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4584	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4585	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4584MH0001820021604328C00	4328	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
4584MH0001820021604329C00	4329	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4584MH0001820021604330C00	4330	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4584MH0001820021604331C00	4331	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4584MH0001820021604332C00	4332	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4584MH0001820021604333C00	4333	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
4584MH0001820021604334C00	4334	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4584MH0001820021604335C00	4335	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2025

SOL 4584 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4584MH0001820011604337C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4585MH0002270001604370R00	4370	MOTOR COUNT:		14018	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4585MH0002270001604371S00	4371	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4584	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4585		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4584MH0001820021604338C00	4338	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4584MH0001820021604339C00	4339	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4584MH0001820021604340C00	4340	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4584MH0001820021604341C00	4341	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4584MH0001820021604342C00	4342	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4584MH0001820021604343C00	4343	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	95	6
4584MH0001820021604344C00	4344	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
4584MH0001820021604345C00	4345	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4584 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ticatica - stereo-1 - ~26 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4584MH0008650011604347C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4585MH0002270001604368R00	4368	MOTOR COUNT:		13003	RANGE (cm):	27.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4585MH0002270001604369S00	4369	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jun-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4584	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4585		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4584MH0008650021604348C00	4348	12907	35.21	-3.0	3.7	130.8	11.8	255	1
4584MH0008650021604349C00	4349	12931	32.90	-2.7	3.2	122.7	10.3	223	2
4584MH0008650021604350C00	4350	12955	30.85	-2.4	2.8	115.5	9.0	191	3
4584MH0008650021604351C00	4351	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	159	4
4584MH0008650021604352C00	4352	13003	27.40	-1.9	2.1	103.3	7.1	127	5
4584MH0008650021604353C00	4353	13027	25.93	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	95	6
4584MH0008650021604354C00	4354	13051	24.59	-1.5	1.7	93.5	5.7	63	7
4584MH0008650021604355C00	4355	13075	23.37	-1.4	1.5	89.2	5.1	31	8

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SOL 4584 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ticatica - stereo-2 - ~26 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4584MH0008650011604357C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4585MH0002270001604366R00		4366		MOTOR COUNT:		12994		RANGE (cm):	28.0
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4585MH0002270001604367S00		4367		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865		STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		29-Jun-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4584		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4585	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4584MH0008650021604358C00	4358	12898	36.15	-3.2	3.9	134.2	12.4	255	1		
4584MH0008650021604359C00	4359	12922	33.73	-2.8	3.3	125.6	10.8	223	2		
4584MH0008650021604360C00	4360	12946	31.59	-2.5	2.9	118.1	9.5	191	3		
4584MH0008650021604361C00	4361	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	159	4		
4584MH0008650021604362C00	4362	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	127	5		
4584MH0008650021604363C00	4363	13018	26.46	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	95	6		
4584MH0008650021604364C00	4364	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	63	7		
4584MH0008650021604365C00	4365	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	31	8		

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SOL 4586 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4586MH0008760011604377C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4587MH0001630001604451R00	4451	MOTOR COUNT:		13018	RANGE (cm):	26.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4587MH0001630001604452S00	4452	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4586	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4587		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4586MH0008760021604378C00	4378	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	255	1
4586MH0008760021604379C00	4379	12982	28.82	-2.1	2.4	108.3	7.9	223	2
4586MH0008760021604380C00	4380	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	191	3
4586MH0008760021604381C00	4381	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	159	4
4586MH0008760021604382C00	4382	13018	26.46	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	127	5
4586MH0008760021604383C00	4383	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	95	6
4586MH0008760021604384C00	4384	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	63	7
4586MH0008760021604385C00	4385	13054	24.43	-1.5	1.7	92.9	5.6	31	8

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SOL 4586 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4586MH0001730011604387C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4587MH0001630001604449R00	4449	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4587MH0001630001604450S00	4450	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4586	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4587		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4586MH0001730021604388C00	4388	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
4586MH0001730021604389C00	4389	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
4586MH0001730021604390C00	4390	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
4586MH0001730021604391C00	4391	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4586MH0001730021604392C00	4392	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4586MH0001730021604393C00	4393	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4586MH0001730021604394C00	4394	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4586MH0001730021604395C00	4395	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4586 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4586MH0001730011604397C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4587MH0001630001604447R00	4447	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4587MH0001630001604448S00	4448	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4586	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4587		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4586MH0001730021604398C00	4398	13873	7.76	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
4586MH0001730021604399C00	4399	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
4586MH0001730021604400C00	4400	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
4586MH0001730021604401C00	4401	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4586MH0001730021604402C00	4402	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4586MH0001730021604403C00	4403	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4586MH0001730021604404C00	4404	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4586MH0001730021604405C00	4405	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4586 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Paz - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4586MH0008760011604407C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4587MH0001630001604445R00	4445	MOTOR COUNT:		13016	RANGE (cm):	26.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4587MH0001630001604446S00	4446	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4586	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4587		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4586MH0008760021604408C00	4408	12968	29.84	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	255	1
4586MH0008760021604409C00	4409	12980	28.96	-2.1	2.4	108.8	7.9	223	2
4586MH0008760021604410C00	4410	12992	28.13	-2.0	2.3	105.9	7.5	191	3
4586MH0008760021604411C00	4411	13004	27.34	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	159	4
4586MH0008760021604412C00	4412	13016	26.58	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	127	5
4586MH0008760021604413C00	4413	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	95	6
4586MH0008760021604414C00	4414	13040	25.19	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	63	7
4586MH0008760021604415C00	4415	13052	24.54	-1.5	1.7	93.3	5.7	31	8

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SOL 4586 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Paz - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4586MH0001730011604417C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4587MH0001630001604443R00		4443		MOTOR COUNT:		13980		RANGE (cm): 7.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4587MH0001630001604444S00		4444		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		1-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4586		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4587	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4586MH0001730021604418C00	4418	13860	7.86	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1		
4586MH0001730021604419C00	4419	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2		
4586MH0001730021604420C00	4420	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3		
4586MH0001730021604421C00	4421	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4		
4586MH0001730021604422C00	4422	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5		
4586MH0001730021604423C00	4423	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6		
4586MH0001730021604424C00	4424	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7		
4586MH0001730021604425C00	4425	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4586 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Paz - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4586MH0001730011604427C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4587MH0001630001604441R00		4441		MOTOR COUNT:		13986		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4587MH0001630001604442S00		4442		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		1-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4586		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4587	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4586MH0001730021604428C00	4428	13866	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1		
4586MH0001730021604429C00	4429	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2		
4586MH0001730021604430C00	4430	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3		
4586MH0001730021604431C00	4431	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4		
4586MH0001730021604432C00	4432	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5		
4586MH0001730021604433C00	4433	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6		
4586MH0001730021604434C00	4434	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7		
4586MH0001730021604435C00	4435	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4588 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Guapay - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4588MH0008790011604457C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4588MH0001930001604493R00		4493		MOTOR COUNT:		14044		RANGE (cm): 6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4588MH0001930001604494S00		4494		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4588		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4588	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4588MH0008790031604459C00	4459	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	255	1		
4588MH0008790031604460C00	4460	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	223	2		
4588MH0008790031604461C00	4461	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	191	3		
4588MH0008790031604462C00	4462	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4		
4588MH0008790031604463C00	4463	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5		
4588MH0008790031604464C00	4464	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6		
4588MH0008790031604465C00	4465	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7		
4588MH0008790031604466C00	4466	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4588 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Guapay - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4588MH0008790011604468C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4588MH0001930001604491R00		4491		MOTOR COUNT:		14040		RANGE (cm): 6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4588MH0001930001604492S00		4492		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4588		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4588	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4588MH0008790031604470C00	4470	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1		
4588MH0008790031604471C00	4471	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2		
4588MH0008790031604472C00	4472	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3		
4588MH0008790031604473C00	4473	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4		
4588MH0008790031604474C00	4474	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5		
4588MH0008790031604475C00	4475	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6		
4588MH0008790031604476C00	4476	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7		
4588MH0008790031604477C00	4477	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4588 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Guapay – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4588MH0008350011604479C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4588MH0001930001604489R00	4489	MOTOR COUNT:		15163	RANGE (cm):		2.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4588MH0001930001604490S00	4490	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00835		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jul-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4588		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4588
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4588MH0008350031604481C00	4481	15043	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	255	1
4588MH0008350031604482C00	4482	15073	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	223	2
4588MH0008350031604483C00	4483	15103	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	191	3
4588MH0008350031604484C00	4484	15133	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
4588MH0008350031604485C00	4485	15163	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
4588MH0008350031604486C00	4486	15193	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
4588MH0008350031604487C00	4487	15223	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
4588MH0008350031604488C00	4488	15253	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4590 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4590MH0008340011604499C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4591MH0002270001604561R00	4561	MOTOR COUNT:	14006	RANGE (cm):	6.8			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4591MH0002270001604562S00	4562	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4590	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4591			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4590MH0008340031604501C00	4501	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4590MH0008340031604502C00	4502	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4590MH0008340031604503C00	4503	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4590MH0008340031604504C00	4504	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4590MH0008340031604505C00	4505	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4590MH0008340031604506C00	4506	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4590MH0008340031604507C00	4507	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	63	7
4590MH0008340031604508C00	4508	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4590 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4590MH0008340011604510C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4591MH0002270001604559R00	4559	MOTOR COUNT:	14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4591MH0002270001604560S00	4560	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4590	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4591			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4590MH0008340031604512C00	4512	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4590MH0008340031604513C00	4513	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4590MH0008340031604514C00	4514	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4590MH0008340031604515C00	4515	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4590MH0008340031604516C00	4516	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4590MH0008340031604517C00	4517	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4590MH0008340031604518C00	4518	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4590MH0008340031604519C00	4519	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4590 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4590MH0008340011604521C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4591MH0002270001604557R00	4557	MOTOR COUNT:		14014	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4591MH0002270001604558S00	4558	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4590	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4591		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4590MH0008340031604523C00	4523	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4590MH0008340031604524C00	4524	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4590MH0008340031604525C00	4525	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4590MH0008340031604526C00	4526	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4590MH0008340031604527C00	4527	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4590MH0008340031604528C00	4528	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4590MH0008340031604529C00	4529	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4590MH0008340031604530C00	4530	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4590 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4590MH0008010011604532C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4591MH0002270001604555R00	4555	MOTOR COUNT:		14985	RANGE (cm):	3.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4591MH0002270001604556S00	4556	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00801	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4590	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4591		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4590MH0008010031604534C00	4534	14841	3.41	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	255	1
4590MH0008010031604535C00	4535	14877	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	223	2
4590MH0008010031604536C00	4536	14913	3.23	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	191	3
4590MH0008010031604537C00	4537	14949	3.15	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	159	4
4590MH0008010031604538C00	4538	14985	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	127	5
4590MH0008010031604539C00	4539	15021	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	95	6
4590MH0008010031604540C00	4540	15057	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	63	7
4590MH0008010031604541C00	4541	15093	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4590 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4590MH0008010011604543C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4591MH0002270001604553R00		4553		MOTOR COUNT:		15012		RANGE (cm):	3.0
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4591MH0002270001604554S00		4554		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00801	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Jul-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4590		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4591	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4590MH0008010031604545C00	4545	14868	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	255	1		
4590MH0008010031604546C00	4546	14904	3.25	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	223	2		
4590MH0008010031604547C00	4547	14940	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	191	3		
4590MH0008010031604548C00	4548	14976	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	159	4		
4590MH0008010031604549C00	4549	15012	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	127	5		
4590MH0008010031604550C00	4550	15048	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	95	6		
4590MH0008010031604551C00	4551	15084	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	63	7		
4590MH0008010031604552C00	4552	15120	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	31	8		

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SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pan_De_Azucar – mosaic position 1 of 3 – ~50 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0008990011604564C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4594MH0004490001504693R00		4693		MOTOR COUNT:		12796		RANGE (cm): 51.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4594MH0004490001404694S00		4694		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00899		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4593		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4593MH0008990021604565C00	4565	12628	155.39	-46.2	118.2	553.9	289.4	255	1		
4593MH0008990021604566C00	4566	12670	104.00	-22.9	41.9	373.0	114.0	223	2		
4593MH0008990021604567C00	4567	12712	77.91	-13.6	21.2	281.1	61.1	191	3		
4593MH0008990021604568C00	4568	12754	62.11	-8.9	12.6	225.5	37.9	159	4		
4593MH0008990021604569C00	4569	12796	51.52	-6.3	8.3	188.3	25.7	127	5		
4593MH0008990021604570C00	4570	12838	43.92	-4.6	5.9	161.5	18.5	95	6		
4593MH0008990021604571C00	4571	12880	38.19	-3.6	4.4	141.4	13.9	63	7		
4593MH0008990021604572C00	4572	12922	33.73	-2.8	3.3	125.6	10.8	31	8		

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SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pan_De_Azucar – mosaic position 2 of 3 – ~35 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0008990011604574C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4594MH0004490001504691R00		4691		MOTOR COUNT:		12896		RANGE (cm): 36.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4594MH0004490001504692S00		4692		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00899		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4593		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4593MH0008990021604575C00	4575	12728	71.05	-11.4	17.1	257.0	50.3	255	1		
4593MH0008990021604576C00	4576	12770	57.62	-7.7	10.7	209.7	32.4	223	2		
4593MH0008990021604577C00	4577	12812	48.35	-5.6	7.3	177.1	22.6	191	3		
4593MH0008990021604578C00	4578	12854	41.56	-4.2	5.2	153.2	16.5	159	4		
4593MH0008990021604579C00	4579	12896	36.37	-3.2	3.9	134.9	12.6	127	5		
4593MH0008990021604580C00	4580	12938	32.28	-2.6	3.0	120.5	9.9	95	6		
4593MH0008990021604581C00	4581	12980	28.96	-2.1	2.4	108.8	7.9	63	7		
4593MH0008990021604582C00	4582	13022	26.22	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	31	8		

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SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pan_De_Azucar – mosaic position 3 of 3 – ~31 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0008990011604584C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4594MH0004490001504689R00	4689		MOTOR COUNT:		12936	RANGE (cm):	32.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4594MH0004490001504690S00	4690		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00899	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Jul-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4593	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4593MH0008990021604585C00	4585	12768	58.15	-7.9	10.9	211.6	33.1	255	1
4593MH0008990021604586C00	4586	12810	48.72	-5.7	7.4	178.4	22.9	223	2
4593MH0008990021604587C00	4587	12852	41.84	-4.2	5.3	154.2	16.8	191	3
4593MH0008990021604588C00	4588	12894	36.59	-3.3	4.0	135.7	12.7	159	4
4593MH0008990021604589C00	4589	12936	32.45	-2.6	3.1	121.1	10.0	127	5
4593MH0008990021604590C00	4590	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	95	6
4593MH0008990021604591C00	4591	13020	26.34	-1.8	2.0	99.6	6.6	63	7
4593MH0008990021604592C00	4592	13062	24.02	-1.5	1.6	91.5	5.4	31	8

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SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Parinacota – after DRT – ~25 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0003590011604594C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4594MH0004490001504687R00	4687		MOTOR COUNT:		13018	RANGE (cm):	26.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4594MH0004490001504688S00	4688		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Jul-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4593	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4593MH0003590021604595C00	4595	12946	31.59	-2.5	2.9	118.1	9.5	255	1
4593MH0003590021604596C00	4596	12964	30.15	-2.3	2.6	113.0	8.6	223	2
4593MH0003590021604597C00	4597	12982	28.82	-2.1	2.4	108.3	7.9	191	3
4593MH0003590021604598C00	4598	13000	27.59	-1.9	2.2	104.0	7.2	159	4
4593MH0003590021604599C00	4599	13018	26.46	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	127	5
4593MH0003590021604600C00	4600	13036	25.41	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	95	6
4593MH0003590021604601C00	4601	13054	24.43	-1.5	1.7	92.9	5.6	63	7
4593MH0003590021604602C00	4602	13072	23.52	-1.4	1.6	89.7	5.2	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2025

SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Parinacota – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0001680011604604C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4594MH0004490001504685R00		4685		MOTOR COUNT:		13999		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4594MH0004490001504686S00		4686		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4593		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4593MH0001680021604605C00	4605	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1		
4593MH0001680021604606C00	4606	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2		
4593MH0001680021604607C00	4607	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3		
4593MH0001680021604608C00	4608	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4		
4593MH0001680021604609C00	4609	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5		
4593MH0001680021604610C00	4610	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6		
4593MH0001680021604611C00	4611	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7		
4593MH0001680021604612C00	4612	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Parinacota – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0001680011604614C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4594MH0004490001504683R00		4683		MOTOR COUNT:		14002		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4594MH0004490001504684S00		4684		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4593		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4593MH0001680021604615C00	4615	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1		
4593MH0001680021604616C00	4616	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2		
4593MH0001680021604617C00	4617	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3		
4593MH0001680021604618C00	4618	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4		
4593MH0001680021604619C00	4619	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5		
4593MH0001680021604620C00	4620	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6		
4593MH0001680021604621C00	4621	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7		
4593MH0001680021604622C00	4622	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Parinacota – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0008640011604624C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4594MH0004490001504681R00	4681	MOTOR COUNT:		15000	RANGE (cm):	3.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4594MH0004490001504682S00	4682	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4593	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4593MH0008640021604625C00	4625	14880	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	255	1
4593MH0008640021604626C00	4626	14910	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	223	2
4593MH0008640021604627C00	4627	14940	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	191	3
4593MH0008640021604628C00	4628	14970	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	159	4
4593MH0008640021604629C00	4629	15000	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	127	5
4593MH0008640021604630C00	4630	15030	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	95	6
4593MH0008640021604631C00	4631	15060	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	63	7
4593MH0008640021604632C00	4632	15090	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2025

SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wila_Willki – ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0008650011604634C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4594MH0004490001504679R00	4679	MOTOR COUNT:		13010	RANGE (cm):	27.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4594MH0004490001504680S00	4680	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4593	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4593MH0008650021604635C00	4635	12914	34.50	-2.9	3.5	128.4	11.3	255	1
4593MH0008650021604636C00	4636	12938	32.28	-2.6	3.0	120.5	9.9	223	2
4593MH0008650021604637C00	4637	12962	30.30	-2.3	2.7	113.6	8.7	191	3
4593MH0008650021604638C00	4638	12986	28.54	-2.0	2.3	107.4	7.7	159	4
4593MH0008650021604639C00	4639	13010	26.95	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	127	5
4593MH0008650021604640C00	4640	13034	25.52	-1.7	1.8	96.7	6.1	95	6
4593MH0008650021604641C00	4641	13058	24.22	-1.5	1.7	92.2	5.5	63	7
4593MH0008650021604642C00	4642	13082	23.04	-1.4	1.5	88.0	5.0	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2025

SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wila_Willki - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0002240011604644C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4594MH0004490001504677R00	4677	MOTOR COUNT:		13978	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4594MH0004490001504678S00	4678	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4593	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4593MH0002240021604645C00	4645	13810	8.28	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
4593MH0002240021604646C00	4646	13852	7.93	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	223	2
4593MH0002240021604647C00	4647	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	191	3
4593MH0002240021604648C00	4648	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
4593MH0002240021604649C00	4649	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
4593MH0002240021604650C00	4650	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4593MH0002240021604651C00	4651	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4593MH0002240021604652C00	4652	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2025

SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wila_Willki - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0002240011604654C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4594MH0004490001504675R00	4675	MOTOR COUNT:		13956	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4594MH0004490001504676S00	4676	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4593	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4593MH0002240021604655C00	4655	13788	8.48	-0.2	0.2	36.7	0.8	255	1
4593MH0002240021604656C00	4656	13830	8.11	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	223	2
4593MH0002240021604657C00	4657	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3
4593MH0002240021604658C00	4658	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	159	4
4593MH0002240021604659C00	4659	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
4593MH0002240021604660C00	4660	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4593MH0002240021604661C00	4661	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4593MH0002240021604662C00	4662	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2025

SOL 4593 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wila_Willki – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4593MH0003350011604664C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4594MH0004490001504673R00	4673	MOTOR COUNT:		14590	RANGE (cm):		4.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4594MH0004490001504674S00	4674	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00335	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4593	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4594	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4593MH0003350021604665C00	4665	14374	4.90	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	255	1
4593MH0003350021504666C00	4666	14428	4.69	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	223	2
4593MH0003350021504667C00	4667	14482	4.49	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	191	3
4593MH0003350021504668C00	4668	14536	4.30	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	159	4
4593MH0003350021504669C00	4669	14590	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	127	5
4593MH0003350021504670C00	4670	14644	3.95	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	95	6
4593MH0003350021504671C00	4671	14698	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	63	7
4593MH0003350021504672C00	4672	14752	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 14_July_2025

SOL 4595 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rio_Ivirizu - ~24 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4595MH0003590011404696C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4596MH0001630001004767R00		4767		MOTOR COUNT:		13033		RANGE (cm): 25.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4596MH0001630001004768S00		4768		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4595		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4596	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4595MH0003590021404697C00	4697	12961	30.38	-2.3	2.7	113.8	8.7	255	1		
4595MH0003590021404698C00	4698	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	223	2		
4595MH0003590021404699C00	4699	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	191	3		
4595MH0003590021404700C00	4700	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	159	4		
4595MH0003590021404701C00	4701	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	127	5		
4595MH0003590021404702C00	4702	13051	24.59	-1.5	1.7	93.5	5.7	95	6		
4595MH0003590021404703C00	4703	13069	23.67	-1.4	1.6	90.2	5.3	63	7		
4595MH0003590021404704C00	4704	13087	22.81	-1.3	1.5	87.2	4.9	31	8		

UPDATED: 14_July_2025

SOL 4595 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rio_Ivirizu - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4595MH0002240011404706C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4596MH0001630001004765R00		4765		MOTOR COUNT:		14277		RANGE (cm): 5.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4596MH0001630001004766S00		4766		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4595		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4596	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4595MH0002240021404707C00	4707	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	255	1		
4595MH0002240021404708C00	4708	14151	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	223	2		
4595MH0002240021404709C00	4709	14193	5.73	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	191	3		
4595MH0002240021404710C00	4710	14235	5.52	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	159	4		
4595MH0002240021404711C00	4711	14277	5.32	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	127	5		
4595MH0002240021404712C00	4712	14319	5.13	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	95	6		
4595MH0002240021404713C00	4713	14361	4.96	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	63	7		
4595MH0002240021404714C00	4714	14403	4.79	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.4	31	8		

UPDATED: 14_July_2025

SOL 4595 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rio_Ivirizu – stereo-2 – ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4595MH0002240011404716C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4596MH0001630001004763R00	4763	MOTOR COUNT:		14280	RANGE (cm):	5.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4596MH0001630001004764S00	4764	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4595	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4596		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4595MH0002240021404717C00	4717	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	255	1
4595MH0002240021404718C00	4718	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	223	2
4595MH0002240021404719C00	4719	14196	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	191	3
4595MH0002240021404720C00	4720	14238	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	159	4
4595MH0002240021404721C00	4721	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	127	5
4595MH0002240021404722C00	4722	14322	5.12	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	95	6
4595MH0002240021404723C00	4723	14364	4.94	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	63	7
4595MH0002240021404724C00	4724	14406	4.77	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 14_July_2025

SOL 4595 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cataratas_Del_Jardin – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4595MH0003360011404728C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4596MH0001630001104761R00	4761	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4596MH0001630001104762S00	4762	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4595	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4596		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4595MH0003360021404729C00	4729	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4595MH0003360021404730C00	4730	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4595MH0003360021404731C00	4731	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4595MH0003360021404732C00	4732	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4595MH0003360021404733C00	4733	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4595MH0003360021404734C00	4734	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4595MH0003360021404735C00	4735	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4595MH0003360021304736C00	4736	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 14_July_2025

SOL 4595 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cataratas_Del_Jardin – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4595MH0003360011204738C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4596MH0001630001104759R00	4759	MOTOR COUNT:		13989	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4596MH0001630001104760S00	4760	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4595	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4596	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4595MH0003360021204739C00	4739	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4595MH0003360021204740C00	4740	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4595MH0003360021204741C00	4741	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4595MH0003360021204742C00	4742	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4595MH0003360021204743C00	4743	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4595MH0003360021204744C00	4744	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4595MH0003360021204745C00	4745	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4595MH0003360021204746C00	4746	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 14_July_2025

SOL 4595 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cataratas_Del_Jardin – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4595MH0008480011204748C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4596MH0001630001104757R00	4757	MOTOR COUNT:		14835	RANGE (cm):	3.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4596MH0001630001104758S00	4758	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4595	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4596	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4595MH0008480021204749C00	4749	14739	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	255	1
4595MH0008480021204750C00	4750	14763	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	223	2
4595MH0008480021204751C00	4751	14787	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	191	3
4595MH0008480021104752C00	4752	14811	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	159	4
4595MH0008480021104753C00	4753	14835	3.42	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	127	5
4595MH0008480021104754C00	4754	14859	3.36	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	95	6
4595MH0008480021104755C00	4755	14883	3.30	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	63	7
4595MH0008480021104756C00	4756	14907	3.25	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 15_July_2025

SOL 4597 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Cochabamba – after DRT – stereo-1 – relief model position 1 – ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4597MH0003360011004772C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4598MH0005360001700017R00	17	MOTOR COUNT:		13991	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4598MH0005360001700018S00	18	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4597	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4598		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4597MH0003360021004773C00	4773	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4597MH0003360021004774C00	4774	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4597MH0003360021004775C00	4775	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4597MH0003360021004776C00	4776	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4597MH0003360021004777C00	4777	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4597MH0003360021004778C00	4778	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4597MH0003360021004779C00	4779	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4597MH0003360021004780C00	4780	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4597 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Cochabamba – after DRT – stereo-2 – relief model position 2 – ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4597MH0003360011004782C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4598MH0005360001700015R00	15	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4598MH0005360001700016S00	16	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4597	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4598		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4597MH0003360021004783C00	4783	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4597MH0003360021004784C00	4784	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4597MH0003360021004785C00	4785	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4597MH0003360021004786C00	4786	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4597MH0003360021004787C00	4787	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4597MH0003360021004788C00	4788	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4597MH0003360021004789C00	4789	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4597MH0003360021004790C00	4790	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4597 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cochabamba – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4597MH0008480011004798C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4598MH0005360001700013R00	13	MOTOR COUNT:		15069	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4598MH0005360001700014S00	14	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4597	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4598		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4597MH0008480021004799C00	4799	14973	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
4597MH0008480021004800C00	4800	14997	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
4597MH0008480021004801C00	4801	15021	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	191	3
4597MH0008480021004802C00	4802	15045	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	159	4
4597MH0008480021004803C00	4803	15069	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	127	5
4597MH0008480021004804C00	4804	15093	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	95	6
4597MH0008480021004805C00	4805	15117	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	63	7
4597MH0008480021004806C00	4806	15141	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4597 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Incachaca – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4597MH0003080011004810C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4598MH0005360001700011R00	11	MOTOR COUNT:		13966	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4598MH0005360001700012S00	12	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4597	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4598		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4597MH0003080021004811C00	4811	13702	9.31	-0.3	0.3	39.7	0.9	255	1
4597MH0003080021004812C00	4812	13768	8.66	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	223	2
4597MH0003080021004813C00	4813	13834	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	191	3
4597MH0003080021004814C00	4814	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
4597MH0003080021004815C00	4815	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
4597MH0003080021004816C00	4816	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4597MH0003080021004817C00	4817	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
4597MH0003080021004818C00	4818	14164	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4597 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Incachaca - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4597MH0003080011004820C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4598MH0005360001700009R00	9	MOTOR COUNT:		13975	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4598MH0005360001700010S00	10	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4597	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4598		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4597MH0003080021004821C00	4821	13711	9.22	-0.3	0.3	39.3	0.9	255	1
4597MH0003080021004822C00	4822	13777	8.58	-0.2	0.2	37.1	0.8	223	2
4597MH0003080021004823C00	4823	13843	8.00	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	191	3
4597MH0003080021004824C00	4824	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	159	4
4597MH0003080021004825C00	4825	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
4597MH0003080021004826C00	4826	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4597MH0003080021004827C00	4827	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
4597MH0003080021004828C00	4828	14173	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4597 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Incachaca - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4597MH0003570010904830C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4598MH0005360001700007R00	7	MOTOR COUNT:		14624	RANGE (cm):	4.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4598MH0005360001700008S00	8	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00357	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		84	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4597	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4598		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4597MH0003570020904831C00	4831	14288	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	255	1
4597MH0003570020904832C00	4832	14372	4.91	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	223	2
4597MH0003570020904833C00	4833	14456	4.58	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	191	3
4597MH0003570020904834C00	4834	14540	4.28	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	159	4
4597MH0003570020904835C00	4835	14624	4.01	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	127	5
4597MH0003570020904836C00	4836	14708	3.76	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	95	6
4597MH0003570020904837C00	4837	14792	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	63	7
4597MH0003570020904838C00	4838	14876	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4597 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tejas – ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4597MH0008760010904840C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4598MH0005360001700005R00	5	MOTOR COUNT:		13022	RANGE (cm):	26.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4598MH0005360001700006S00	6	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4597	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4598		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4597MH0008760020904841C00	4841	12974	29.40	-2.2	2.5	110.4	8.2	255	1
4597MH0008760020904842C00	4842	12986	28.54	-2.0	2.3	107.4	7.7	223	2
4597MH0008760020904843C00	4843	12998	27.73	-1.9	2.2	104.5	7.3	191	3
4597MH0008760020904844C00	4844	13010	26.95	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	159	4
4597MH0008760020904845C00	4845	13022	26.22	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	127	5
4597MH0008760020904846C00	4846	13034	25.52	-1.7	1.8	96.7	6.1	95	6
4597MH0008760020904847C00	4847	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	63	7
4597MH0008760020904848C00	4848	13058	24.22	-1.5	1.7	92.2	5.5	31	8

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SOL 4597 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tejas – stereo-1 – ~95 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4597MH0008780010804850C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4598MH0005360001700003R00	3	MOTOR COUNT:		13517	RANGE (cm):	11.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4598MH0005360001700004S00	4	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00878	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4597	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4598		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4597MH0008780020804851C00	4851	13445	12.74	-0.5	0.5	51.7	1.6	255	1
4597MH0008780020804852C00	4852	13463	12.44	-0.4	0.4	50.7	1.5	223	2
4597MH0008780020804853C00	4853	13481	12.14	-0.4	0.4	49.7	1.5	191	3
4597MH0008780020804854C00	4854	13499	11.87	-0.4	0.4	48.7	1.4	159	4
4597MH0008780020604855C00	4855	13517	11.60	-0.4	0.4	47.7	1.3	127	5
4597MH0008780020604856C00	4856	13535	11.34	-0.4	0.4	46.8	1.3	95	6
4597MH0008780020604857C00	4857	13553	11.09	-0.4	0.4	45.9	1.3	63	7
4597MH0008780020604858C00	4858	13571	10.84	-0.3	0.3	45.1	1.2	31	8

UPDATED: 15_July_2025

SOL 4597 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tejas - stereo-2 - ~95 mm standoff										
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4597MH0008780010604860C00						
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4598MH0005360001800001R00		1		MOTOR COUNT:		13525		RANGE (cm): 11.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4598MH0005360001700002S00		2		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00878		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		12-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE: BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4597		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4598	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8			
				NEAR	FAR							
4597MH0008780020604861C00	4861	13453	12.60	-0.5	0.4	51.3	1.6	255	1			
4597MH0008780020604862C00	4862	13471	12.30	-0.4	0.4	50.2	1.5	223	2			
4597MH0008780020604863C00	4863	13489	12.02	-0.4	0.4	49.2	1.4	191	3			
4597MH0008780020604864C00	4864	13507	11.74	-0.4	0.4	48.2	1.4	159	4			
4597MH0008780020604865C00	4865	13525	11.48	-0.4	0.4	47.3	1.3	127	5			
4597MH0008780020604866C00	4866	13543	11.22	-0.4	0.4	46.4	1.3	95	6			
4597MH0008780020604867C00	4867	13561	10.98	-0.4	0.3	45.5	1.2	63	7			
4597MH0008780020604868C00	4868	13579	10.74	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	31	8			

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SOL 4600 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4600MH0008790011700029C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4600MH0007030001700074R00	74	MOTOR COUNT:		14057	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4600MH0007030001700075S00	75	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00703	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4600	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4600		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4600MH0008790031700031C00	31	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	255	1
4600MH0008790031700032C00	32	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	223	2
4600MH0008790031700033C00	33	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	191	3
4600MH0008790031700034C00	34	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	159	4
4600MH0008790031700035C00	35	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	127	5
4600MH0008790031700036C00	36	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4600MH0008790031700037C00	37	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4600MH0008790031700038C00	38	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4600 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4600MH0008790011700040C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4600MH0007030001700072R00	72	MOTOR COUNT:		14067	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4600MH0007030001700073S00	73	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00703	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4600	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4600		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4600MH0008790031700042C00	42	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	255	1
4600MH0008790031700043C00	43	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	223	2
4600MH0008790031700044C00	44	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	191	3
4600MH0008790031700045C00	45	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	159	4
4600MH0008790031700046C00	46	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	127	5
4600MH0008790031700047C00	47	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	95	6
4600MH0008790031700048C00	48	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
4600MH0008790031700049C00	49	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4602 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Nocarane - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4602MH0003590011700077C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4602MH0001930001700110R00	110	MOTOR COUNT:		13031	RANGE (cm):	25.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4602MH0001930001700111S00	111	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4602	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4602		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4602MH0003590021700078C00	78	12959	30.54	-2.3	2.7	114.4	8.8	255	1
4602MH0003590021700079C00	79	12977	29.18	-2.1	2.4	109.6	8.0	223	2
4602MH0003590021700080C00	80	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	191	3
4602MH0003590021700081C00	81	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	159	4
4602MH0003590021700082C00	82	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	127	5
4602MH0003590021700083C00	83	13049	24.70	-1.6	1.7	93.8	5.8	95	6
4602MH0003590021700084C00	84	13067	23.77	-1.4	1.6	90.6	5.3	63	7
4602MH0003590021700085C00	85	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	31	8

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SOL 4602 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Nocarane - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4602MH0001730011700087C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4602MH0001930001700108R00	108	MOTOR COUNT:		14160	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4602MH0001930001700109S00	109	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4602	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4602		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4602MH0001730021700088C00	88	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	255	1
4602MH0001730021700089C00	89	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
4602MH0001730021700090C00	90	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	191	3
4602MH0001730021700091C00	91	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	159	4
4602MH0001730021700092C00	92	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4602MH0001730021700093C00	93	14190	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	95	6
4602MH0001730021700094C00	94	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7
4602MH0001730021700095C00	95	14250	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 18_July_2025

SOL 4602 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Nocarane - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4602MH0001730011700097C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4602MH0001930001700106R00	106	MOTOR COUNT:		14167	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4602MH0001930001700107S00	107	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4602	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4602	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4602MH0001730021700098C00	98	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	255	1
4602MH0001730021700099C00	99	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	223	2
4602MH0001730021700100C00	100	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	191	3
4602MH0001730021700101C00	101	14137	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	159	4
4602MH0001730021700102C00	102	14167	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	127	5
4602MH0001730021700103C00	103	14197	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	95	6
4602MH0001730021700104C00	104	14227	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	63	7
4602MH0001730021700105C00	105	14257	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 23_July_2025

SOL 4604 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Vicuna - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4604MH0003590011700113C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4605MH0005360001700218R00	218	MOTOR COUNT:		13015	RANGE (cm):	26.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4605MH0005360001700219S00	219	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4604	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4605		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4604MH0003590021700114C00	114	12943	31.85	-2.5	2.9	119.0	9.6	255	1
4604MH0003590021700115C00	115	12961	30.38	-2.3	2.7	113.8	8.7	223	2
4604MH0003590021700116C00	116	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	191	3
4604MH0003590021700117C00	117	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	159	4
4604MH0003590021700118C00	118	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	127	5
4604MH0003590021700119C00	119	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	95	6
4604MH0003590021700120C00	120	13051	24.59	-1.5	1.7	93.5	5.7	63	7
4604MH0003590021700121C00	121	13069	23.67	-1.4	1.6	90.2	5.3	31	8

UPDATED: 23_July_2025

SOL 4604 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Vicuna - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4604MH0002240011700123C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4605MH0005360001700216R00	216	MOTOR COUNT:		14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4605MH0005360001700217S00	217	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4604	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4605		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4604MH0002240021700124C00	124	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
4604MH0002240021700125C00	125	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
4604MH0002240021700126C00	126	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
4604MH0002240021700127C00	127	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
4604MH0002240021700128C00	128	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4604MH0002240021700129C00	129	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4604MH0002240021700130C00	130	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
4604MH0002240021700131C00	131	14134	6.04	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_July_2025

SOL 4604 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Vicuna - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4604MH0002240011700133C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4605MH0005360001700214R00	214	MOTOR COUNT:		14024	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4605MH0005360001700215S00	215	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4604	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4605		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4604MH0002240021700134C00	134	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1
4604MH0002240021700135C00	135	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
4604MH0002240021700136C00	136	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
4604MH0002240021700137C00	137	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4604MH0002240021700138C00	138	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4604MH0002240021700139C00	139	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4604MH0002240021700140C00	140	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
4604MH0002240021700141C00	141	14150	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_July_2025

SOL 4604 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Totoral - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4604MH0003590011700143C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4605MH0005360001700212R00	212	MOTOR COUNT:		13004	RANGE (cm):	27.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4605MH0005360001700213S00	213	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4604	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4605		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4604MH0003590021700144C00	144	12932	32.81	-2.7	3.1	122.4	10.2	255	1
4604MH0003590021700145C00	145	12950	31.26	-2.4	2.8	116.9	9.3	223	2
4604MH0003590021700146C00	146	12968	29.84	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	191	3
4604MH0003590021700147C00	147	12986	28.54	-2.0	2.3	107.4	7.7	159	4
4604MH0003590021700148C00	148	13004	27.34	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	127	5
4604MH0003590021700149C00	149	13022	26.22	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	95	6
4604MH0003590021700150C00	150	13040	25.19	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	63	7
4604MH0003590021700151C00	151	13058	24.22	-1.5	1.7	92.2	5.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_July_2025

SOL 4604 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Totoral - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4604MH0002240011700153C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4605MH0005360001700210R00	210	MOTOR COUNT:		13911	RANGE (cm):	7.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4605MH0005360001700211S00	211	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4604	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4605	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4604MH0002240021700154C00	154	13743	8.90	-0.3	0.2	38.2	0.8	255	1
4604MH0002240021700155C00	155	13785	8.50	-0.2	0.2	36.8	0.8	223	2
4604MH0002240021700156C00	156	13827	8.13	-0.2	0.2	35.5	0.7	191	3
4604MH0002240021700157C00	157	13869	7.79	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	159	4
4604MH0002240021700158C00	158	13911	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	127	5
4604MH0002240021700159C00	159	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	95	6
4604MH0002240021700160C00	160	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	63	7
4604MH0002240021700161C00	161	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_July_2025

SOL 4604 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Totoral - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4604MH0002240011700163C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4605MH0005360001700208R00	208	MOTOR COUNT:		13922	RANGE (cm):	7.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4605MH0005360001700209S00	209	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4604	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4605	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4604MH0002240021700164C00	164	13754	8.79	-0.2	0.2	37.8	0.8	255	1
4604MH0002240021700165C00	165	13796	8.40	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	223	2
4604MH0002240021700166C00	166	13838	8.04	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
4604MH0002240021700167C00	167	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	159	4
4604MH0002240021700168C00	168	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	127	5
4604MH0002240021700169C00	169	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	95	6
4604MH0002240021700170C00	170	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
4604MH0002240021700171C00	171	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_July_2025

SOL 4604 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sillar - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4604MH0003590011700173C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4605MH0005360001700206R00	206	MOTOR COUNT:		13006	RANGE (cm):	27.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4605MH0005360001700207S00	207	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4604	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4605		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4604MH0003590021700174C00	174	12934	32.63	-2.6	3.1	121.8	10.1	255	1
4604MH0003590021700175C00	175	12952	31.10	-2.4	2.8	116.4	9.2	223	2
4604MH0003590021700176C00	176	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	191	3
4604MH0003590021700177C00	177	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	159	4
4604MH0003590021700178C00	178	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	127	5
4604MH0003590021700179C00	179	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	95	6
4604MH0003590021700180C00	180	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	63	7
4604MH0003590021700181C00	181	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_July_2025

SOL 4604 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sillar - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4604MH0002240011700183C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4605MH0005360001700204R00	204	MOTOR COUNT:		13887	RANGE (cm):	7.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4605MH0005360001700205S00	205	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4604	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4605		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4604MH0002240021700184C00	184	13719	9.13	-0.3	0.3	39.1	0.9	255	1
4604MH0002240021700185C00	185	13761	8.72	-0.2	0.2	37.6	0.8	223	2
4604MH0002240021700186C00	186	13803	8.34	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	191	3
4604MH0002240021700187C00	187	13845	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	159	4
4604MH0002240021700188C00	188	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	127	5
4604MH0002240021700189C00	189	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	95	6
4604MH0002240021700190C00	190	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	63	7
4604MH0002240021700191C00	191	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 23_July_2025

SOL 4604 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sillar - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4604MH0002240011700193C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4605MH0005360001700202R00	202	MOTOR COUNT:		13914	RANGE (cm):		7.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4605MH0005360001700203S00	203	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4604		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4605
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4604MH0002240021700194C00	194	13746	8.87	-0.2	0.2	38.1	0.8	255	1
4604MH0002240021700195C00	195	13788	8.48	-0.2	0.2	36.7	0.8	223	2
4604MH0002240021700196C00	196	13830	8.11	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	191	3
4604MH0002240021700197C00	197	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	159	4
4604MH0002240021700198C00	198	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	127	5
4604MH0002240021700199C00	199	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	95	6
4604MH0002240021700200C00	200	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	63	7
4604MH0002240021700201C00	201	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_July_2025

SOL 4608 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Paposo - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4608MH0001730011700223C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4608MH0001710001700308R00	308	MOTOR COUNT:		14027	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4608MH0001710001700309S00	309	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4608	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4608		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4608MH0001730021700224C00	224	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
4608MH0001730021700225C00	225	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4608MH0001730021700226C00	226	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4608MH0001730021700227C00	227	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4608MH0001730021700228C00	228	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4608MH0001730021700229C00	229	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4608MH0001730021700230C00	230	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4608MH0001730021700231C00	231	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_July_2025

SOL 4608 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Paposo - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4608MH0001730011700233C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4608MH0001710001700306R00	306	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4608MH0001710001700307S00	307	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4608	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4608		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4608MH0001730021700234C00	234	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
4608MH0001730021700235C00	235	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
4608MH0001730021700236C00	236	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4608MH0001730021700237C00	237	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4608MH0001730021700238C00	238	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4608MH0001730021700239C00	239	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4608MH0001730021700240C00	240	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4608MH0001730021700241C00	241	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_July_2025

SOL 4608 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4608MH0003360011700245C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4608MH0001710001700304R00	304	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4608MH0001710001700305S00	305	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4608	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4608	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4608MH0003360021700246C00	246	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4608MH0003360021700247C00	247	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4608MH0003360021700248C00	248	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4608MH0003360021700249C00	249	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4608MH0003360021700250C00	250	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4608MH0003360021700251C00	251	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4608MH0003360021700252C00	252	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4608MH0003360021700253C00	253	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_July_2025

SOL 4608 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4608MH0003360011700255C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4608MH0001710001700302R00	302	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4608MH0001710001700303S00	303	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Jul-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4608	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4608	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4608MH0003360021700256C00	256	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4608MH0003360021700257C00	257	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4608MH0003360021700258C00	258	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4608MH0003360021700259C00	259	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4608MH0003360021700260C00	260	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4608MH0003360021700261C00	261	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4608MH0003360021700262C00	262	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4608MH0003360021700263C00	263	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 31_July_2025

SOL 4608 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Tranquita - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4608MH0001680011700267C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4608MH0001710001700300R00		300		MOTOR COUNT:		13986		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4608MH0001710001700301S00		301		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		23-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4608		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4608	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4608MH0001680021700268C00	268	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1		
4608MH0001680021700269C00	269	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2		
4608MH0001680021700270C00	270	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3		
4608MH0001680021700271C00	271	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4		
4608MH0001680021700272C00	272	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5		
4608MH0001680021700273C00	273	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6		
4608MH0001680021700274C00	274	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7		
4608MH0001680021700275C00	275	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 31_July_2025

SOL 4608 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Tranquita - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4608MH0001680011700277C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4608MH0001710001700298R00		298		MOTOR COUNT:		13988		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4608MH0001710001700299S00		299		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		23-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4608		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4608	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4608MH0001680021700278C00	278	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1		
4608MH0001680021700279C00	279	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2		
4608MH0001680021700280C00	280	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3		
4608MH0001680021700281C00	281	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4		
4608MH0001680021700282C00	282	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5		
4608MH0001680021700283C00	283	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6		
4608MH0001680021700284C00	284	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7		
4608MH0001680021700285C00	285	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4608 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Tranquita – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4608MH0007430011700287C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4608MH0001710001700296R00	296	MOTOR COUNT:		14905	RANGE (cm):		3.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4608MH0001710001700297S00	297	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4608	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4608	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4608MH0007430021700288C00	288	14761	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	255	1
4608MH0007430021700289C00	289	14797	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	223	2
4608MH0007430021700290C00	290	14833	3.43	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	191	3
4608MH0007430021700291C00	291	14869	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	159	4
4608MH0007430021700292C00	292	14905	3.25	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	127	5
4608MH0007430021700293C00	293	14941	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	95	6
4608MH0007430021700294C00	294	14977	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	63	7
4608MH0007430021700295C00	295	15013	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4611 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tipnis - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4611MH0001730011700313C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4612MH0002270001700372R00		372		MOTOR COUNT:		14272		RANGE (cm): 5.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4612MH0002270001700373S00		373		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		27-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4611		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4612	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4611MH0001730021700314C00	314	14152	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	255	1		
4611MH0001730021700315C00	315	14182	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	223	2		
4611MH0001730021700316C00	316	14212	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	191	3		
4611MH0001730021700317C00	317	14242	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	159	4		
4611MH0001730021700318C00	318	14272	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	127	5		
4611MH0001730021700319C00	319	14302	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	95	6		
4611MH0001730021700320C00	320	14332	5.08	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	63	7		
4611MH0001730021700321C00	321	14362	4.95	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	31	8		

UPDATED: 31_July_2025

SOL 4611 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tipnis - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4611MH0001730011700323C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4612MH0002270001700370R00		370		MOTOR COUNT:		14259		RANGE (cm): 5.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4612MH0002270001700371S00		371		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		27-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4611		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4612	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4611MH0001730021700324C00	324	14139	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	255	1		
4611MH0001730021700325C00	325	14169	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	223	2		
4611MH0001730021700326C00	326	14199	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	191	3		
4611MH0001730021700327C00	327	14229	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	159	4		
4611MH0001730021700328C00	328	14259	5.41	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	127	5		
4611MH0001730021700329C00	329	14289	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	95	6		
4611MH0001730021700330C00	330	14319	5.13	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7		
4611MH0001730021700331C00	331	14349	5.01	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	31	8		

UPDATED: 31_July_2025

SOL 4611 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Yura_Tuff - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4611MH0001680011700335C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4612MH0002270001700368R00		368		MOTOR COUNT:		14013		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4612MH0002270001700369S00		369		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		27-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4611		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4612	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4611MH0001680021700336C00	336	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1		
4611MH0001680021700337C00	337	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2		
4611MH0001680021700338C00	338	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3		
4611MH0001680021700339C00	339	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4		
4611MH0001680021700340C00	340	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5		
4611MH0001680021700341C00	341	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6		
4611MH0001680021700342C00	342	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7		
4611MH0001680021700343C00	343	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4611 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Yura_Tuff - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4611MH0001680011700345C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4612MH0002270001700366R00		366		MOTOR COUNT:		14022		RANGE (cm): 6.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4612MH0002270001700367S00		367		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		27-Jul-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4611		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4612	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4611MH0001680021700346C00	346	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1		
4611MH0001680021700347C00	347	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2		
4611MH0001680021700348C00	348	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3		
4611MH0001680021700349C00	349	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4		
4611MH0001680021700350C00	350	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5		
4611MH0001680021700351C00	351	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6		
4611MH0001680021700352C00	352	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7		
4611MH0001680021700353C00	353	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 31_July_2025

SOL 4611 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Yura_Tuff – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4611MH0007430011700355C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4612MH0002270001700364R00	364	MOTOR COUNT:		14912	RANGE (cm):		3.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4612MH0002270001700365S00	365	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jul-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4611	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4612	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4611MH0007430021700356C00	356	14768	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	255	1
4611MH0007430021700357C00	357	14804	3.50	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	223	2
4611MH0007430021700358C00	358	14840	3.41	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	191	3
4611MH0007430021700359C00	359	14876	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	159	4
4611MH0007430021700360C00	360	14912	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	127	5
4611MH0007430021700361C00	361	14948	3.15	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	95	6
4611MH0007430021700362C00	362	14984	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	63	7
4611MH0007430021700363C00	363	15020	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI Team drafts each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 4489–4612. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 4489, 4498, 4500, 4505, 4509, 4510, 4511, 4512, 4513, 4514, 4518, 4522, 4523, 4525, 4526, 4527, 4529, 4530, 4532, 4534, 4536, 4537, 4539, 4543, 4544, 4546, 4547, 4548, 4550, 4552, 4553, 4554, 4559, 4560, 4561, 4568, 4569, 4570, 4571, 4573, 4575, 4577, 4578, 4580, 4584, 4585, 4586, 4587, 4588, 4590, 4591, 4593, 4594, 4595, 4596, 4597, 4598, 4600, 4602, 4604, 4605, 4608, 4611, 4612.**

updated: 24_March_2025

Sol 4489 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-Mar-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	14

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4488 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002171	Focus Merges	4489MH00017J0001602611900	2611	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2603-2610 - best focus image product
		4489MH00017J0001602612500	2612	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2603-2610 - range map product
		4489MH00017J0001602612900	2613	target Black_Oak - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2593-2600 - best focus image product
		4489MH00017J0001602614500	2614	target Black_Oak - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2593-2600 - range map product
		4489MH00017J0001602615900	2615	target Black_Oak - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2583-2590 - best focus image product
		4489MH00017J0001602616500	2616	target Black_Oak - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2583-2590 - range map product
		4489MH00017J0001602617900	2617	target Solstice_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2573-2580 - best focus image product
		4489MH00017J0001602618500	2618	target Solstice_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2573-2580 - range map product
		4489MH00017J0001602619900	2619	target Solstice_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2563-2570 - best focus image product
		4489MH00017J0001602620500	2620	target Solstice_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2563-2570 - range map product
		4489MH00017J0001602621900	2621	target Solstice_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2553-2560 - best focus image product
		4489MH00017J0001602622500	2622	target Solstice_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2553-2560 - range map product
		4489MH00017J0001602623900	2623	target Solstice_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2543-2550 - best focus image product
		4489MH00017J0001602624500	2624	target Solstice_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4488 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2543-2550 - range map product

Sol 4498 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0 Apr 25
camera position	6
total parent images	63
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	74

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target **Los_Ocos** and the target **Black_Star_Canyon**. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Los_Ocos after DRT ~25 cm standoff	498MH0019000116026250D	2625	autofocus sub-frame for target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		498MH0019000116026260D	2626	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Los_Ocos after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	498MH0033600116026270D	2627	autofocus sub-frame for target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		498MH0033600116026280D	2628	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		498MH0033600116026290D	2629	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026300D	2630	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026310D	2631	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026320D	2632	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026330D	2633	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026340D	2634	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026350D	2635	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026360D	2636	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Los_Ocos after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	498MH0033600116026370D	2637	autofocus sub-frame for target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		498MH0033600116026380D	2638	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		498MH0033600116026390D	2639	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026400D	2640	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026410D	2641	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026420D	2642	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026430D	2643	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026440D	2644	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026450D	2645	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0033600116026460D	2646	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00848	Los_Ocos after DRT ~15 mm standoff	498MH0084800116026470D	2647	autofocus sub-frame for target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		498MH0084800116026480D	2648	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		498MH0084800116026490D	2649	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0084800116026500D	2650	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0084800116026510D	2651	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0084800116026520D	2652	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0084800116026530D	2653	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0084800116026540D	2654	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0084800116026550D	2655	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0084800116026560D	2656	target Los_Ocos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00359	Black_Star_Canyon ~24 cm standoff	498MH0035900116026570D	2657	autofocus sub-frame for target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		498MH0035900116026580D	2658	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		498MH0035900116026590D	2659	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035900116026600D	2660	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035900116026610D	2661	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035900116026620D	2662	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035900116026630D	2663	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035900116026640D	2664	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035900116026650D	2665	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035900116026660D	2666	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00356	Black_Star_Canyon stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	498MH0035600116026670D	2667	autofocus sub-frame for target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		498MH0035600116026680D	2668	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		498MH0035600116026690D	2669	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026700D	2670	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026710D	2671	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026720D	2672	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026730D	2673	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026740D	2674	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026750D	2675	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026760D	2676	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00356	Black_Star_Canyon stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	498MH0035600116026770D	2677	autofocus sub-frame for target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		498MH0035600116026780D	2678	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		498MH0035600116026790D	2679	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026800D	2680	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026810D	2681	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026820D	2682	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026830D	2683	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026840D	2684	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026850D	2685	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		498MH0035600116026860D	2686	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mnh00163	Focus Merge	4498MH0016300160268700	2687	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2679-2686 - best focus image product
		4498MH00163001602688500	2688	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2679-2686 - range map product
		4498MH0016300160268900	2689	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2669-2676 - best focus image product
		4498MH00163001602690500	2690	target Black_Star_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2669-2676 - range map product
		4498MH00163001602691000	2691	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2659-2666 - best focus image product
		4498MH00163001602692500	2692	target Black_Star_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2659-2666 - range map product
		4498MH00163001602693000	2693	target Los_Oesa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2649-2656 - best focus image product
		4498MH00163001602694500	2694	target Los_Oesa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2649-2656 - range map product
		4498MH00163001602695000	2695	target Los_Oesa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2639-2646 - best focus image product
		4498MH00163001602696500	2696	target Los_Oesa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2639-2646 - range map product
		4498MH00163001602697000	2697	target Los_Oesa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2629-2636 - best focus image product
		4498MH00163001602698500	2698	target Los_Oesa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4498 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2629-2636 - range map product

updated: 24_October_2025

Sol 4500 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	8-Apr-25
camera position:	6
total parent images:	41
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	47

MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets as well the DRT-brushed target Chuckwalla. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	4500MH000372001602899000	2699	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		4500MH000372001602700000	2700	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
mNI00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	4500MH000372001602701000	2701	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		4500MH000372001602702000	2702	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
mNI00374	MAHLI cal target = wheel + surface 30 cm working distance from target	4500MH000374001602703000	2703	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4500MH000374001602704000	2704	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4500MH000374001602705000	2705	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
mNI00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	4500MH000373001602706000	2706	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		4500MH000373001602707000	2707	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00390	Chuckwalla after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4500MH000360001602708000	2708	autofocus sub-frame for target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4500MH000360001602709000	2709	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mNI00396	Chuckwalla after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4500MH000360001602710000	2710	autofocus sub-frame for target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4500MH000360001602711000	2711	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4500MH000360001602712000	2712	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602713000	2713	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602714000	2714	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602715000	2715	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602716000	2716	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602717000	2717	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602718000	2718	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602719000	2719	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00396	Chuckwalla after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4500MH000360001602720000	2720	autofocus sub-frame for target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4500MH000360001602721000	2721	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4500MH000360001602722000	2722	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602723000	2723	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602724000	2724	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602725000	2725	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602726000	2726	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602727000	2727	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602728000	2728	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000360001602729000	2729	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00408	Chuckwalla after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4500MH000848001602730000	2730	autofocus sub-frame for target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4500MH000848001602731000	2731	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4500MH000848001602732000	2732	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000848001602733000	2733	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000848001602734000	2734	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000848001602735000	2735	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000848001602736000	2736	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000848001602737000	2737	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000848001602738000	2738	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4500MH000848001602739000	2739	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00393	Focus Merges	4500MH000193001602740000	2740	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4500 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2732-2739 - best focus image product
		4500MH000193001602741000	2741	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4500 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2732-2739 - range map product
		4500MH000193001602742000	2742	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4500 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2722-2729 - best focus image product
		4500MH000193001602743000	2743	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4500 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2722-2729 - range map product
		4500MH000193001602744000	2744	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4500 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2712-2719 - best focus image product
		4500MH000193001602745000	2745	target Chuckwalla - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4500 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2712-2719 - range map product

updated: 24_October_2025

Sol 4505 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8 Apr 25
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Coronado and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Coronado after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4505MH001900001602746C00	2746	autoFocus sub-frame for target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4505MH001900011602747C00	2747	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Coronado after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4505MH001680001602748C00	2748	autoFocus sub-frame for target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4505MH001680011602749C00	2749	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4505MH001680021602750C00	2750	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680031602751C00	2751	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680041602752C00	2752	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680051602753C00	2753	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680061602754C00	2754	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680071602755C00	2755	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680081602756C00	2756	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680091602757C00	2757	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Coronado after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4505MH001680001602758C00	2758	autoFocus sub-frame for target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4505MH001680011602759C00	2759	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4505MH001680021602760C00	2760	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680031602761C00	2761	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680041602762C00	2762	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680051602763C00	2763	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680061602764C00	2764	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680071602765C00	2765	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680081602766C00	2766	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH001680091602767C00	2767	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00848	Coronado after DRT ~15 mm standoff	4505MH008480001602768C00	2768	autoFocus sub-frame for target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4505MH008480011602769C00	2769	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4505MH008480021602770C00	2770	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH008480031602771C00	2771	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH008480041602772C00	2772	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH008480051602773C00	2773	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH008480061602774C00	2774	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH008480071602775C00	2775	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH008480081602776C00	2776	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4505MH008480091602777C00	2777	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	4505MH001930001602778C00	2778	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4505 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2770-2777 - best focus image product
		4505MH001930001602779C00	2779	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4505 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2770-2777 - range map product
		4505MH001930001602780C00	2780	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4505 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2760-2767 - best focus image product
		4505MH001930001602781C00	2781	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4505 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2760-2767 - range map product
		4505MH001930001602782C00	2782	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4505 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2750-2757 - best focus image product
		4505MH001930001602783C00	2783	target Coronado - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4505 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2750-2757 - range map product

updated: 14_April_2025

Sol 4510 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		16_Apr_25		
camera position:	0	Image ID:		
total parent images:	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed:	2	CDPID:		
total focus merge products:	4	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products:	4			
summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4509 were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100025	Focus Merges	4510MH002650001602852900	2852	target Iron_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4509 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2842-2849 - best focus image product
		4510MH002650001602853500	2853	target Iron_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4509 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2842-2849 - range map product
		4510MH002650001602854900	2854	target Iron_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI stereo optimization test - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - center position - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4509 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2788-2795 - best focus image product
		4510MH002650001602855500	2855	target Iron_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - MAHLI stereo optimization test - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - center position - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4509 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2788-2795 - range map product

updated: 15_April_2025

Sol 4511 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15-Apr-25
camera position	2
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the target Torrey_Pines and the DRT-brushed target The_Grotto.		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Torrey_Pines ~25 cm standoff	4511MH00290001602856C00	2856	autofocus sub-frame for target Torrey_Pines - standoff near 25 cm
		4511MH00290001602857C00	2857	target Torrey_Pines - standoff near 25 cm
mN00299	Torrey_Pines stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4511MH00299001602858C00	2858	autofocus sub-frame for target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4511MH00299001602859C00	2859	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4511MH00299001602860C00	2860	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602861C00	2861	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602862C00	2862	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602863C00	2863	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602864C00	2864	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602865C00	2865	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602866C00	2866	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602867C00	2867	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Torrey_Pines stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4511MH00299001602868C00	2868	autofocus sub-frame for target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4511MH00299001602869C00	2869	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4511MH00299001602870C00	2870	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602871C00	2871	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602872C00	2872	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602873C00	2873	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602874C00	2874	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602875C00	2875	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602876C00	2876	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00299001602877C00	2877	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00290	The_Grotto after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4511MH00190001602878C00	2878	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4511MH00190001602879C00	2879	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	The_Grotto after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4511MH00168001602880C00	2880	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4511MH00168001602881C00	2881	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4511MH00168001602882C00	2882	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602883C00	2883	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602884C00	2884	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602885C00	2885	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602886C00	2886	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602887C00	2887	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602888C00	2888	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602889C00	2889	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	The_Grotto after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4511MH00168001602890C00	2890	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4511MH00168001602891C00	2891	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4511MH00168001602892C00	2892	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602893C00	2893	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602894C00	2894	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602895C00	2895	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602896C00	2896	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602897C00	2897	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602898C00	2898	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00168001602899C00	2899	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	The_Grotto after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4511MH00743001602900C00	2900	autofocus sub-frame for target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4511MH00743001602901C00	2901	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4511MH00743001602902C00	2902	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00743001602903C00	2903	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00743001602904C00	2904	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00743001602905C00	2905	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00743001602906C00	2906	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00743001602907C00	2907	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00743001602908C00	2908	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4511MH00743001602909C00	2909	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 16_April_2025

Sol 4512 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-Apr-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4511 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4512MH0002270001602910R00	2910	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2902-2909 - best focus image product
		4512MH0002270001602911S00	2911	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2902-2909 - range map product
		4512MH0002270001602912R00	2912	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2892-2899 - best focus image product
		4512MH0002270001602913S00	2913	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2892-2899 - range map product
		4512MH0002270001602914R00	2914	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2882-2889 - best focus image product
		4512MH0002270001602915S00	2915	target The_Grotto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2882-2889 - range map product
		4512MH0002270001602916R00	2916	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2870-2877 - best focus image product
		4512MH0002270001602917S00	2917	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2870-2877 - range map product
		4512MH0002270001602918R00	2918	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2860-2867 - best focus image product
		4512MH0002270001602919S00	2919	target Torrey_Pines - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4511 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2860-2867 - range map product

updated: 18_April_2025

Sol 4514 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Apr-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	13

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4513 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4514MH000163000160298200	2982	target Ia_Purissima - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2974-2981 - best focus image product
		4514MH000163000160298350	2983	target Ia_Purissima - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2974-2981 - range map product
		4514MH000163000160298400	2984	target Ia_Purissima - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2964-2971 - best focus image product
		4514MH000163000160298550	2985	target Ia_Purissima - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2964-2971 - range map product
		4514MH000163000160298600	2986	target Ia_Purissima - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2964-2961 - best focus image product
		4514MH000163000160298750	2987	target Ia_Purissima - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2964-2961 - range map product
		4514MH000163000160298800	2988	target Elephant_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2942-2949 - best focus image product
		4514MH000163000160298950	2989	target Elephant_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2942-2949 - range map product
		4514MH000163000160299000	2990	target Elephant_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2932-2939 - best focus image product
		4514MH000163000160299150	2991	target Elephant_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2932-2939 - range map product
		4514MH000163000160299200	2992	target Elephant_Tree - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2922-2929 - best focus image product
		4514MH000163000160299350	2993	target Elephant_Tree - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4513 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2922-2929 - range map product

updated: 22_April_2025

Sol 4518 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Apr-25	Image ID:	
camera position:	25	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	25	CDPID:	
focus merges performed:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total focus merge products:	0		
total parent images + focus merge products:	25		

MAHLI imaged 2367 of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4518MH007690011602994E01	2994	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4518MH007700011602995E01	2995	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4518MH007710011602996E01	2996	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4518MH007720011602997E01	2997	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4518MH007690011602998E01	2998	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4518MH007700011602999E01	2999	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4518MH007710011603000E01	3000	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4518MH007720011603001E01	3001	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4518MH007690011603002E01	3002	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4518MH007700011603003E01	3003	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4518MH007710011603004E01	3004	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4518MH007720011603005E01	3005	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4518MH007690011603006E01	3006	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4518MH007700011603007E01	3007	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4518MH007710011603008E01	3008	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4518MH007720011603009E01	3009	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4518MH007690011603010E01	3010	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4518MH007700011603011E01	3011	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4518MH007710011603012E01	3012	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4518MH007720011603013E01	3013	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4518 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm

updated: 30_April_2025

Sol 4522 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Apr-25
camera position	2
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

Image ID:
black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the target Hale_Telescope and the target Cerro_Alto, which includes a 3x3 mosaic.		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000190	Hale_Telescope ~25 cm standoff	4522MH0001900001.1603014C00	3014	autofocus sub-frame for target Hale_Telescope - standoff near 25 cm
		4522MH000190001.1603015C00	3015	target Hale_Telescope - standoff near 25 cm
mN000336	Hale_Telescope stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4522MH0003360001.1603016C00	3016	autofocus sub-frame for target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4522MH000336001.1603017C00	3017	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4522MH000336002.1603018C00	3018	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603019C00	3019	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603020C00	3020	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603021C00	3021	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603022C00	3022	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603023C00	3023	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603024C00	3024	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603025C00	3025	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000336	Hale_Telescope stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4522MH0003360001.1603026C00	3026	autofocus sub-frame for target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4522MH000336001.1603027C00	3027	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4522MH000336002.1603028C00	3028	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603029C00	3029	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603030C00	3030	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603031C00	3031	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603032C00	3032	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603033C00	3033	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603034C00	3034	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603035C00	3035	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000190	Cerro_Alto ~24 cm standoff	4522MH0001900001.1603036C00	3036	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Alto - standoff near 24 cm
		4522MH000190001.1603037C00	3037	target Cerro_Alto - standoff near 24 cm
mN000336	Cerro_Alto mosaic position 1 of 3 ~45 mm standoff	4522MH0003360001.1603038C00	3038	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm
		4522MH000336001.1603039C00	3039	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm
		4522MH000336002.1603040C00	3040	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603041C00	3041	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603042C00	3042	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603043C00	3043	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603044C00	3044	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603045C00	3045	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603046C00	3046	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603047C00	3047	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000336	Cerro_Alto mosaic position 2 of 3 ~35 mm standoff	4522MH0003360001.1603048C00	3048	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm
		4522MH000336001.1603049C00	3049	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm
		4522MH000336002.1603050C00	3050	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603051C00	3051	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603052C00	3052	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603053C00	3053	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603054C00	3054	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603055C00	3055	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603056C00	3056	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603057C00	3057	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000336	Cerro_Alto mosaic position 3 of 3 ~4 cm standoff	4522MH0003360001.1603058C00	3058	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		4522MH000336001.1603059C00	3059	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		4522MH000336002.1603060C00	3060	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603061C00	3061	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603062C00	3062	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603063C00	3063	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603064C00	3064	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603065C00	3065	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603066C00	3066	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4522MH000336002.1603067C00	3067	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 28_April_2025

Sol 4523 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27_Apr_25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities		Focus stack images from Sol 4522 were merged.		Focus stack images from Sol 4522 were merged.	
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN00227	Focus Merges	4523MH000227000160306800	3068	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3060-3067 - best focus image product	
		4523MH000227000160306950	3069	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3060-3067 - range map product	
		4523MH000227000160307000	3070	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3050-3057 - best focus image product	
		4523MH000227000160307150	3071	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3050-3057 - range map product	
		4523MH000227000160307200	3072	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3040-3047 - best focus image product	
		4523MH000227000160307350	3073	target Cerro_Alto - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3040-3047 - range map product	
		4523MH000227000160307400	3074	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3028-3035 - best focus image product	
		4523MH000227000160307500	3075	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3028-3035 - range map product	
		4523MH000227000160307600	3076	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3018-3025 - best focus image product	
		4523MH000227000160307750	3077	target Hale_Telescope - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4522 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3018-3025 - range map product	

updated: 02_May_2025

Sol 4526 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20-Apr-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4525 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4526MH001630001603142900	3142	target Sweetwater_River - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3134-3141 - best focus image product
		4526MH001630001603143500	3143	target Sweetwater_River - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3134-3141 - range map product
		4526MH001630001603144900	3144	target Sweetwater_River - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-0 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3124-3131 - best focus image product
		4526MH001630001603145500	3145	target Sweetwater_River - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3124-3131 - range map product
		4526MH001630001603146900	3146	target Sweetwater_River - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3114-3121 - best focus image product
		4526MH001630001603147500	3147	target Sweetwater_River - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3114-3121 - range map product
		4526MH001630001603148900	3148	target Bradshaw_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3102-3109 - best focus image product
		4526MH001630001603149500	3149	target Bradshaw_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3102-3109 - range map product
		4526MH001630001603150900	3150	target Bradshaw_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3092-3099 - best focus image product
		4526MH001630001603151500	3151	target Bradshaw_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3092-3099 - range map product
		4526MH001630001603152900	3152	target Bradshaw_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3082-3089 - best focus image product
		4526MH001630001603153500	3153	target Bradshaw_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4525 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3082-3089 - range map product

updated: 05_May_2025

Sol 4527 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	1-May-25
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Tamarak_Valley and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose [RATIONAL, DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit]
mN002190	Tamarak_Valley after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4527MH000190001160315400D	3154	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4527MH000190001160315500D	3155	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN002168	Tamarak_Valley after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4527MH0001680001160315600D	3156	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4527MH0001680001160315700D	3157	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4527MH0001680001160315800D	3158	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160315900D	3159	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160316000D	3160	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160316100D	3161	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160316200D	3162	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160316300D	3163	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160316400D	3164	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160316500D	3165	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Tamarak_Valley after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4527MH0001680001160316600D	3166	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4527MH0001680001160316700D	3167	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4527MH0001680001160316800D	3168	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160316900D	3169	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160317000D	3170	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160317100D	3171	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160317200D	3172	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160317300D	3173	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160317400D	3174	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001680001160317500D	3175	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Tamarak_Valley after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4527MH0007430001160317600D	3176	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4527MH0007430001160317700D	3177	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4527MH0007430001160317800D	3178	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0007430001160317900D	3179	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0007430001160318000D	3180	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0007430001160318100D	3181	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0007430001160318200D	3182	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0007430001160318300D	3183	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4527MH0001930001160318400D	3184	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0007430001160318500D	3185	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4527MH0001930001160318600D	3186	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4527 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3178-3183 - best focus image product
		4527MH00019300011603187500D	3187	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4527 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3178-3183 - range map product
		4527MH0001930001160318800D	3188	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4527 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3168-3175 - best focus image product
		4527MH00019300011603189500D	3189	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4527 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3168-3175 - range map product
mN002193	Focus Merges	4527MH0001930001160319000D	3190	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4527 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3158-3165 - best focus image product
		4527MH00019300011603191500D	3191	target Tamarak_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4527 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3158-3165 - range map product

mH00363	Orosco_Ridge stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4529MH00036300160332C00	3322	autofocus sub-frame for target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4529MH000363001603323C00	3323	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4529MH000363001603324C00	3324	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4529MH000363001603325C00	3325	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4529MH000363001603326C00	3326	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4529MH000363001603327C00	3327	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4529MH000363001603328C00	3328	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4529MH000363001603329C00	3329	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4529MH000363001603330C00	3330	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4529MH000363001603331C00	3331	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 05_May_2025

Sol 4530 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	4-May-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed	14
total focus merge products	28
total parent images + focus merge products	28
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4529 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000728	Focus Merges	4530MH00728000160332900	3332	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3324-3331 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160333500	3333	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3324-3331 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160334400	3334	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3314-3321 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160335500	3335	target Orosco_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3314-3321 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160336800	3336	target Orosco_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3304-3311 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160337500	3337	target Orosco_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3304-3311 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160338800	3338	target Box_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3294-3301 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160339500	3339	target Box_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3294-3301 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160340800	3340	target Box_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3284-3291 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160341500	3341	target Box_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3284-3291 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160342800	3342	target Box_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3274-3281 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160343500	3343	target Box_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3274-3281 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160344800	3344	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 8 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3264-3271 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160345500	3345	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 8 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3264-3271 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160346800	3346	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 7 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3254-3261 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160347500	3347	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 7 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3254-3261 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160348800	3348	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3244-3251 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160349500	3349	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3244-3251 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160350800	3350	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3234-3241 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160351500	3351	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3234-3241 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160352800	3352	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3224-3231 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160353500	3353	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3224-3231 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160354800	3354	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3214-3221 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160355500	3355	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3214-3221 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160356800	3356	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3204-3211 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160357500	3357	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3204-3211 - range map product
		4530MH00728000160358800	3358	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3194-3201 - best focus image product
		4530MH00728000160359500	3359	target Valley_of_The_Moon - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff between 12 cm and 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4529 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3194-3201 - range map product

Sol 4532 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8-May-25
camera position	7
total parent images	63
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	74

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Encinitas and the target Jack_Creek. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Encinitas after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4532MH00190001603960C0	3360	autofocus sub-frame for target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4532MH00190001603961C0	3361	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4532MH001680001603962C0	3362	autofocus sub-frame for target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00168	Encinitas after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4532MH001680001603963C0	3363	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4532MH001680001603964C0	3364	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH001680001603965C0	3365	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH001680001603966C0	3366	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH001680001603967C0	3367	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH001680001603968C0	3368	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH001680001603969C0	3369	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH001680001603970C0	3370	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH001680001603971C0	3371	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00168	Encinitas after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4532MH001680001603972C0
4532MH001680001603973C0	3373			target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
4532MH001680001603974C0	3374			target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4532MH001680001603975C0	3375			target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4532MH001680001603976C0	3376			target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
4532MH001680001603977C0	3377			target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
4532MH001680001603978C0	3378			target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
4532MH001680001603979C0	3379			target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4532MH001680001603980C0	3380			target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4532MH001680001603981C0	3381			target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Encinitas after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4532MH000864001603982C0	3382	autofocus sub-frame for target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4532MH000864001603983C0	3383	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4532MH000864001603984C0	3384	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000864001603985C0	3385	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000864001603986C0	3386	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000864001603987C0	3387	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000864001603988C0	3388	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000864001603989C0	3389	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000864001603990C0	3390	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000864001603991C0	3391	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00359	Jack_Creek ~24 cm standoff	4532MH000359001603992C0	3392	autofocus sub-frame for target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
		4532MH000359001603993C0	3393	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
		4532MH000359001603994C0	3394	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000359001603995C0	3395	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000359001603996C0	3396	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000359001603997C0	3397	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000359001603998C0	3398	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000359001603999C0	3399	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000359001603400C0	3400	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000359001603401C0	3401	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Jack_Creek stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4532MH000152001603402C0	3402	autofocus sub-frame for target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4532MH000152001603403C0	3403	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4532MH000152001603404C0	3404	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603405C0	3405	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603406C0	3406	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603407C0	3407	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603408C0	3408	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603409C0	3409	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603410C0	3410	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603411C0	3411	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Jack_Creek stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4532MH000152001603412C0	3412	autofocus sub-frame for target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4532MH000152001603413C0	3413	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4532MH000152001603414C0	3414	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603415C0	3415	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603416C0	3416	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603417C0	3417	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603418C0	3418	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603419C0	3419	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603420C0	3420	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4532MH000152001603421C0	3421	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

mnh00163	Focus Merge	4512MH0016300160342800	3422	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3414-3421 - best focus image product
		4512MH0016300160342900	3423	target Jack_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3414-3421 - range map product
		4512MH0016300160342900	3424	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3404-3411 - best focus image product
		4512MH0016300160342900	3425	target Jack_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3404-3411 - range map product
		4512MH0016300160342900	3426	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3394-3401 - best focus image product
		4512MH0016300160342900	3427	target Jack_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3394-3401 - range map product
		4512MH0016300160342900	3428	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3384-3391 - best focus image product
		4512MH0016300160342900	3429	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3384-3391 - range map product
		4512MH0016300160343000	3430	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3374-3381 - best focus image product
		4512MH0016300160343100	3431	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3374-3381 - range map product
		4512MH0016300160343200	3432	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3364-3371 - best focus image product
		4512MH0016300160343300	3433	target Encinitas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3364-3371 - range map product

updated: 12_May_2025

Sol 4534 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8-May-25
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Chumash and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN002190	Chumash after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4534MH001900011603434C00	3434	autoFocus sub-frame for target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm		
		4534MH001900011603435C00	3435	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm		
mN002168	Chumash after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4534MH001680021603436C00	3436	autoFocus sub-frame for target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4534MH001680021603437C00	3437	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4534MH001680021603438C00	3438	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH001680021603439C00	3439	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH001680021603440C00	3440	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH001680021603441C00	3441	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH001680021603442C00	3442	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH001680021603443C00	3443	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH001680021603444C00	3444	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH001680021603445C00	3445	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN002168	Chumash after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4534MH001680021603446C00	3446	autoFocus sub-frame for target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4534MH001680021603447C00	3447	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
4534MH001680021603448C00	3448			target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4534MH001680021603449C00	3449			target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4534MH001680021603450C00	3450			target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4534MH001680021603451C00	3451			target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4534MH001680021603452C00	3452			target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4534MH001680021603453C00	3453			target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4534MH001680021603454C00	3454			target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4534MH001680021603455C00	3455			target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00864	Chumash after DRT ~5 mm standoff			4534MH008640021603456C00	3456	autoFocus sub-frame for target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
				4534MH008640021603457C00	3457	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4534MH008640021603458C00	3458	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH008640021603459C00	3459	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH008640021603460C00	3460	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH008640021603461C00	3461	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH008640021603462C00	3462	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH008640021603463C00	3463	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH008640021603464C00	3464	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4534MH008640021603465C00	3465	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN002193	Focus Merges	4534MH001930011603466R00	3466	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4534 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3458-3465 - best focus image product		
		4534MH001930011603467S00	3467	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4534 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3458-3465 - range map product		
		4534MH001930011603468R00	3468	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4534 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3448-3455 - best focus image product		
		4534MH001930011603469S00	3469	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4534 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3448-3455 - range map product		
		4534MH001930011603470R00	3470	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4534 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3438-3445 - best focus image product		
		4534MH001930011603471S00	3471	target Chumash - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4534 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3438-3445 - range map product		

updated: 12_May_2025

Sol 4536 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-May-25
camera position	7
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities				MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Crescenta_Valley and the target Rockhouse_Canyon.
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Crescenta_Valley after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4536MH00190001603472C00	3472	autofocus sub-frame for target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4536MH00190001603473C00	3473	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Crescenta_Valley after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4536MH00168001603474C00	3474	autofocus sub-frame for target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4536MH00168001603475C00	3475	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4536MH00168001603476C00	3476	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603477C00	3477	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603478C00	3478	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603479C00	3479	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603480C00	3480	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603481C00	3481	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603482C00	3482	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603483C00	3483	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Crescenta_Valley after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4536MH00168001603484C00	3484	autofocus sub-frame for target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4536MH00168001603485C00	3485	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4536MH00168001603486C00	3486	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603487C00	3487	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603488C00	3488	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603489C00	3489	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603490C00	3490	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603491C00	3491	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603492C00	3492	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603493C00	3493	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Crescenta_Valley after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4536MH00743001603494C00	3494	autofocus sub-frame for target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4536MH00743001603495C00	3495	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4536MH00743001603496C00	3496	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00743001603497C00	3497	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00743001603498C00	3498	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00743001603499C00	3499	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00743001603500C00	3500	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00743001603501C00	3501	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00743001603502C00	3502	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00743001603503C00	3503	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Rockhouse_Canyon ~24 cm standoff	4536MH00190001603504C00	3504	autofocus sub-frame for target Rockhouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		4536MH00190001603505C00	3505	target Rockhouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Rockhouse_Canyon stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4536MH00168001603506C00	3506	autofocus sub-frame for target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4536MH00168001603507C00	3507	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4536MH00168001603508C00	3508	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603509C00	3509	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603510C00	3510	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603511C00	3511	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603512C00	3512	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603513C00	3513	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603514C00	3514	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603515C00	3515	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Rockhouse_Canyon stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4536MH00168001603516C00	3516	autofocus sub-frame for target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4536MH00168001603517C00	3517	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4536MH00168001603518C00	3518	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603519C00	3519	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603520C00	3520	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603521C00	3521	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603522C00	3522	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603523C00	3523	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603524C00	3524	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4536MH00168001603525C00	3525	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 12_May_2025

Sol 4537 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	11-May-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4536 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4537MH0002270001603526800	3526	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3518-3525 - best focus image product
		4537MH0002270001603527500	3527	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3518-3525 - range map product
		4537MH0002270001603528800	3528	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3508-3515 - best focus image product
		4537MH0002270001603529500	3529	target Rockhouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3508-3515 - range map product
		4537MH0002270001603530800	3530	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3496-3503 - best focus image product
		4537MH0002270001603531500	3531	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3496-3503 - range map product
		4537MH0002270001603532800	3532	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3486-3493 - best focus image product
		4537MH0002270001603533500	3533	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3486-3493 - range map product
		4537MH0002270001603534800	3534	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3476-3483 - best focus image product
		4537MH0002270001603535500	3535	target Crescenta_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4536 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3476-3483 - range map product

updated: 14_May_2025

Sol 4539 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	13-May-25
camera positions	6
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	31

MAHLI imaged the targets Canyon_Oak and Jeffrey_Pine. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Canyon_Oak Stereo-1 ~24 cm standoff	4539MH001900011603536C0D	3536	autoFocus sub-frame for target Canyon_Oak - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm
		4539MH001900011603537C0D	3537	target Canyon_Oak - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00290	Canyon_Oak Stereo-2 ~24 cm standoff	4539MH001900011603538C0D	3538	autoFocus sub-frame for target Canyon_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4539MH001900011603539C0D	3539	target Canyon_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00290	Canyon_Oak Stereo-3 ~24 cm standoff	4539MH001900011603540C0D	3540	autoFocus sub-frame for target Canyon_Oak - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4539MH001900011603541C0D	3541	target Canyon_Oak - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00290	Jeffrey_Pine ~25 cm standoff	4539MH001900011603542C0D	3542	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jeffrey_Pine - standoff near 25 cm
		4539MH001900011603543C0D	3543	target Jeffrey_Pine - standoff near 25 cm
mN00268	Jeffrey_Pine Stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4539MH001680021603544C0D	3544	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4539MH001680021603545C0D	3545	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4539MH001680021603546C0D	3546	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603547C0D	3547	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603548C0D	3548	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603549C0D	3549	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603550C0D	3550	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603551C0D	3551	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603552C0D	3552	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603553C0D	3553	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00268	Jeffrey_Pine Stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4539MH001680021603554C0D	3554	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4539MH001680021603555C0D	3555	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4539MH001680021603556C0D	3556	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603557C0D	3557	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603558C0D	3558	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603559C0D	3559	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603560C0D	3560	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603561C0D	3561	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603562C0D	3562	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4539MH001680021603563C0D	3563	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	4539MH002650001603564C0D	3564	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3556-3563 - best focus image product
		4539MH002650001603565C0D	3565	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3556-3563 - range map product
		4539MH002650001603566C0D	3566	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3546-3553 - best focus image product
		4539MH002650001603567C0D	3567	target Jeffrey_Pine - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3546-3553 - range map product

updated: 17_June_2025

Sol 4543 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-May-25
camera position	0
total parent images	72
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	72

MAHLI imaged the target Mesa_Grande and the DRT finished target Arroyo_Seco.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00359	Mesa_Grande 25 cm standoff	4543MH0029900216035680C0	3568	autofocus sub-frame for target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm		
		4543MH0029900216035690C0	3569	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm		
		4543MH0029900216035700C0	3570	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035710C0	3571	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035720C0	3572	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035730C0	3573	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035740C0	3574	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035750C0	3575	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035760C0	3576	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035770C0	3577	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00299	Mesa_Grande stereo-1 5 cm standoff	4543MH0029900216035780C0	3578	autofocus sub-frame for target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4543MH0029900216035790C0	3579	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4543MH0029900216035800C0	3580	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4543MH0029900216035810C0	3581	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4543MH0029900216035820C0	3582			target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0029900216035830C0	3583			target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0029900216035840C0	3584			target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0029900216035850C0	3585			target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0029900216035860C0	3586			target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0029900216035870C0	3587			target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00299	Mesa_Grande stereo-2 5 cm standoff			4543MH0029900216035880C0	3588	autofocus sub-frame for target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4543MH0029900216035890C0	3589	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4543MH0029900216035900C0	3590	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4543MH0029900216035910C0	3591	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4543MH0029900216035920C0	3592	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035930C0	3593	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035940C0	3594	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035950C0	3595	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035960C0	3596	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0029900216035970C0	3597	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00796	Mesa_Grande 1 cm standoff	4543MH0079600216035980C0	3598	autofocus sub-frame for target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm
				4543MH0079600216035990C0	3599	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm
				4543MH0079600216036000C0	3600	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4543MH0079600216036010C0	3601	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4543MH0079600216036020C0	3602			target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0079600216036030C0	3603			target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0079600216036040C0	3604			target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0079600216036050C0	3605			target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0079600216036060C0	3606			target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0079600216036070C0	3607			target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00290	Arroyo_Seco after DRT 25 cm standoff			4543MH0019000216036080C0	3608	autofocus sub-frame for target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
				4543MH0019000216036090C0	3609	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Arroyo_Seco after DRT stereo-1 5 cm standoff			4543MH0016800216036100C0	3610	autofocus sub-frame for target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4543MH0016800216036110C0	3611	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4543MH0016800216036120C0	3612	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0016800216036130C0	3613	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0016800216036140C0	3614	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0016800216036150C0	3615	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0016800216036160C0	3616	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0016800216036170C0	3617	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0016800216036180C0	3618	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4543MH0016800216036190C0	3619	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00168	Arroyo_Seco after DRT stereo-2 5 cm standoff	4543MH0016800216036200C0	3620	autofocus sub-frame for target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4543MH0016800216036210C0	3621	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4543MH0016800216036220C0	3622	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4543MH0016800216036230C0	3623	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4543MH0016800216036240C0	3624			target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0016800216036250C0	3625			target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0016800216036260C0	3626			target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0016800216036270C0	3627			target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0016800216036280C0	3628			target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4543MH0016800216036290C0	3629			target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mH00743	Arroyo_Seco after DRT ~15 mm standoff	4543MH00743001603639C00	3630	autofocus sub-frame for target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4543MH00743001603631C00	3631	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4543MH00743001603632C00	3632	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4543MH00743001603633C00	3633	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4543MH00743001603634C00	3634	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4543MH00743001603635C00	3635	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4543MH00743001603636C00	3636	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4543MH00743001603637C00	3637	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4543MH00743001603638C00	3638	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4543MH00743001603639C00	3639	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 19_May_2025

Sol 4544 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	19-May-25
camera positions	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	14

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4543 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002171	Focus Merges	4544MH00017J0001603640R00	3640	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3632-3639 - best focus image product
		4544MH00017J0001603641S00	3641	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3632-3639 - range map product
		4544MH00017J0001603642R00	3642	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3622-3629 - best focus image product
		4544MH00017J0001603643S00	3643	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3622-3629 - range map product
		4544MH00017J0001603644R00	3644	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3612-3619 - best focus image product
		4544MH00017J0001603645S00	3645	target Arroyo_Seco - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3612-3619 - range map product
		4544MH00017J0001603646R00	3646	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3600-3607 - best focus image product
		4544MH00017J0001603647S00	3647	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3600-3607 - range map product
		4544MH00017J0001603648R00	3648	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3590-3597 - best focus image product
		4544MH00017J0001603649S00	3649	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3590-3597 - range map product
		4544MH00017J0001603650R00	3650	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3580-3587 - best focus image product
		4544MH00017J0001603651S00	3651	target Mesa_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3580-3587 - range map product
		4544MH00017J0001603652R00	3652	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3570-3577 - best focus image product
		4544MH00017J0001603653S00	3653	target Mesa_Grande - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4543 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3570-3577 - range map product

updated: 21_May_2025

Sol 4546 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	21_May_25	
		camera positions	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	38	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Cucamonga_Peak and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Cucamonga_Peak after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4546MH001900011603654C00	3654	autoFocus sub-frame for target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4546MH001900011603655C00	3655	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN002168	Cucamonga_Peak after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4546MH001680011603656C00	3656	autoFocus sub-frame for target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4546MH001680011603657C00	3657	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4546MH001680011603658C00	3658	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603659C00	3659	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603660C00	3660	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603661C00	3661	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603662C00	3662	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603663C00	3663	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603664C00	3664	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603665C00	3665	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Cucamonga_Peak after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4546MH001680011603666C00	3666	autoFocus sub-frame for target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4546MH001680011603667C00	3667	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4546MH001680011603668C00	3668	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603669C00	3669	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603670C00	3670	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603671C00	3671	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603672C00	3672	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603673C00	3673	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603674C00	3674	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH001680011603675C00	3675	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002164	Cucamonga_Peak after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4546MH0020840011603676C00	3676	autoFocus sub-frame for target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4546MH0020840011603677C00	3677	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4546MH0020840011603678C00	3678	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH0020840011603679C00	3679	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH0020840011603680C00	3680	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH0020840011603681C00	3681	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH0020840011603682C00	3682	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH0020840011603683C00	3683	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH0020840011603684C00	3684	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4546MH0020840011603685C00	3685	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4546MH001930011603686R00	3686	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4546 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3678-3685 - best focus image product
		4546MH001930011603687S00	3687	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4546 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3678-3685 - range map product
		4546MH001930011603688R00	3688	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4546 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3668-3675 - best focus image product
		4546MH001930011603689S00	3689	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4546 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3668-3675 - range map product
		4546MH001930011603690R00	3690	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4546 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3656-3665 - best focus image product
		4546MH001930011603691S00	3691	target Cucamonga_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4546 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3658-3665 - range map product

updated: 23_May_2025

Sol 4547 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Big_Bear_Lake.		22-May-25	
acquired/performed date(s)		22-May-25		Image ID:	
camera position		6		black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images		49		CDPID:	
focus merges performed		0		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total focus merge products		0			
total parent images + focus merge products		49			
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN00190	Big_Bear_Lake before DRT ~24 cm standoff	4547MH0001900011603692C00	3692	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Bear_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm	
		4547MH0001900011603693C00	3693	target Big_Bear_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm	
mN00122	Big_Bear_Lake before DRT ~5 cm standoff	4547MH0001220011603694C00	3694	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Bear_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm	
		4547MH0001220011603695C00	3695	target Big_Bear_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm	
mN00706	Big_Bear_Lake after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4547MH0007060011603696C00	3696	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm	
		4547MH0007060011603697C00	3697	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm	
		4547MH0007060021603698C00	3698	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
mN00879	Big_Bear_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4547MH0008790011603699C00	3699	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		4547MH0008790011603700C00	3700	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		4547MH0008790011603701C00	3701	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
		4547MH0008790011603702C00	3702	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008790011603703C00	3703	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008790011603704C00	3704	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008790011603705C00	3705	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008790011603706C00	3706	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008790011603707C00	3707	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008790011603708C00	3708	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008790011603709C00	3709	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		mN00879	Big_Bear_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4547MH0008790011603710C00	3710
4547MH0008790011603711C00	3711			target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
4547MH0008790011603712C00	3712			target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
4547MH0008790011603713C00	3713			target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
4547MH0008790011603714C00	3714			target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
4547MH0008790011603715C00	3715			target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
4547MH0008790011603716C00	3716			target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
4547MH0008790011603717C00	3717			target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
4547MH0008790011603718C00	3718			target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
4547MH0008790011603719C00	3719			target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00822	Big_Bear_Lake after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4547MH0008220011603720C00	3720	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm	
		4547MH0008220011603721C00	3721	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm	
		4547MH0008220011603722C00	3722	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
		4547MH0008220011603723C00	3723	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008220011603724C00	3724	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008220011603725C00	3725	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008220011603726C00	3726	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008220011603727C00	3727	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008220011603728C00	3728	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008220011603729C00	3729	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00822	Big_Bear_Lake after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4547MH0008220011603730C00	3730	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4547MH0008220011603731C00	3731	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	

updated: 23_May_2025

Sol 4548 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-May-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	6

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4547 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00189	Focus Merges	4548MH001930001603732900	3732	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4547 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3724-3731 - best focus image product
		4548MH001930001603733500	3733	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4547 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3724-3731 - range map product
		4548MH001930001603734900	3734	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4547 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3713-3720 - best focus image product
		4548MH001930001603735500	3735	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4547 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3713-3720 - range map product
		4548MH001930001603736900	3736	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4547 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3702-3709 - best focus image product
		4548MH001930001603737500	3737	target Big_Bear_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4547 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3702-3709 - range map product

mH00815	Camino_Del_Mar after DRT -5 mm standoff	4550MH00835001603799C00	3799	autofocus sub-frame for target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4550MH00835001603800C00	3800	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4550MH00835001603801C00	3801	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4550MH00835001603802C00	3802	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4550MH00835001603803C00	3803	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4550MH00835001603804C00	3804	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4550MH00835001603805C00	3805	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4550MH00835001603806C00	3806	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4550MH00835001603807C00	3807	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4550MH00835001603808C00	3808	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4550MH00835001603809C00	3809	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 27_May_2025

Sol 4552 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-May-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4550 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4552MH001630001603810900	3810	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3802-3809 - best focus image product
		4552MH001630001603811500	3811	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3802-3809 - range map product
		4552MH001630001603812000	3812	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3791-3798 - best focus image product
		4552MH001630001603813500	3813	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3791-3798 - range map product
		4552MH001630001603814000	3814	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3780-3787 - best focus image product
		4552MH001630001603815500	3815	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3780-3787 - range map product
		4552MH001630001603816000	3816	target Mount_Baden_Powell - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3766-3773 - best focus image product
		4552MH001630001603817500	3817	target Mount_Baden_Powell - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3766-3773 - range map product
		4552MH001630001603818000	3818	target Mount_Baden_Powell - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3755-3762 - best focus image product
		4552MH001630001603819500	3819	target Mount_Baden_Powell - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3755-3762 - range map product
		4552MH001630001603820000	3820	target Mount_Baden_Powell - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3744-3751 - best focus image product
		4552MH001630001603821500	3821	target Mount_Baden_Powell - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3744-3751 - range map product

updated: 28_May_2025

Sol 4553 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-May-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	6

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from the Sol 4550 target Camino_Del_Mar were merged again; this happened because a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented acquisition and merge of new MAHLI data planned for the target Palo_Verde_Mountains.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002193	Focus Merges	4553MH001930001603822900	3822	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3802-3809 - best focus image product
		4553MH001930001603823500	3823	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3802-3809 - range map product
		4553MH001930001603824000	3824	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3791-3798 - best focus image product
		4553MH001930001603825500	3825	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3791-3798 - range map product
		4553MH001930001603826000	3826	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3780-3787 - best focus image product
		4553MH001930001603827500	3827	target Camino_Del_Mar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4550 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3780-3787 - range map product

updated: 02_June_2025

Sol 4554 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29-May-25
camera position	2
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Palo_Verde_Mountains and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00359	Palo_Verde_Mountains ~24 cm standoff	4554MH000390001603829C0D	3828	autofocus sub-frame for target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm
		4554MH000390001603829C0D	3829	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm
		4554MH000390001603830C0D	3830	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH000390001603831C0D	3831	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH000390001603832C0D	3832	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH000390001603833C0D	3833	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH000390001603834C0D	3834	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH000390001603835C0D	3835	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH000390001603836C0D	3836	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH000390001603837C0D	3837	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00352	Palo_Verde_Mountains stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4554MH00015200016038938C0D	3838	autofocus sub-frame for target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4554MH00015200016038939C0D	3839	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4554MH00015200016038940C0D	3840	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038941C0D	3841	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038942C0D	3842	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038943C0D	3843	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038944C0D	3844	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038945C0D	3845	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038946C0D	3846	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038947C0D	3847	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00352	Palo_Verde_Mountains stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4554MH00015200016038948C0D	3848	autofocus sub-frame for target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4554MH00015200016038949C0D	3849	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4554MH00015200016038950C0D	3850	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038951C0D	3851	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038952C0D	3852	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038953C0D	3853	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038954C0D	3854	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038955C0D	3855	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038956C0D	3856	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4554MH00015200016038957C0D	3857	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00359	Focus Merges	4554MH00019300016038958C0D	3858	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4554 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3850-3857 - best focus image product
		4554MH00019300016038959C0D	3859	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4554 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3850-3857 - range map product
		4554MH00019300016038960C0D	3860	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4554 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3840-3847 - best focus image product
		4554MH00019300016038961C0D	3861	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4554 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3840-3847 - range map product
		4554MH00019300016038962C0D	3862	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4554 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3830-3837 - best focus image product
		4554MH00019300016038963C0D	3863	target Palo_Verde_Mountains - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4554 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3830-3837 - range map product

updated: 05_June_2025

Sol 4559 - MAHLI Images

acquired (performed date(s))	3-Jun-25
camera position	6
total parent images	72
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	72

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed targets Holcomb_Valley and Santa_Ysabel_Valley.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00706	Holcomb_Valley after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4559MH000706001603864C00	3884	autoFocus sub-frame for target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm		
		4559MH000706001603865C00	3885	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm		
		4559MH000706001603866C00	3886	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00879	Holcomb_Valley after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4559MH0008790011603874C00	3887	autoFocus sub-frame for target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4559MH0008790011603884C00	3888	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4559MH0008790011603894C00	3889	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4559MH0008790011603870C00	3870	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603871C00	3871	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603872C00	3872	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603873C00	3873	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603874C00	3874	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603875C00	3875	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603876C00	3876	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603877C00	3877	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00879	Holcomb_Valley after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4559MH0008790011603878C00	3878	autoFocus sub-frame for target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4559MH0008790011603879C00	3879	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4559MH0008790011603880C00	3880	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
				4559MH0008790011603881C00	3881	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4559MH0008790011603882C00	3882			target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603883C00	3883			target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603884C00	3884			target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603885C00	3885			target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603886C00	3886			target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603887C00	3887			target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603888C00	3888			target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00822	Holcomb_Valley after DRT ~15 mm standoff			4559MH0008220011603894C00	3889	autoFocus sub-frame for target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
				4559MH0008220011603895C00	3890	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
				4559MH0008220011603896C00	3891	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - alternative auto-exposure
				4559MH0008220011603897C00	3892	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4559MH0008220011603898C00	3893	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008220011603899C00	3894	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008220011603900C00	3895	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008220011603901C00	3896	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008220011603897C00	3897	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008220011603898C00	3898	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008220011603899C00	3899	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00706	Santa_Ysabel_Valley after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4559MH000706001603904C00	3900	autoFocus sub-frame for target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
				4559MH000706001603905C00	3901	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
				4559MH000706001603906C00	3902	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		mNI00879	Santa_Ysabel_Valley after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4559MH0008790011603904C00	3903	autoFocus sub-frame for target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
4559MH0008790011603905C00	3904			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
4559MH0008790011603906C00	3905			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
4559MH0008790011603907C00	3906			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603908C00	3907			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603909C00	3908			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603910C00	3909			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603911C00	3910			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603912C00	3911			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603913C00	3912			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4559MH0008790011603914C00	3913			target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00879	Santa_Ysabel_Valley after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			4559MH0008790011603914C00	3914	autoFocus sub-frame for target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4559MH0008790011603915C00	3915	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4559MH0008790011603916C00	3916	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
				4559MH0008790011603917C00	3917	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4559MH0008790011603918C00	3918	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603919C00	3919	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603920C00	3920	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603921C00	3921	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603922C00	3922	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603923C00	3923	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4559MH0008790011603924C00	3924	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mH00822	Santa_Ysabel_Valley after DRT ~15 mm standoff	4559MH008220011603925C00	3925	autofocus sub-frame for target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4559MH008220011603926C00	3926	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4559MH008220011603927C00	3927	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4559MH008220011603928C00	3928	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4559MH008220011603929C00	3929	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4559MH008220011603930C00	3930	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4559MH008220011603931C00	3931	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4559MH008220011603932C00	3932	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4559MH008220011603933C00	3933	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4559MH008220011603934C00	3934	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4559MH008220011603935C00	3935	target Santa_Ysabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 04_June_2025

Sol 4560 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	4-Jun-25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4559 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	4560MH001630001603936R00	3936	target Santa_Yaabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 13 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3928-3935 - best focus image product
		4560MH001630001603937S00	3937	target Santa_Yaabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3928-3935 - range map product
		4560MH001630001603938R00	3938	target Santa_Yaabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3917-3924 - best focus image product
		4560MH001630001603939S00	3939	target Santa_Yaabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3917-3924 - range map product
		4560MH001630001603940R00	3940	target Santa_Yaabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3906-3913 - best focus image product
		4560MH001630001603941S00	3941	target Santa_Yaabel_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3906-3913 - range map product
		4560MH001630001603942R00	3942	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 13 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3892-3899 - best focus image product
		4560MH001630001603943S00	3943	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 13 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3892-3899 - range map product
		4560MH001630001603944R00	3944	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3881-3888 - best focus image product
		4560MH001630001603945S00	3945	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3881-3888 - range map product
		4560MH001630001603946R00	3946	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3870-3877 - best focus image product
		4560MH001630001603947S00	3947	target Holcomb_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4559 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3870-3877 - range map product

updated: 01_May_2026

Sol 4561 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	5-Jun-25	
		camera position	55	Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		total parent images	4	CDPID:
		focus merges performed	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total focus merge products	8	
		total parent images + focus merge products	54	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI images of the intended drill target Altadena after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN100705	Altadena after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4561MH0007060001603948C00	3948	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4561MH000706001603949C00	3949	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4561MH0007060021603950C00	3950	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100879	Altadena after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4561MH0008790001603951C00	3951	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4561MH0008790021603952C00	3952	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4561MH0008790031603953C00	3953	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4561MH0008790041603954C00	3954	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790051603955C00	3955	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790061603956C00	3956	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790071603957C00	3957	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790081603958C00	3958	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790091603959C00	3959	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790101603960C00	3960	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH000879011603961C00	3961	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100879	Altadena after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4561MH0008790001603962C00	3962	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4561MH0008790011603963C00	3963	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4561MH0008790021603964C00	3964	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4561MH0008790031603965C00	3965	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790041603966C00	3966	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790051603967C00	3967	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790061603968C00	3968	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790071603969C00	3969	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790081603970C00	3970	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790091603971C00	3971	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790101603972C00	3972	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100879	Altadena after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	4561MH0008790001603973C00	3973	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4561MH0008790011603974C00	3974	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4561MH0008790021603975C00	3975	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4561MH0008790031603976C00	3976	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790041603977C00	3977	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790051603978C00	3978	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790061603979C00	3979	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790071603980C00	3980	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790081603981C00	3981	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790091603982C00	3982	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008790101603983C00	3983	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100822	Altadena after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	4561MH0008220001603984C00	3984	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4561MH0008220011603985C00	3985	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4561MH0008220021603986C00	3986	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4561MH0008220031603987C00	3987	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008220041603988C00	3988	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008220051603989C00	3989	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008220061603990C00	3990	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008220071603991C00	3991	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008220081603992C00	3992	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008220091603993C00	3993	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4561MH0008220101603994C00	3994	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100881	Altadena after DRT after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	4561MH0008810001603995C00	3995	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Altadena drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 4561 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		4561MH0008810011603996C00	3996	intended Altadena drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 4561 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		4561MH0008810021603997C00	3997	intended Altadena drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 4561 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100153	Focus Merges	4561MH0001530001604000C00	3998	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4561 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3987-3994 - best focus image product
		4561MH0001530001603995C00	3999	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4561 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3987-3994 - range map product
		4561MH0001530001604000C00	4000	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4561 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3976-3983 - best focus image product
		4561MH0001530001604001C00	4001	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4561 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3976-3983 - range map product
		4561MH0001530001604002C00	4002	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4561 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3965-3972 - best focus image product
		4561MH0001530001604003C00	4003	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4561 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3965-3972 - range map product
		4561MH0001530001604004C00	4004	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4561 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3954-3961 - best focus image product
		4561MH0001530001604005C00	4005	intended Altadena drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4561 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3954-3961 - range map product

updated: 13_june_2025

Sol 4568 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	13_jun_25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	15
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	15

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Altadena drill hole and cuttings.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00187	Altadena drill hole drilled on Sol 4564 ~24 cm standoff	4568MH001970001694006C00	4006	autoFocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Altadena - drilled sol 4564 - standoff near 24 cm
		4568MH0019700011694007C00	4007	drill hole in rock named Altadena - drilled sol 4564 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00774	Altadena drill hole drilled on Sol 4564 ~9 cm standoff	4568MH0007740001694008C00	4008	autoFocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Altadena - drilled sol 4564 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 9 cm
		4568MH0007740011694009C00	4009	drill hole in rock named Altadena - drilled sol 4564 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 9 cm
mN00152	Altadena drill cuttings ~5 cm standoff	4568MH001520001694010C00	4010	autoFocus sub-frame for Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm
		4568MH0015200011694011C00	4011	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm
		4568MH0015200011694012C00	4012	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4568MH0015200011694013C00	4013	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4568MH0015200011694014C00	4014	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4568MH0015200011694015C00	4015	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4568MH0015200011694016C00	4016	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4568MH0015200011694017C00	4017	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4568MH0015200011694018C00	4018	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4568MH0015200011694019C00	4019	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 13_june_2025

Sol 4569 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	19_jun_25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	1
total focus merge products:	2
total parent images + focus merge products:	2

Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities:	Focus stack images from Sol 4568 were merged.
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Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00258	Focus Merge	4569MH002580001604020R00	4020	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4569 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4012-4019 - best focus image product
		4569MH002580001604021S00	4021	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4569 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4012-4019 - range map product

Sol 4570 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	04-06-2025
camera position	12
total parent images	88
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	88

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Angels_Flight, the target Ballona_Creek, and the Altadena drill cuttings. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the ChemMin inlet for cleanliness.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mhl00705	Angels_Flight after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4570MH00070600016040220D	4022	autofocus sub-frame for target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		4570MH00070600116040230D	4023	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		4570MH00070600216040240D	4024	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mhl00879	Angels_Flight after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4570MH00087900116040250D	4025	autofocus sub-frame for target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4570MH00087900216040260D	4026	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4570MH00087900316040270D	4027	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4570MH00087900416040280D	4028	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00087900516040290D	4029	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00087900616040300D	4030	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00087900716040310D	4031	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00087900816040320D	4032	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00087900916040330D	4033	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00087901016040340D	4034	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00087901116040350D	4035	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mhl00879	Angels_Flight after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4570MH00087900116040360D	4036	autofocus sub-frame for target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4570MH00087900216040370D	4037	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4570MH00087900316040380D	4038	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
				4570MH00087900416040390D	4039	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4570MH00087900516040400D	4040			target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00087900616040410D	4041			target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00087900716040420D	4042			target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00087900816040430D	4043			target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00087900916040440D	4044			target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00087901016040450D	4045			target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00087901116040460D	4046			target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mhl00822	Angels_Flight after DRT ~15 mm standoff			4570MH00082200116040470D	4047	autofocus sub-frame for target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
				4570MH00082200216040480D	4048	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
				4570MH00082200316040490D	4049	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - alternative auto-exposure
				4570MH00082200416040500D	4050	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4570MH00082200516040510D	4051	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00082200616040520D	4052	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00082200716040530D	4053	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00082200816040540D	4054	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00082200916040550D	4055	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00082201016040560D	4056	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00082201116040570D	4057	target Angels_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mhl00706	Ballona_Creek ~24 cm standoff	4570MH00070600016040580D	4058	autofocus sub-frame for target Ballona_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
				4570MH00070600116040590D	4059	target Ballona_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
				4570MH00070600216040600D	4060	target Ballona_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		mhl00834	Ballona_Creek stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4570MH00083400116040610D	4061	autofocus sub-frame for target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
4570MH00083400216040620D	4062			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
4570MH00083400316040630D	4063			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
4570MH00083400416040640D	4064			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00083400516040650D	4065			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00083400616040660D	4066			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00083400716040670D	4067			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00083400816040680D	4068			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00083400916040690D	4069			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00083401016040700D	4070			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4570MH00083401116040710D	4071			target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mhl00834	Ballona_Creek stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff			4570MH00083400116040720D	4072	autofocus sub-frame for target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4570MH00083400216040730D	4073	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4570MH00083400316040740D	4074	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
				4570MH00083400416040750D	4075	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4570MH00083400516040760D	4076	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00083400616040770D	4077	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00083400716040780D	4078	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00083400816040790D	4079	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00083400916040800D	4080	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00083401016040810D	4081	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4570MH00083401116040820D	4082	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mhl00122	Altadena drill cuttings ~5 cm standoff	4570MH00012200116040830D	4083	autofocus sub-frame for Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm
				4570MH00012200216040840D	4084	Altadena drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm
		mhl00312	MAHLI 12.3 cm working distance above ChemMin inlet mesh, inlet cover open, position 1 of 3, otherwise same as above	4570MH00031200116040850D	4085	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
				4570MH00031200216040860D	4086	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mhl00326	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	4570MH00031200316040870D	4087	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance		
mhl00228	~19 cm above open ChemMin inlet	4570MH00022800116040880D	4088	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance		
		4570MH00022800216040890D	4089	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance		

updated: 16_June_2025

Sol 4571 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	15_Aug_25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4570 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4571MH000227000160409000	4090	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4075-4082 - best focus image product
		4571MH0002270001604091500	4091	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4075-4082 - range map product
		4571MH0002270001604092000	4092	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4064-4071 - best focus image product
		4571MH0002270001604093500	4093	target Ballona_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4064-4071 - range map product
		4571MH0002270001604094000	4094	target Angela_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4039-4046 - best focus image product
		4571MH0002270001604095500	4095	target Angela_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4039-4046 - range map product
		4571MH0002270001604096000	4096	target Angela_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4028-4035 - best focus image product
		4571MH0002270001604097500	4097	target Angela_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4028-4035 - range map product
		4571MH0002270001604098000	4098	target Angela_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4028-4035 - best focus image product
		4571MH0002270001604099500	4099	target Angela_Flight - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4570 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4028-4035 - range map product

updated: 19_June_2025

Sol 4573 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17_Jan_25
camera position	2
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Flamingo and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00876	Flamingo *25 cm standoff	4573MH0008760021604100C00	4100	autoFocus sub-frame for target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm
		4573MH0008760021604101C00	4101	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm
		4573MH0008760021604102C00	4102	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0008760021604103C00	4103	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0008760021604104C00	4104	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0008760021604105C00	4105	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0008760021604106C00	4106	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0008760021604107C00	4107	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0008760021604108C00	4108	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0008760021604109C00	4109	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Flamingo stereo-1 *55 mm standoff	4573MH0002240021604110C00	4110	autoFocus sub-frame for target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4573MH0002240021604111C00	4111	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4573MH0002240021604112C00	4112	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604113C00	4113	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604114C00	4114	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604115C00	4115	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604116C00	4116	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604117C00	4117	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604118C00	4118	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604119C00	4119	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Flamingo stereo-2 *55 mm standoff	4573MH0002240021604120C00	4120	autoFocus sub-frame for target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4573MH0002240021604121C00	4121	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4573MH0002240021604122C00	4122	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604123C00	4123	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604124C00	4124	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604125C00	4125	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604126C00	4126	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604127C00	4127	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604128C00	4128	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4573MH0002240021604129C00	4129	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	4573MH0001930021604130R00	4130	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4122-4129 - best focus image product
		4573MH0001930021604131S00	4131	target Flamingo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4122-4129 - range map product
		4573MH0001930021604132R00	4132	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4112-4119 - best focus image product
		4573MH0001930021604133S00	4133	target Flamingo - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4112-4119 - range map product
		4573MH0001930021604134R00	4134	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4102-4109 - best focus image product
		4573MH0001930021604135S00	4135	target Flamingo - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4102-4109 - range map product

updated: 30_June_2025

Sol 4575 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	19_Jun_25
camera position	4
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	41

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Tarija and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00705	Tarija after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4575MH000706001604136C0D	4136	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm		
		4575MH000706001604137C0D	4137	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm		
		4575MH0007060021604138C0D	4138	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00834	Tarija after DRT Stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4575MH0008340011604139C0D	4139	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4575MH0008340011604140C0D	4140	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4575MH0008340021604141C0D	4141	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4575MH0008340031604142C0D	4142	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008340041604143C0D	4143	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008340051604144C0D	4144	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008340061604145C0D	4145	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008340071604146C0D	4146	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008340081604147C0D	4147	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008340091604148C0D	4148	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008340101604149C0D	4149	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00834	Tarija after DRT Stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4575MH0008340011604150C0D	4150	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4575MH0008340011604151C0D	4151	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
4575MH0008340021604152C0D	4152			target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
4575MH0008340031604153C0D	4153			target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4575MH0008340041604154C0D	4154			target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4575MH0008340051604155C0D	4155			target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4575MH0008340061604156C0D	4156			target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4575MH0008340071604157C0D	4157			target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4575MH0008340081604158C0D	4158			target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4575MH0008340091604159C0D	4159			target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00835	Tarija after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4575MH0008350011604161C0D	4161	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm		
		4575MH0008350011604162C0D	4162	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm		
		4575MH0008350021604163C0D	4163	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4575MH0008350031604164C0D	4164	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008350041604165C0D	4165	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008350051604166C0D	4166	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008350061604167C0D	4167	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008350071604168C0D	4168	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008350081604169C0D	4169	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4575MH0008350091604170C0D	4170	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00189	Focus Merges	4575MH0001930001604171C0D	4171	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4164-4171 - best focus image product		
		4575MH0001930001604173C0D	4173	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4164-4171 - range map product		
		4575MH0001930001604174C0D	4174	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4153-4160 - best focus image product		
		4575MH0001930001604175C0D	4175	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4153-4160 - range map product		
		4575MH0001930001604176C0D	4176	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4142-4149 - best focus image product		
		4575MH0001930001604177C0D	4177	target Tarija - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4142-4149 - range map product		

Sol 4577 - MAHLI Images

acquired (performed date(s))	23 Jun 25
camera positions	11
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	75

MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. MAHLI also imaged the target Copiapo and the DRT-brushed target Copacabana.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN000371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	4577MH0003720016041780C0	4178	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance		
		4577MH00037100116041790C0	4179	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance		
mN000372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	4577MH0003720016041800C0	4180	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance		
		4577MH00037200116041810C0	4181	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance		
mN000374	MAHLI cal target = wheel + surface 30 cm working distance from target	4577MH00037400116041820C0	4182	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target		
		4577MH00037400116041830C0	4183	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target		
		4577MH00037400116041840C0	4184	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity		
mN000373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	4577MH00037300116041850C0	4185	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm		
		4577MH00037300116041860C0	4186	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm		
mN000376	Copiapo ~26 cm standoff	4577MH00087600116041870C0	4187	autofocus sub-frame for target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm		
		4577MH00087600116041880C0	4188	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm		
		4577MH00087600116041890C0	4189	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00087600116041900C0	4190	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00087600116041910C0	4191	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00087600116041920C0	4192	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00087600116041930C0	4193	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00087600116041940C0	4194	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00087600116041950C0	4195	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00087600116041960C0	4196	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN000299	Copiapo stereo-1 ~6 cm standoff	4577MH00029900116041970C0	4197	autofocus sub-frame for target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm
				4577MH00029900116041980C0	4198	target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm
4577MH00029900116041990C0	4199			target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH00029900116042000C0	4200			target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH00029900116042010C0	4201			target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH00029900116042020C0	4202			target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH00029900116042030C0	4203			target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH00029900116042040C0	4204			target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH00029900116042050C0	4205			target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH00029900116042060C0	4206			target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN000299	Copiapo stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff			4577MH00029900116042070C0	4207	autofocus sub-frame for target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
				4577MH00029900116042080C0	4208	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4577MH00029900116042090C0	4209	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00029900116042100C0	4210	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00029900116042110C0	4211	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00029900116042120C0	4212	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00029900116042130C0	4213	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00029900116042140C0	4214	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00029900116042150C0	4215	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH00029900116042160C0	4216	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN000376	Copacabana after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4577MH0007600116042170C0	4217	autofocus sub-frame for target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
				4577MH0007600116042180C0	4218	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
4577MH0007600116042190C0	4219			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN000834	Copacabana after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4577MH0008400116042200C0	4220	autofocus sub-frame for target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4577MH0008400116042210C0	4221	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4577MH0008400116042220C0	4222	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4577MH0008400116042230C0	4223	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH0008400116042240C0	4224	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH0008400116042250C0	4225	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH0008400116042260C0	4226	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH0008400116042270C0	4227	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH0008400116042280C0	4228	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH0008400116042290C0	4229	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4577MH0008400116042300C0	4230	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN000834	Copacabana after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4577MH0008400116042310C0	4231	autofocus sub-frame for target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
4577MH0008400116042320C0	4232			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm		
4577MH0008400116042330C0	4233			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
4577MH0008400116042340C0	4234			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH0008400116042350C0	4235			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH0008400116042360C0	4236			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH0008400116042370C0	4237			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH0008400116042380C0	4238			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH0008400116042390C0	4239			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH0008400116042400C0	4240			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4577MH0008400116042410C0	4241			target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

Continued on Next Page...

mH00815	Copacabana after DRT 5 mm standoff	4577MH000835001160424200	4242	autofocus sub-frame for target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4577MH000835001160424300	4243	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4577MH000835001160424400	4244	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4577MH000835001160424500	4245	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4577MH000835001160424600	4246	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4577MH000835001160424700	4247	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4577MH000835001160424800	4248	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4577MH000835001160424900	4249	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4577MH000835001160425000	4250	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4577MH000835001160425100	4251	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4577MH000835001160425200	4252	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 23_june_2025

Sol 4578 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23_jun_25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4577 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4578MH00163000160423900	4253	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 3 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4244-4252 - best focus image product
		4578MH00163000160425400	4254	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4245-4252 - range map product
		4578MH00163000160425900	4255	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4234-4241 - best focus image product
		4578MH00163000160426500	4256	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4234-4241 - range map product
		4578MH00163000160427900	4257	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4223-4230 - best focus image product
		4578MH00163000160428500	4258	target Copacabana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4223-4230 - range map product
		4578MH00163000160429900	4259	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4209-4216 - best focus image product
		4578MH00163000160426000	4260	target Copiapo - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4209-4216 - range map product
		4578MH00163000160426100	4261	target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4199-4206 - best focus image product
		4578MH00163000160426200	4262	target Copiapo - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4199-4206 - range map product
		4578MH00163000160426300	4263	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4189-4196 - best focus image product
		4578MH00163000160426400	4264	target Copiapo - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4577 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4189-4196 - range map product

updated: 30_June_2025

Sol 4580 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Jan-25
camera position	4
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	41

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Hornitos and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00705	Hornitos after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4580MH0070600216042650CD	4265	autoFocus sub-frame for target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4580MH0070600116042660CD	4266	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4580MH0070600216042670CD	4267	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00879	Hornitos after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4580MH0087900116042680CD	4268	autoFocus sub-frame for target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4580MH0087900116042690CD	4269	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4580MH0087900116042700CD	4270	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4580MH0087900116042710CD	4271	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042720CD	4272	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042730CD	4273	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042740CD	4274	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042750CD	4275	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042760CD	4276	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042770CD	4277	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042780CD	4278	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00879	Hornitos after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4580MH0087900116042790CD	4279	autoFocus sub-frame for target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4580MH0087900116042800CD	4280	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4580MH0087900116042810CD	4281	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4580MH0087900116042820CD	4282	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042830CD	4283	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042840CD	4284	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042850CD	4285	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042860CD	4286	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042870CD	4287	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042880CD	4288	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0087900116042890CD	4289	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00885	Hornitos after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4580MH0088500116042900CD	4290	autoFocus sub-frame for target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4580MH0088500116042910CD	4291	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4580MH0088500116042920CD	4292	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4580MH0088500116042930CD	4293	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0088500116042940CD	4294	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0088500116042950CD	4295	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0088500116042960CD	4296	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0088500116042970CD	4297	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0088500116042980CD	4298	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0088500116042990CD	4299	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4580MH0088500116043000CD	4300	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	4580MH0019300116043010CD	4301	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4580 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4293-4300 - best focus image product
		4580MH0019300116043020CD	4302	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4580 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4293-4300 - range map product
		4580MH0019300116043030CD	4303	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4580 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4282-4289 - best focus image product
		4580MH0019300116043040CD	4304	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4580 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4282-4289 - range map product
		4580MH0019300116043050CD	4305	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4580 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4271-4278 - best focus image product
		4580MH0019300116043060CD	4306	target Hornitos - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4580 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4271-4278 - range map product

updated: 07_July_2025

Sol 4584 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29 Jun 25
camera position	0
total parent images	59
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	59

MAHLI images of the targets Estancia_Alikamari, Santa_Elena, and Ticatica.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00706	Estancia_Alikamari ~25 cm standoff	458MH0007060016043070Z0	4307	autoFocus sub-frame for target Estancia_Alikamari - standoff near 25 cm
		458MH0007060016043080Z0	4308	target Estancia_Alikamari - standoff near 25 cm
		458MH00070600216043090Z0	4309	target Estancia_Alikamari - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00554	Estancia_Alikamari stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	458MH0005540016043100Z0	4310	autoFocus sub-frame for target Estancia_Alikamari - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		458MH0005540016043110Z0	4311	target Estancia_Alikamari - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		458MH00055400216043120Z0	4312	target Estancia_Alikamari - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00554	Estancia_Alikamari stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	458MH0005540016043130Z0	4313	autoFocus sub-frame for target Estancia_Alikamari - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		458MH0005540016043140Z0	4314	target Estancia_Alikamari - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		458MH00055400216043150Z0	4315	target Estancia_Alikamari - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00076	Santa_Elena ~25 cm standoff	458MH0008760016043160Z0	4316	autoFocus sub-frame for target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm
		458MH0008760016043170Z0	4317	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm
		458MH0008760016043180Z0	4318	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008760016043190Z0	4319	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008760016043200Z0	4320	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008760016043210Z0	4321	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008760016043220Z0	4322	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008760016043230Z0	4323	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008760016043240Z0	4324	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008760016043250Z0	4325	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00182	Santa_Elena stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	458MH0001820016043260Z0
458MH0001820016043270Z0	4327			target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
458MH0001820016043280Z0	4328			target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0001820016043290Z0	4329			target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0001820016043300Z0	4330			target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0001820016043310Z0	4331			target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0001820016043320Z0	4332			target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0001820016043330Z0	4333			target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0001820016043340Z0	4334			target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0001820016043350Z0	4335			target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Santa_Elena stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			458MH0001820016043360Z0
		458MH0001820016043370Z0	4337	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		458MH0001820016043380Z0	4338	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0001820016043390Z0	4339	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0001820016043400Z0	4340	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0001820016043410Z0	4341	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0001820016043420Z0	4342	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0001820016043430Z0	4343	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0001820016043440Z0	4344	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0001820016043450Z0	4345	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00885	Ticatica stereo-1 ~26 cm standoff	458MH0008850016043460Z0
458MH0008850016043470Z0	4347			target Ticatica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm
458MH0008850016043480Z0	4348			target Ticatica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0008850016043490Z0	4349			target Ticatica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0008850016043500Z0	4350			target Ticatica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0008850016043510Z0	4351			target Ticatica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0008850016043520Z0	4352			target Ticatica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0008850016043530Z0	4353			target Ticatica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0008850016043540Z0	4354			target Ticatica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
458MH0008850016043550Z0	4355			target Ticatica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00885	Ticatica stereo-2 ~26 cm standoff			458MH0008850016043560Z0
		458MH0008850016043570Z0	4357	target Ticatica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm
		458MH0008850016043580Z0	4358	target Ticatica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008850016043590Z0	4359	target Ticatica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008850016043600Z0	4360	target Ticatica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008850016043610Z0	4361	target Ticatica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008850016043620Z0	4362	target Ticatica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008850016043630Z0	4363	target Ticatica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008850016043640Z0	4364	target Ticatica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		458MH0008850016043650Z0	4365	target Ticatica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 30_june_2025

Sol 4585 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	30_jun_25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4584 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4585MH0002270001604366R00	4366	target Ticatlica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4358-4365 - best focus image product
		4585MH0002270001604367500	4367	target Ticatlica - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4338-4365 - range map product
		4585MH0002270001604368R00	4368	target Ticatlica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4348-4355 - best focus image product
		4585MH0002270001604369500	4369	target Ticatlica - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4348-4355 - range map product
		4585MH0002270001604370R00	4370	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4338-4345 - best focus image product
		4585MH0002270001604371500	4371	target Santa_Elena - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4338-4345 - range map product
		4585MH0002270001604372R00	4372	target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4328-4335 - best focus image product
		4585MH0002270001604373500	4373	target Santa_Elena - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4328-4335 - range map product
		4585MH0002270001604374R00	4374	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4318-4325 - best focus image product
		4585MH0002270001604375500	4375	target Santa_Elena - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4584 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4318-4325 - range map product

Sol 4586 - MAHLI Images

		acquired(performed date(s))	3 Jul 25	
		camera position	65	Image ID:
		total parent images	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	65	
MAHLI image of the targets Playa_Agua_De_Luna and La_Paz. At right, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00076	Playa_Agua_De_Luna ~25 cm standoff	4586MH000760021604376C00	4376	autofocus sub-frame for target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm
		4586MH000760021604377C00	4377	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm
		4586MH000760021604378C00	4378	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604379C00	4379	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604380C00	4380	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604381C00	4381	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604382C00	4382	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604383C00	4383	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604384C00	4384	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604385C00	4385	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00077	Playa_Agua_De_Luna stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4586MH0001730021604386C00	4386	autofocus sub-frame for target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4586MH0001730021604387C00	4387	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4586MH0001730021604388C00	4388	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604389C00	4389	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604390C00	4390	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604391C00	4391	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604392C00	4392	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604393C00	4393	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604394C00	4394	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604395C00	4395	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00077	Playa_Agua_De_Luna stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4586MH0001730021604396C00	4396	autofocus sub-frame for target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4586MH0001730021604397C00	4397	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4586MH0001730021604398C00	4398	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604399C00	4399	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604400C00	4400	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604401C00	4401	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604402C00	4402	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604403C00	4403	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604404C00	4404	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604405C00	4405	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00076	La_Paz ~25 cm standoff	4586MH000760021604406C00	4406	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm
		4586MH000760021604407C00	4407	target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm
		4586MH000760021604408C00	4408	target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604409C00	4409	target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604410C00	4410	target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604411C00	4411	target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604412C00	4412	target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604413C00	4413	target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604414C00	4414	target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH000760021604415C00	4415	target La_Paz - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00077	La_Paz stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4586MH0001730021604416C00	4416	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4586MH0001730021604417C00	4417	target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4586MH0001730021604418C00	4418	target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604419C00	4419	target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604420C00	4420	target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604421C00	4421	target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604422C00	4422	target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604423C00	4423	target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604424C00	4424	target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604425C00	4425	target La_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00077	La_Paz stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4586MH0001730021604426C00	4426	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4586MH0001730021604427C00	4427	target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4586MH0001730021604428C00	4428	target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604429C00	4429	target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604430C00	4430	target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604431C00	4431	target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604432C00	4432	target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604433C00	4433	target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604434C00	4434	target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4586MH0001730021604435C00	4435	target La_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000312	MAHLI 12.3 cm working distance above CheMin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; imaging at night	4586MH000320001604436C00	4436	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN000326	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	4586MH000320001604437C00	4437	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mN000326	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	4586MH000320001604438C00	4438	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN000326	~19 cm above open CheMin inlet	4586MH000320001604439C00	4439	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN000328		4586MH000320001604440C00	4440	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance

updated: 02_July_2025

Sol 4587 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	2 Jul 25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4586 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4587MH0016300160441300	4441	target Ia_Per - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4428-4433 - best focus image product
		4587MH0016300160442500	4442	target Ia_Paz - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4428-4433 - range map product
		4587MH0016300160443800	4443	target Ia_Per - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4418-4423 - best focus image product
		4587MH0016300160444500	4444	target Ia_Paz - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4418-4423 - range map product
		4587MH0016300160445900	4445	target Ia_Per - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4408-4413 - best focus image product
		4587MH0016300160446500	4446	target Ia_Paz - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4408-4413 - range map product
		4587MH0016300160447800	4447	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4398-4403 - best focus image product
		4587MH0016300160448500	4448	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4398-4403 - range map product
		4587MH0016300160449800	4449	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4388-4393 - best focus image product
		4587MH0016300160450500	4450	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4388-4393 - range map product
		4587MH0016300160451800	4451	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4378-4383 - best focus image product
		4587MH0016300160452500	4452	target Playa_Agua_De_Luna - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4586 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4378-4383 - range map product

Sol 4588 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	3 Jul 25
camera position:	4
total parent images:	35
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	41

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Guapay and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00705	Guapay after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4588MH00070600160445300	4453	autoFocus sub-frame for target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4588MH00070601160445400	4454	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4588MH00070602160445500	4455	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00879	Guapay after DRT Stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4588MH00087900116044500	4456	autoFocus sub-frame for target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4588MH000879001160445700	4457	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4588MH000879001160445800	4458	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4588MH000879001160445900	4459	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH000879001160446000	4460	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH000879001160446100	4461	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH000879001160446200	4462	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH000879001160446300	4463	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH000879001160446400	4464	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH000879001160446500	4465	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH000879001160446600	4466	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00879	Guapay after DRT Stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4588MH000879001160446700
4588MH000879001160446800	4468			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
4588MH000879001160446900	4469			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
4588MH000879001160447000	4470			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4588MH000879001160447100	4471			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4588MH000879001160447200	4472			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
4588MH000879001160447300	4473			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
4588MH000879001160447400	4474			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
4588MH000879001160447500	4475			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4588MH000879001160447600	4476			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4588MH000879001160447700	4477			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00885	Guapay after DRT ~1 cm standoff			4588MH00085001160447800
		4588MH00085001160447900	4479	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4588MH00085001160448000	4480	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4588MH00085001160448100	4481	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH00085001160448200	4482	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH00085001160448300	4483	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH00085001160448400	4484	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH00085001160448500	4485	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH00085001160448600	4486	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH00085001160448700	4487	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4588MH00085001160448800	4488	target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00193	Focus Merges	4588MH00193001160448900
4588MH00193001160449000	4490			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4588 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4481-4488 - range map product
4588MH00193001160449100	4491			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4588 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4470-4477 - best focus image product
4588MH00193001160449200	4492			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4588 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4470-4477 - range map product
4588MH00193001160449300	4493			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4588 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4459-4466 - best focus image product
4588MH00193001160449400	4494			target Guapay - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4588 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4459-4466 - range map product

updated: 07_July_2025

Sol 4591 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	6-Jul-25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4590 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4591MH000227000160453900	4553	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4545-4552 - best focus image product
		4591MH000227000160454500	4554	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4545-4552 - range map product
		4591MH000227000160455900	4555	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4534-4541 - best focus image product
		4591MH000227000160456500	4556	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4534-4541 - range map product
		4591MH000227000160457900	4557	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4523-4530 - best focus image product
		4591MH000227000160458500	4558	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4523-4530 - range map product
		4591MH000227000160459900	4559	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4512-4519 - best focus image product
		4591MH000227000160460500	4560	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4512-4519 - range map product
		4591MH000227000160461900	4561	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4501-4508 - best focus image product
		4591MH000227000160462500	4562	target Huellas_De_Dinosaurios - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4590 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4501-4508 - range map product

updated: 09_July_2025

Sol 4594 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	9 Jul 25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	11
total focus merge products:	22
total parent images + focus merge products:	22

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4593 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00449	Focus Merges	4594MH0004900010467300	4673	target Wila_Willki - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4665-4672 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010467450	4674	target Wila_Willki - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4665-4672 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010467500	4675	target Wila_Willki - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4655-4662 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010467650	4676	target Wila_Willki - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4655-4662 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010467700	4677	target Wila_Willki - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4645-4652 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010467850	4678	target Wila_Willki - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4645-4652 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010467900	4679	target Wila_Willki - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4635-4642 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010468050	4680	target Wila_Willki - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4635-4642 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010468100	4681	target Parinaocta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4625-4632 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010468250	4682	target Parinaocta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4625-4632 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010468300	4683	target Parinaocta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4615-4622 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010468450	4684	target Parinaocta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4615-4622 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010468500	4685	target Parinaocta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4605-4612 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010468650	4686	target Parinaocta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4605-4612 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010468700	4687	target Parinaocta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4595-4602 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010468850	4688	target Parinaocta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4595-4602 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010468900	4689	target Pan_De_Azucar - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 31 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4585-4592 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010469050	4690	target Pan_De_Azucar - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 31 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4585-4592 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010469100	4691	target Pan_De_Azucar - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4575-4582 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010469250	4692	target Pan_De_Azucar - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 35 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4575-4582 - range map product
		4594MH0004900010469300	4693	target Pan_De_Azucar - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 50 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4565-4572 - best focus image product
		4594MH0004900010469450	4694	target Pan_De_Azucar - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 50 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4593 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4565-4572 - range map product

updated: 14_July_2025

Sol 4595 - MAHLI Images

acquired(performed date(s))	08 Jul 25
camera position	2
total parent images	63
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	63

Image ID:
black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Rio_Vivizu and the DRT-brushed target Cataratas_Del_Jardin.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00359	Rio_Vivizu ~24 cm standoff	4695	4695	autofocus sub-frame for target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm		
		4696	4696	target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm		
		4697	4697	target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4698	4698	target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4699	4699	target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4700	4700	target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4701	4701	target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4702	4702	target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4703	4703	target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4704	4704	target Rio_Vivizu - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00224	Rio_Vivizu Stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	4705	4705	autofocus sub-frame for target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
				4706	4706	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
				4707	4707	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4708	4708	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4709	4709			target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4710	4710			target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4711	4711			target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4712	4712			target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4713	4713			target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4714	4714			target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00224	Rio_Vivizu Stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff			4715	4715	autofocus sub-frame for target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
				4716	4716	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
				4717	4717	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4718	4718	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4719	4719	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4720	4720	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4721	4721	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4722	4722	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4723	4723	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4724	4724	target Rio_Vivizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00190	Cataratas_Del_Jardin after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4725	4725	autofocus sub-frame for target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4726	4726	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		mN00336	Cataratas_Del_Jardin after DRT Stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4727	4727	autofocus sub-frame for target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4728	4728	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
4729	4729			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4730	4730			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4731	4731			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4732	4732			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4733	4733			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4734	4734			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4735	4735			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4736	4736			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00336	Cataratas_Del_Jardin after DRT Stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			4737	4737	autofocus sub-frame for target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4738	4738	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4739	4739	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4740	4740	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4741	4741	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4742	4742	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4743	4743	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4744	4744	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4745	4745	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4746	4746	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00848	Cataratas_Del_Jardin after DRT ~15 mm standoff	4747	4747	autofocus sub-frame for target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
				4748	4748	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
				4749	4749	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4750	4750	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4751	4751			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4752	4752			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4753	4753			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4754	4754			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4755	4755			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4756	4756			target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 11_May_2025

Sol 4596 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	23_May_25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4595 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4596MH001630001104757900	4757	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4749-4756 - best focus image product
		4596MH001630001104758500	4758	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4749-4756 - range map product
		4596MH001630001104759900	4759	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4739-4746 - best focus image product
		4596MH001630001104760500	4760	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4739-4746 - range map product
		4596MH001630001104761900	4761	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4729-4736 - best focus image product
		4596MH001630001104762500	4762	target Cataratas_Del_Jardin - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4729-4736 - range map product
		4596MH00163000104763900	4763	target Rio_Iviriizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4717-4724 - best focus image product
		4596MH00163000104764500	4764	target Rio_Iviriizu - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4717-4724 - range map product
		4596MH00163000104765900	4765	target Rio_Iviriizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4707-4714 - best focus image product
		4596MH00163000104766500	4766	target Rio_Iviriizu - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4707-4714 - range map product
		4596MH00163000104767900	4767	target Rio_Iviriizu - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4697-4704 - best focus image product
		4596MH00163000104768500	4768	target Rio_Iviriizu - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4595 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4697-4704 - range map product

Sol 4597 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23 Jun 25
camera position	14
total parent images	100
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	100

MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Cochabamba and the targets Incachaca and Tejas.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Cochabamba after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4597MH0019000100479000	4769	autofocus sub-frame for target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4597MH0019000100479000	4770	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Cochabamba after DRT stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	4597MH00336002100477200	4771	autofocus sub-frame for target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH00336002100477200	4772	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH00336002100477200	4773	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100477200	4774	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100477200	4775	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100477200	4776	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100477200	4777	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100477200	4778	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100477200	4779	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100477200	4780	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Cochabamba after DRT stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	4597MH00336002100478200	4781	autofocus sub-frame for target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH00336002100478200	4782	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH00336002100478200	4783	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100478200	4784	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100478200	4785	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100478200	4786	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100478200	4787	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100478200	4788	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100478200	4789	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00336002100478200	4790	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00705	Cochabamba after DRT relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	4597MH0070500100479300	4791	autofocus sub-frame for target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH0070500100479300	4792	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Cochabamba after DRT relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	4597MH0070500100479300	4793	autofocus sub-frame for target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH0070500100479300	4794	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Cochabamba after DRT relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	4597MH0070500100479300	4795	autofocus sub-frame for target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH0070500100479300	4796	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00848	Cochabamba after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4597MH0084800100479700	4797	autofocus sub-frame for target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4597MH0084800100479700	4798	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4597MH00848002100479900	4799	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00848002100480000	4800	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00848002100480100	4801	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00848002100480200	4802	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00848002100480300	4803	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00848002100480400	4804	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00848002100480500	4805	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00848002100480600	4806	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Incachaca ~25 cm standoff	4597MH0019000100480700	4807	autofocus sub-frame for target Incachaca - standoff near 25 cm
		4597MH0019000100480800	4808	target Incachaca - standoff near 25 cm
mN00338	Incachaca stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4597MH00338002100480900	4809	autofocus sub-frame for target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH00338002100481000	4810	target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH00338002100481100	4811	target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100481200	4812	target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100481300	4813	target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100481400	4814	target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100481500	4815	target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100481600	4816	target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100481700	4817	target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100481800	4818	target Incachaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00338	Incachaca stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4597MH00338002100481900	4819	autofocus sub-frame for target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH00338002100482000	4820	target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4597MH00338002100482100	4821	target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100482200	4822	target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100482300	4823	target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100482400	4824	target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100482500	4825	target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100482600	4826	target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100482700	4827	target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00338002100482800	4828	target Incachaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00357	Incachaca *2 cm standoff	4597MH00357001094829C0D	4E29	autofocus sub-frame for target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm
		4597MH00357001094830C0D	4E30	target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm
		4597MH00357002094831C0D	4E31	target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00357002094832C0D	4E32	target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00357002094833C0D	4E33	target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00357002094834C0D	4E34	target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00357002094835C0D	4E35	target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00357002094836C0D	4E36	target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00357002094837C0D	4E37	target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4597MH00357002094838C0D	4E38	target Incachaca - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00876	Tejas *24 cm standoff	4597MH00876002094839C0D	4E39	autofocus sub-frame for target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm
		4597MH00876001094840C0D	4E40	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm
		4597MH00876002094841C0D	4E41	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00876002094842C0D	4E42	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00876002094843C0D	4E43	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00876002094844C0D	4E44	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00876002094845C0D	4E45	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00876002094846C0D	4E46	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00876002094847C0D	4E47	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4597MH00876002094848C0D	4E48	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00878	Tejas stereo-1 *95 mm standoff	4597MH00878000094849C0D	4E49	autofocus sub-frame for target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm
		4597MH00878001094850C0D	4E50	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm
		4597MH00878002094851C0D	4E51	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094852C0D	4E52	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094853C0D	4E53	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094854C0D	4E54	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094855C0D	4E55	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094856C0D	4E56	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094857C0D	4E57	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4597MH00878002094858C0D	4E58	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00878	Tejas stereo-2 *95 mm standoff	4597MH00878000094859C0D	4E59	autofocus sub-frame for target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm
		4597MH00878001094860C0D	4E60	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm
		4597MH00878002094861C0D	4E61	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094862C0D	4E62	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094863C0D	4E63	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094864C0D	4E64	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094865C0D	4E65	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094866C0D	4E66	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4597MH00878002094867C0D	4E67	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4597MH00878002094868C0D	4E68	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 14_July_2025

Sol 4598 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	23 Jul 25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	9
total focus merge products:	18
total parent images + focus merge products:	18

summary of MAHLI activities: On Sol 4598, MAHLI images that correspond to COPIDs 1 through 3535 (data from Sols 4359-4537) were deleted from the MAHLI OGA non-volatile memory storage. Focus stack images from Sol 4597 were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	COPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00536	Focus Merges	4598MH00536000100001900	1	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4861-4868 - best focus image product
		4598MH005360001700002500	2	target Tejas - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4861-4868 - range map product
		4598MH005360001700003900	3	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4801-4838 - best focus image product
		4598MH005360001700004500	4	target Tejas - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4801-4838 - range map product
		4598MH005360001700005900	5	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4841-4848 - best focus image product
		4598MH005360001700006500	6	target Tejas - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4841-4848 - range map product
		4598MH005360001700007900	7	target Incahaca - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4831-4838 - best focus image product
		4598MH005360001700008500	8	target Incahaca - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4831-4838 - range map product
		4598MH005360001700009900	9	target Incahaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4821-4828 - best focus image product
		4598MH005360001700010500	10	target Incahaca - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4821-4828 - range map product
		4598MH005360001700011900	11	target Incahaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4811-4818 - best focus image product
		4598MH005360001700012500	12	target Incahaca - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4811-4818 - range map product
		4598MH005360001700013900	13	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4793-4806 - best focus image product
		4598MH005360001700014500	14	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4793-4806 - range map product
		4598MH005360001700015900	15	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4783-4790 - best focus image product
		4598MH005360001700016500	16	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4783-4790 - range map product
		4598MH005360001700017900	17	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4773-4780 - best focus image product
		4598MH005360001700018500	18	target Cochabamba - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4597 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4773-4780 - range map product

updated: 29_April_2026

Sol 4600 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	ES 20 25
camera position	6
total parent images	53
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	57

MAHLI imaged the target Playa_De_La_Gallina. MAHLI also imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding (sky flats). The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00706	Playa_De_La_Gallina ~24 cm standoff	4600MH007060011700019C0D	19	autofocus sub-frame for target Playa_De_La_Gallina - standoff near 24 cm		
		4600MH00706011700020C0D	20	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - standoff near 24 cm		
		4600MH00706021170001C0D	21	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00900	Playa_De_La_Gallina stereo-1 ~95 mm standoff	4600MH00900001170002C0D	22	autofocus sub-frame for target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm		
		4600MH0090001170003C0D	23	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm		
		4600MH00900021170004C0D	24	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 95 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00900	Playa_De_La_Gallina stereo-2 ~95 mm standoff	4600MH00900001170005C0D	25	autofocus sub-frame for target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm		
		4600MH0090001170006C0D	26	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm		
		4600MH00900021170007C0D	27	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 95 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00879	Playa_De_La_Gallina stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4600MH008790011700028C0D	28	autofocus sub-frame for target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4600MH00879011700029C0D	29	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4600MH008790011700030C0D	30	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4600MH008790311700031C0D	31	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4600MH008790011700032C0D	32	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4600MH008790311700033C0D	33	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4600MH008790011700034C0D	34	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4600MH008790311700035C0D	35	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4600MH008790011700036C0D	36	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4600MH008790311700037C0D	37	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4600MH008790011700038C0D	38	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00879	Playa_De_La_Gallina stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4600MH008790011700039C0D	39	autofocus sub-frame for target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4600MH008790011700040C0D	40	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
4600MH008790311700041C0D	41			target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
4600MH008790011700042C0D	42			target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4600MH008790311700043C0D	43			target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4600MH008790011700044C0D	44			target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4600MH008790311700045C0D	45			target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4600MH008790011700046C0D	46			target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4600MH008790311700047C0D	47			target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4600MH008790011700048C0D	48			target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4600MH008790311700049C0D	49			target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +130° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck			4600MH007120011700050C0D	50	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 0 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm
				4600MH007120011700051C0D	51	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm
		4600MH007120011700052C0D	52	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm		
		4600MH007120011700053C0D	53	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 268 mm		
mNI00453	sky flats - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +130° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck	4600MH004530011700054C0D	54	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus		
		4600MH004530011700055C0D	55	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm		
		4600MH004530011700056C0D	56	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm		
		4600MH004530011700057C0D	57	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm		
		4600MH004530011700058C0D	58	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm		
		4600MH004530011700059C0D	59	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm		
mNI00453	sky flats - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +130° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck camera rotated 180° relative to the preceding set of sky flats	4600MH004530011700060C0D	60	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus		
		4600MH004530011700061C0D	61	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		4600MH004530011700062C0D	62	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		4600MH004530011700063C0D	63	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		4600MH004530011700064C0D	64	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		4600MH004530011700065C0D	65	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
mNI00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +130° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck camera rotated 180° relative to the preceding set of sky flats	4600MH007120011700066C0D	66	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		4600MH007120011700067C0D	67	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 0 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		4600MH007120011700068C0D	68	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		4600MH007120011700069C0D	69	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		4600MH007120011700070C0D	70	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 268 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		4600MH007120011700071C0D	71	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
mNI00703	Focus Merges	4600MH007030011700072C0D	72	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4600 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 42-49 - best focus image product		
		4600MH007030011700073C0D	73	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4600 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 42-49 - range map product		
		4600MH007030011700074C0D	74	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4600 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 31-38 - best focus image product		
		4600MH007030011700075C0D	75	target Playa_De_La_Gallina - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4600 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 31-38 - range map product		

updated: 18_July_2025

Sol 4602 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	27 Jul 25
camera position:	2
total parent images:	35
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	39

summary of MAHLI activities:

MAHLI imaged the target Nocarane and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000359	Nocarane ~24 cm standoff	4602MH00039001700076C00	76	autoFocus sub-frame for target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm
		4602MH00039001700077C00	77	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm
		4602MH00039001700078C00	78	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH00039001700079C00	79	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH00039001700080C00	80	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH00039001700081C00	81	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH00039001700082C00	82	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH00039001700083C00	83	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH00039001700084C00	84	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH00039001700085C00	85	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000373	Nocarane stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4602MH000173001700086C00	86	autoFocus sub-frame for target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4602MH000173001700087C00	87	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4602MH000173001700088C00	88	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700089C00	89	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700090C00	90	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700091C00	91	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700092C00	92	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700093C00	93	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700094C00	94	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700095C00	95	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000373	Nocarane stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4602MH000173001700096C00	96	autoFocus sub-frame for target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4602MH000173001700097C00	97	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4602MH000173001700098C00	98	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700099C00	99	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700100C00	100	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700101C00	101	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700102C00	102	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700103C00	103	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700104C00	104	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4602MH000173001700105C00	105	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000383	Focus Merges	4602MH000193001700106R00	106	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4602 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 98-105 - best focus image product
		4602MH000193001700107S00	107	target Nocarane - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4602 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 98-105 - range map product
		4602MH000193001700108R00	108	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4602 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 88-95 - best focus image product
		4602MH000193001700109S00	109	target Nocarane - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4602 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 88-95 - range map product
		4602MH000193001700110R00	110	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4602 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 78-85 - best focus image product
		4602MH000193001700111S00	111	target Nocarane - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4602 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 78-85 - range map product

Sol 4604 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28 Jul 25
camera position	90
total parent images	90
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	90

MAHLI image of the targets Vicuna, Totoral and Sillar.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00359	Vicuna ~25 cm standoff	46GMH000359001170011200	112	autofocus sub-frame for target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm		
		46GMH000359001170011300	113	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm		
		46GMH000359001170011400	114	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH000359001170011500	115	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH000359001170011600	116	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH000359001170011700	117	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH000359001170011800	118	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH000359001170011900	119	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH000359001170012000	120	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH000359001170012100	121	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00224	Vicuna stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	46GMH00024001170012200	122	autofocus sub-frame for target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				46GMH00024001170012300	123	target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
46GMH00024001170012400	124			target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170012500	125			target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170012600	126			target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170012700	127			target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170012800	128			target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170012900	129			target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170013000	130			target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170013100	131			target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00224	Vicuna stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			46GMH00024001170013200	132	autofocus sub-frame for target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				46GMH00024001170013300	133	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		46GMH00024001170013400	134	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170013500	135	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170013600	136	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170013700	137	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170013800	138	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170013900	139	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170014000	140	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170014100	141	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00359	Totoral ~25 cm standoff	46GMH000359001170014200	142	autofocus sub-frame for target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm
				46GMH000359001170014300	143	target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm
46GMH000359001170014400	144			target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH000359001170014500	145			target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH000359001170014600	146			target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH000359001170014700	147			target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH000359001170014800	148			target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH000359001170014900	149			target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH000359001170015000	150			target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH000359001170015100	151			target Totoral - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00224	Totoral stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff			46GMH00024001170015200	152	autofocus sub-frame for target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
				46GMH00024001170015300	153	target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		46GMH00024001170015400	154	target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170015500	155	target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170015600	156	target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170015700	157	target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170015800	158	target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170015900	159	target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170016000	160	target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		46GMH00024001170016100	161	target Totoral - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00224	Totoral stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	46GMH00024001170016200	162	autofocus sub-frame for target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
				46GMH00024001170016300	163	target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
46GMH00024001170016400	164			target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170016500	165			target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170016600	166			target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170016700	167			target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170016800	168			target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170016900	169			target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170017000	170			target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
46GMH00024001170017100	171			target Totoral - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mH00359	Sillar ~25 cm standoff	460MH00035900170017400	172	autofocus sub-frame for target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm
		460MH00035900170017300	173	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm
		460MH00035900170017400	174	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00035900170017500	175	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00035900170017600	176	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00035900170017700	177	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00035900170017800	178	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00035900170017900	179	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00035900170018000	180	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00035900170018100	181	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00224	Sillar stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	460MH00022400170018200	182	autofocus sub-frame for target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		460MH00022400170018300	183	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		460MH00022400170018400	184	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170018500	185	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170018600	186	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170018700	187	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170018800	188	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170018900	189	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170019000	190	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170019100	191	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00224	Sillar stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	460MH00022400170019200	192	autofocus sub-frame for target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		460MH00022400170019300	193	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		460MH00022400170019400	194	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170019500	195	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170019600	196	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170019700	197	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170019800	198	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170019900	199	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170020000	200	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460MH00022400170020100	201	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 21_July_2025

Sol 4605 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	20 Jul 25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	9
total focus merge products:	18
total parent images + focus merge products:	18

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4604 were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00536	Focus Merges	4605MH005360001700202900	202	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 194-201 - best focus image product
		4605MH005360001700203500	203	target Sillar - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 194-201 - range map product
		4605MH005360001700204900	204	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 184-191 - best focus image product
		4605MH005360001700205500	205	target Sillar - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 184-191 - range map product
		4605MH005360001700206900	206	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 174-181 - best focus image product
		4605MH005360001700207500	207	target Sillar - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 174-181 - range map product
		4605MH005360001700208900	208	target Total - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 164-171 - best focus image product
		4605MH005360001700209500	209	target Total - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 164-171 - range map product
		4605MH005360001700210900	210	target Total - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 154-161 - best focus image product
		4605MH005360001700211500	211	target Total - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 154-161 - range map product
		4605MH005360001700212900	212	target Total - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 144-151 - best focus image product
		4605MH005360001700213500	213	target Total - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 144-151 - range map product
		4605MH005360001700214900	214	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 134-141 - best focus image product
		4605MH005360001700215500	215	target Vicuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 134-141 - range map product
		4605MH005360001700216900	216	target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 124-131 - best focus image product
		4605MH005360001700217500	217	target Vicuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 124-131 - range map product
		4605MH005360001700218900	218	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 114-121 - best focus image product
		4605MH005360001700219500	219	target Vicuna - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4604 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 114-121 - range map product

Sol 4608 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	2025-07-31
camera position	75
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	90

MAHLI imaged the target Paposo, the target Aqua_Dulce and the DRT-brushed target La_Tranquila. The focus stack images were merged as well.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Paposo ~25 cm standoff	4608MH001900011700220C0	220	autofocus sub-frame for target Paposo - standoff near 25 cm
		4608MH001900011700221C0	221	target Paposo - standoff near 25 cm
mN00273	Paposo stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4608MH001730011700222C0	222	autofocus sub-frame for target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH001730011700223C0	223	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH001730011700224C0	224	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700225C0	225	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700226C0	226	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700227C0	227	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700228C0	228	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700229C0	229	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700230C0	230	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700231C0	231	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00273	Paposo stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4608MH001730011700232C0	232	autofocus sub-frame for target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH001730011700233C0	233	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH001730011700234C0	234	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700235C0	235	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700236C0	236	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700237C0	237	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700238C0	238	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700239C0	239	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700240C0	240	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001730011700241C0	241	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00290	Aqua_Dulce ~25 cm standoff	4608MH001900011700242C0	242	autofocus sub-frame for target Aqua_Dulce - standoff near 25 cm
4608MH001900011700243C0	243	target Aqua_Dulce - standoff near 25 cm		
mN00336	Aqua_Dulce stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4608MH003360011700244C0	244	autofocus sub-frame for target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH003360011700245C0	245	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH003360011700246C0	246	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700247C0	247	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700248C0	248	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700249C0	249	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700250C0	250	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700251C0	251	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700252C0	252	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700253C0	253	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Aqua_Dulce stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4608MH003360011700254C0	254	autofocus sub-frame for target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH003360011700255C0	255	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH003360011700256C0	256	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700257C0	257	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700258C0	258	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700259C0	259	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700260C0	260	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700261C0	261	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700262C0	262	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH003360011700263C0	263	target Aqua_Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00290	La_Tranquila after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4608MH001900011700264C0	264	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
4608MH001900011700265C0	265	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
mN00168	La_Tranquila after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4608MH001680011700266C0	266	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH001680011700267C0	267	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH001680011700268C0	268	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700269C0	269	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700270C0	270	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700271C0	271	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700272C0	272	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700273C0	273	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700274C0	274	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700275C0	275	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	La_Tranquila after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4608MH001680011700276C0	276	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH001680011700277C0	277	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4608MH001680011700278C0	278	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700279C0	279	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700280C0	280	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700281C0	281	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700282C0	282	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700283C0	283	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700284C0	284	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4608MH001680011700285C0	285	target La_Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00743	La Tranquila after DRT -15 mm standoff	460BMH00743001700286C00	286	autofocus sub-frame for target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		460BMH00743001700287C00	287	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		460BMH00743001700288C00	288	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460BMH00743001700289C00	289	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460BMH00743001700290C00	290	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460BMH00743001700291C00	291	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460BMH00743001700292C00	292	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460BMH00743001700293C00	293	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		460BMH00743001700294C00	294	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
460BMH00743001700295C00	295	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00171	Focus Merges	460BMH00171001700296R00	296	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 288-295 - best focus image product
		460BMH00171001700297S00	297	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 288-295 - range map product
		460BMH00171001700298R00	298	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 278-285 - best focus image product
		460BMH00171001700299S00	299	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 278-285 - range map product
		460BMH00171001700300R00	300	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 268-275 - best focus image product
		460BMH00171001700301S00	301	target La Tranquila - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 268-275 - range map product
		460BMH00171001700302R00	302	target Aqua Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 256-263 - best focus image product
		460BMH00171001700303S00	303	target Aqua Dulce - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 256-263 - range map product
		460BMH00171001700304R00	304	target Aqua Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 246-253 - best focus image product
		460BMH00171001700305S00	305	target Aqua Dulce - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 246-253 - range map product
		460BMH00171001700306R00	306	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 234-241 - best focus image product
		460BMH00171001700307S00	307	target Paposo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 234-241 - range map product
		460BMH00171001700308R00	308	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 224-231 - best focus image product
		460BMH00171001700309S00	309	target Paposo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4608 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 224-231 - range map product

updated: 31_July_2025

Sol 4611 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27 Jul 25
camera position	7
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

MAHLI imaged the target Tipnis and the DRT-brushed target Yura_Tuff.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Tipnis ~23 cm standoff	4611MH00190001700310C00	310	autofocus sub-frame for target Tipnis - standoff near 23 cm
		4611MH00190001700311C00	311	target Tipnis - standoff near 23 cm
mN00173	Tipnis stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	4611MH00173001700312C00	312	autofocus sub-frame for target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		4611MH00173001700313C00	313	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		4611MH00173001700314C00	314	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700315C00	315	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700316C00	316	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700317C00	317	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700318C00	318	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700319C00	319	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700320C00	320	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700321C00	321	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Tipnis stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	4611MH00173001700322C00	322	autofocus sub-frame for target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		4611MH00173001700323C00	323	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		4611MH00173001700324C00	324	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700325C00	325	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700326C00	326	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700327C00	327	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700328C00	328	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700329C00	329	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700330C00	330	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00173001700331C00	331	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Yura_Tuff after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4611MH00190001700332C00	332	autofocus sub-frame for target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4611MH00190001700333C00	333	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Yura_Tuff after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4611MH00168001700334C00	334	autofocus sub-frame for target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4611MH00168001700335C00	335	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4611MH00168001700336C00	336	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700337C00	337	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700338C00	338	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700339C00	339	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700340C00	340	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700341C00	341	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700342C00	342	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700343C00	343	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Yura_Tuff after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4611MH00168001700344C00	344	autofocus sub-frame for target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4611MH00168001700345C00	345	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4611MH00168001700346C00	346	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700347C00	347	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700348C00	348	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700349C00	349	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700350C00	350	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700351C00	351	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700352C00	352	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00168001700353C00	353	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Yura_Tuff after DRT ~15 mm standoff	4611MH00743001700354C00	354	autofocus sub-frame for target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4611MH00743001700355C00	355	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4611MH00743001700356C00	356	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00743001700357C00	357	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00743001700358C00	358	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00743001700359C00	359	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00743001700360C00	360	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4611MH00743001700361C00	361	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4611MH00743001700362C00	362	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4611MH00743001700363C00	363	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 28_July_2025

Sol 4612 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-Jul-2025
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4611 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4612MH0002270001700364900	364	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 356-363 - best focus image product
		4612MH0002270001700365500	365	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 356-363 - range map product
		4612MH0002270001700366900	366	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 346-353 - best focus image product
		4612MH0002270001700367500	367	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 346-353 - range map product
		4612MH0002270001700368900	368	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 336-343 - best focus image product
		4612MH0002270001700369500	369	target Yura_Tuff - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 336-343 - range map product
		4612MH0002270001700370900	370	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 324-331 - best focus image product
		4612MH0002270001700371500	371	target Tipnis - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 324-331 - range map product
		4612MH0002270001700372900	372	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 314-321 - best focus image product
		4612MH0002270001700373500	373	target Tipnis - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4611 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 314-321 - range map product

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the – X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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